

ROADMAP

Rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems in the management of animal production

Research and Innovation action: H2020 – 817626

Call: H2020-SFS-2018-2

Type of action: Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Livestock production systems and respective levels of antimicrobial use in Europe and in selected non-European countries

Main authors: Massimo Canali*, Caetano Luiz Beber

(University of Bologna, Italy)

DELIVERABLE D1.2

Workpackage N°1

Due date: 30 June 2021

Dissemination level: Public

* Contact: massimo.canali2@unibo.it

Title: Livestock production systems and respective levels of AMU in Europe and in selected non-European countries

Main authors: Massimo Canali¹ and Caetano Luiz Beber¹

Other contributors: Maurizio Aragrande¹, Chloe Batie², Paolo Bosi¹, Gareth Enticott⁴, Muriel Figuié², Nicolas Fortane⁵, Flavie Goutard², Anne Hemonic⁶, Jonathan Hercule⁷, Fleur Hoorweg⁸, Hanne Kongsted⁹, Mogens Agerbo Krogh⁹, Gerardo Manfreda¹, Sophie Molia², Bernadette Oehen¹⁰, Frédérique Pasquali¹, Eleonore Pommier¹¹, Heleen Prinsen¹², Stefaan Ribbens¹³, Nathalie Rousset⁷, Roberta Ruggieri¹, Orla Shortall¹⁴, Susanna Sternberg Lewerin¹⁵, Lee-Ann Sutherland¹⁴, Lea Tourneur¹⁶, Paolo Trevisi¹, Mette Vaarst⁹, Erwin Wauters³

Project leader: Nicolas Fortane⁵

Work Package leader and co-leader: Massimo Canali¹ and Erwin Wauters³

Deliverable responsible: Massimo Canali¹

¹University of Bologna (Italy)

²CIRAD (France)

³EV-ILVO (Belgium)

⁴Cardiff University (United Kingdom)

⁵INRAE (France)

⁶IFIP (France)

⁷ITAVI (France)

⁸WUR (Netherlands)

⁹Aarhus University (Denmark)

¹⁰FiBL (Switzerland)

¹¹IDELE (France)

¹²ZLTO (Netherlands)

¹³DGZ (Belgium)

¹⁴James Hutton Institute (United Kingdom)

¹⁵SLU (Sweden)

¹⁶ACTA (France)

Bologna, 30 June 2021

About the ROADMAP research project

The overall aim of ROADMAP is to **foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) will be achieved by enhancing antimicrobial decision-systems along the food and drug supply chains.** ROADMAP will focus on supporting animal health and welfare through prevention and health promotion actions.

AMR is recognized as a significant threat to global public health and food security. Overuse and improper use of AMs in many parts of the world contribute to the emergence and spread of AMR. Although human and animal health require AMs, it has been estimated that two thirds of the future AMU growth worldwide will be in animal production. Improving the management of AMU in farm animals is therefore a critical component of dealing with AMR and optimizing production in the livestock sector. Nevertheless, the variety of contexts of AMU in the livestock sector is a major challenge to managing AMR. **There is no “one-size-fits-all” solution to improve AMU and strategies must be contextually developed** (for instance, strategies used in the Danish pig industry are difficult to adapt and adopt in the French free-range poultry farming). Successful solutions must be combined and tailored to the production systems and the social and economic context in which they operate.

ROADMAP will meet three general objectives, in line with the EU AMR Action plan: i) **Rethink AM decision-systems and animal health management**; ii) **Develop options for encouraging prudent AMU in animal production**; iii) **Engage all actors in the food and drug supply chains in fostering a more prudent use of AMs.**

Project consortium

Part . N°	Participant organisation name (acronym)	Country
1	Institut National de recherche pour l’agriculture, l’alimentation et l’environnement (INRAE) **	France
2	Association de coordination technique agricole (ACTA) ***	France
3	Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD) **	France
4	University of Liverpool (ULIV) *	United Kingdom
5	Cardiff University (CU) *	United Kingdom
6	James Hutton Institute (HUT) **	United Kingdom
7	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna (UNIBO) *	Italy
8	Aarhus Universitet (AU) *	Denmark
9	Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw en Visserijonderzoek (EV-ILVO) **	Belgium
10	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL) **	Switzerland
11	Stichting Wageningen Research (WR) *	Netherlands
12	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) *	Sweden
13	Southern Agriculture and Horticulture Organization (ZLTO) ***	Netherlands
14	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders (EFFAB) ****	Netherlands
15	Fundacion Empresa Universidad Gallega (FEUGA) ****	Spain
16	Dierengezondheidszorg Vlaanderen (DGZ) ***	Belgium
17	INRAE Transfert (IT) ****	France

* *Universities/veterinary schools*

** *Research institutes specialized in both fundamental and applied agricultural and veterinary sciences*

*** *Public and private advisory services Organisations*

**** *Knowledge transfer and Innovation organisations*

Table of contents

ABOUT THE ROADMAP RESEARCH PROJECT	3
PROJECT CONSORTIUM	4
TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
LIST OF TABLES.....	9
LIST OF FIGURES.....	12
LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	14
1 SUMMARY.....	15
2 INTRODUCTION	18
3 THE COLLECTION OF ANTIMICROBIAL USE DATA IN LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION SYSTEMS: METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS	20
3.1 LITERATURE REVIEW AND COLLECTION OF EXISTING STATISTICS AND ESTIMATIONS AT GLOBAL, EUROPEAN, AND COUNTRY LEVELS	20
3.2 CHARACTERIZATION OF CASE STUDIES’ LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION SYSTEMS AND IDENTIFICATION OF DATA AVAILABLE	20
3.3 COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS OF AM USE DATA IN CASE STUDIES’ FARMS	21
4 DATA AND TRENDS OF ANTIMICROBIAL USE IN LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION SYSTEMS.....	23
4.1 GLOBAL DATA AND TRENDS	23
4.2 DATA AND TRENDS FROM RELEVANT COUNTRIES OUTSIDE EUROPE	25
4.2.1 JAPAN	25
4.2.2 UNITE STATES OF AMERICA	27
4.2.3 AUSTRALIA.....	29
4.3 DATA AND TRENDS FROM EUROPEAN COUNTRIES.....	31
4.3.1 INDICATOR 1 – AMU IN THE HUMAN SECTOR	32
4.3.2 INDICATOR 2 – AMU IN THE ANIMAL SECTOR	33
4.3.3 INDICATOR 3 – AMR IN THE HUMAN SECTOR	34
4.3.4 ESVAC DATA AND FARM TO FORK TARGETS OF EUROPEAN COUNTRIES.....	36
4.3.5 NATIONAL AMU MONITORING IN EU COUNTRIES	39
4.3.5.1 Belgium.....	39
4.3.5.2 Denmark.....	44
4.3.5.3 Netherlands.....	47

4.3.5.4	Sweden.....	51
5	<u>CASE STUDY ANALYSIS: PIG PRODUCTION IN DENMARK</u>	55
5.1	CONVENTIONAL INDOOR PIG PRODUCTION	55
5.1.1	BACKGROUND	55
5.1.2	METHODS	55
5.1.3	RESULTS.....	56
5.2	ORGANIC PIG PRODUCTION SYSTEM	58
5.2.1	BACKGROUND	58
5.2.2	METHODS	59
5.2.3	RESULTS.....	60
5.3	CONVENTIONAL FREE-RANGE SYSTEM.....	62
5.3.1	BACKGROUND	62
5.3.2	METHODS	62
5.3.3	RESULTS.....	63
5.4	COMPARISON OF PIG PRODUCTION SYSTEMS IN DENMARK.....	64
6	<u>CASE STUDY ANALYSIS: DAIRY PRODUCTION IN DENMARK</u>	66
6.1	BACKGROUND	66
6.1.1	CONVENTIONAL DAIRY PRODUCTION	66
6.1.2	ORGANIC DAIRY PRODUCTION	66
6.2	METHODS	66
6.3	RESULTS	68
6.4	COMPARISON OF CATTLE PRODUCTION SYSTEMS IN DENMARK	69
7	<u>CASE STUDY ANALYSIS: PIG, POULTRY, AND DAIRY COWS PRODUCTION IN FRANCE.....</u>	71
7.1	MONITORING AMU IN FRENCH FARMS	71
7.1.1	AMU REDUCTION TARGETS FOR FARMS.....	71
7.1.2	THE ANSES REPORTING.....	71
7.1.3	IMPROVING AMU MONITORING IN FRENCH FARMS.....	75
7.2	AMU IN FRENCH DAIRY PRODUCTION	77
7.2.1	METHODS	77
7.2.2	CONVENTIONAL PRODUCTION SYSTEMS	78
7.2.2.1	Description of the sample – conventional farms	78
7.2.3	ORGANIC PRODUCTION SYSTEMS	80
7.2.3.1	Description of the sample – organic farms	80
7.2.4	HEALTH INDICATORS OF FARMS IN CONVENTIONAL AND ORGANIC DAIRY PRODUCTION SYSTEMS.....	82
7.2.5	RESULTS.....	84
7.2.6	DISCUSSION	85
7.3	AMU IN FRENCH PIG PRODUCTION.....	86
7.3.1	METHODS	86
7.3.2	RESULTS.....	87

7.3.2.1	General characteristic of the farms.....	87
7.3.2.2	Type of treatment	89
7.3.2.3	Evolution of AMU over the past 3 years and in the next 3 years.....	89
7.3.2.4	Means of actions to decrease AMU in the next 3 years	90
7.4	AMU IN FRENCH POULTRY PRODUCTION	92
7.4.1	SECTOR CHARACTERISTICS	92
7.4.1.1	Production trends for poultry meat in France	92
7.4.1.2	Broiler segmentation.....	92
7.4.1.3	Broiler performances	93
7.4.1.4	Broiler market	94
7.4.2	METHODS	95
7.4.3	RESULTS.....	96
7.4.3.1	Structural data of poultry farms.....	96
7.4.3.2	Production performances of the poultry farms	98
7.4.3.3	Ventilation management and bedding practices.....	99
7.4.3.4	AMU according to different typologies of POs and farms	101
7.4.3.5	Characteristics of antimicrobial treatment.....	102
7.4.4	DISCUSSION: COMPARISON OF POULTRY PRODUCTION SYSTEMS IN FRANCE	103
8	<u>CASE STUDY ANALYSIS: PIG PRODUCTION IN ITALY</u>	<u>106</u>
8.1	INTRODUCTION.....	106
8.2	AMU IN ITALIAN PIG PRODUCTION	107
8.2.1	FIRST PIG CASE STUDY, PORCINE REPRODUCTIVE AND RESPIRATORY SYNDROME (PRRS)	107
8.2.1.1	Background.....	107
8.2.1.2	Methods	108
8.2.1.3	Results and conclusions	108
8.2.2	SECOND CASE STUDY, AB-FREE VS CONVENTIONAL PRODUCTION SYSTEMS.....	109
8.2.2.1	Background.....	109
8.2.2.2	Methods	109
8.2.2.3	Results and conclusions	109
9	<u>CASE STUDY ANALYSIS: POULTRY PRODUCTION IN ITALY</u>	<u>110</u>
9.1	BACKGROUND	110
9.2	METHODS	111
9.3	RESULTS	111
10	<u>CASE STUDY ANALYSIS: VIETNAM.....</u>	<u>113</u>
10.1	POULTRY PRODUCTION IN VIETNAM.....	113
10.1.1	QUANTIFICATION OF AMU FROM THE LITERATURE	113
10.1.2	DISEASES AND STAGES IN WHICH AMS ARE MORE USED	113
10.2	CASE STUDY, INTENSIVE PRODUCTION SYSTEM	113
10.2.1	BACKGROUND	113

10.2.2	METHODS	114
10.2.3	RESULTS.....	115
10.2.3.1	Clustering	115
10.2.3.2	Results of the “contract” farms associated with ABU patterns group.....	117
10.2.3.3	Results of the “family commercial” groups associated with the ABU patterns “independent” and “drugstore”	117
10.2.3.4	Results of the “household” farms associated with ABU pattern group “drugstore”	117
10.3	CASE STUDY, ORGANIC PRODUCTION SYSTEM	118
10.3.1	BACKGROUND	118
10.3.2	METHODS	118
10.3.3	RESULTS.....	119
10.3.4	COMPARISON OF POULTRY PRODUCTION SYSTEMS IN VIETNAM	119
11	<u>CONCLUSIONS</u>	<u>121</u>
12	<u>REFERENCES</u>	<u>122</u>

List of Tables

TABLE 3-1 ROADMAP PROJECT CASE STUDIES SCHEME	21
TABLE 4-1 TOTAL SALES OF VETERINARY ANTIMICROBIALS (TONNES OF ACTIVE CONSTITUENT), BY ANIMAL TYPE AS ESTIMATED (JULY 2005 TO JUNE 2010) IN AUSTRALIA (SOURCE: APVMA)	30
TABLE 4-2 TOTAL SALES OF VETERINARY ANTIMICROBIALS (TONNES OF ACTIVE CONSTITUENT) USED IN FOOD ANIMALS, BY SPECIES AND YEAR (JULY 2005 TO JUNE 2010) IN AUSTRALIA (SOURCE: APVMA)	30
TABLE 4-3 COMPOUND ANNUAL GROWTH RATE (CAGR) ON CONSUMPTION OF ANTIBACTERIALS FOR SYSTEMIC USE (ATC GROUP J01) IN THE COMMUNITY AND HOSPITAL SECTOR IN DDD PER 1000 INHABITANTS AND PER DAY FOR THE WHOLE SERIES, SINCE 2006 AND THE LAST 5 YEARS.....	33
TABLE 4-4 COMPOUND ANNUAL GROWTH RATE SALES IN MG/PCU OF ACTIVE INGREDIENT OF VETERINARY ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS MARKETED MAINLY FOR FOOD-PRODUCING ANIMALS (INCLUDING HORSES) FOR THE WHOLE SERIES AND THE LAST 5 YEARS.....	34
TABLE 4-5 COMPOUND ANNUAL GROWTH RATE (CAGR) ON PERCENTAGE OF RESISTANT ISOLATES / TOTAL TESTED ISOLATES FOR THE WHOLE SERIES, SINCE 2006 AND THE LAST 5 YEARS.....	35
TABLE 4-6 COUNTRIES 2018 AM SALES AND F TO F TARGETS FOR 2030. EFFORTS EVENLY DISTRIBUTED AND COUNTRIES WEIGHTED BY GDP.....	37
TABLE 4-7 COUNTRIES 2018 AM SALES AND F TO F TARGETS FOR 2030. COUNTRIES WEIGHTED BY AREA, POPULATION, AND POPULATION DENSITY.....	39
TABLE 4-8 TOTAL TONNES PER ANTIBACTERIAL CLASS SOLD IN 2019 (SALES 2019) AND TOTAL TONNES USED IN PIGS, POULTRY AND VEAL CALVES (USE 2019). NEXT TO THE TONNES USED BY EACH SPECIES THE % THIS COVERS OF THE SALES DATA (% SALES) IS SHOWN (SOURCE: BELVET-SAC REPORT 2019)	42
TABLE 4-9 ANTIMICROBIAL USE (BD100-SPECIES) IN 2018 AND 2019 IN PIGS, POULTRY AND VEAL CALVES (SOURCE: BELVET-SAC REPORT 2019)	43
TABLE 4-10 ANTIMICROBIAL USE BY ANIMAL SPECIES AND AGE GROUP, KG ACTIVE COMPOUND, DENMARK (SOURCE: DANMAP)...	47
TABLE 4-11 YEARLY SALES OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR VETERINARY USE EXPRESSED AS KG OF ACTIVE SUBSTANCE PER CLASS ^A IN SWEDEN	53
TABLE 4-12 NUMBER OF BROILER FLOCKS TREATED WITH ANTIBIOTICS, AND TOTAL NUMBER OF FLOCKS SLAUGHTERED PER YEAR.....	53
TABLE 4-13 SALES OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR PIGS IN MG/KG SLAUGHTERED PIGS BY MODE OF ADMINISTRATION.....	54
TABLE 5-1 CONVENTIONAL INDOOR FARMS IN THE DANISH PIG CASE STUDY BASED ON A RANDOM SAMPLE OF PIG HERDS WITH EIGHTER MORE THAN 50 SOWS OR 100 WEANERS OR 100 FINISHERS.....	56
TABLE 5-2 ANTIMICROBIAL USE IN ADJUSTED DAILY DOSES (ADD) PER 100 ANIMALS PER DAY FROM 2016 TO 2020 FOR THE THREE AGE GROUPS: SOWS AND PIGLETS, WEANERS, AND FINISHERS IN A RANDOM SAMPLE OF 300 FARMS. THE AMU IS GIVEN AS AN OVERALL AVERAGE OF THE TOTAL USE DIVIDED BY THE TOTAL ANIMAL POPULATION. THE VALUE IN BRACKETS IS THE HERD-MEDIAN AMU	56
TABLE 5-3: ANTIMICROBIAL USE IN ADD/100 ANIMALS/DAY DISTRIBUTED ON THE DIFFERENT ORGAN SYSTEMS THE ANTIBIOTIC WAS PRESCRIBED FOR (ACROSS ALL YEARS)	57
TABLE 5-4: DISTRIBUTION OF THE ADJUSTED DAILY DOSES (ADD) IN PERCENTAGES WITHIN AGE GROUP AND YEAR ON THE WHO CLASSIFICATION OF ANTIBIOTIC IMPORTANCE. THE WHO CLASSIFICATION CONSISTS OF HIGHEST PRIORITY CRITICALLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (CIA*), CRITICALLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (CIA), HIGHLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (HIA) AND IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (IA).	57
TABLE 5-5 FOR COMPARISON OF THE THREE SYSTEMS: LEGAL REQUIREMENTS FOR HOUSING AND MEDICAL TREATMENT IN DANISH ORGANIC, CONVENTIONAL FREE-RANGE AND CONVENTIONAL INDOOR PIG PRODUCTION (ADOPTED FROM NIELSEN ET AL. 2021)	58
TABLE 5-6 ORGANIC FARMS IN THE DANISH PIG CASE STUDY BASED WITH EITHER MORE THAN 50 SOWS OR 100 WEANERS OR 100 FINISHERS	59
TABLE 5-7 ANTIMICROBIAL USE IN ADJUSTED DAILY DOSES (ADD) PER 100 ANIMALS PER DAY FROM 2016 TO 2020 FOR THE THREE AGE GROUPS: SOWS AND PIGLETS, WEANERS, AND FINISHERS IN THE ORGANIC FARMS. THE AMU IS GIVEN AS AN OVERALL AVERAGE OF THE TOTAL USE DIVIDED BY THE TOTAL ANIMAL POPULATION. THE VALUES IN BRACKETS ARE THE HERD-MEDIAN AMU	60
TABLE 5-8 ANTIMICROBIAL USE IN ADD/100 ANIMALS/DAY IN ORGANIC HERDS DISTRIBUTED ON THE DIFFERENT ORGAN SYSTEMS THE ANTIBIOTIC WAS PRESCRIBED FOR (ACROSS ALL YEARS)	60
TABLE 5-9 DISTRIBUTION OF THE ADJUSTED DAILY DOSES (ADD) IN PERCENTAGES WITHIN AGE GROUP AND YEAR ON THE WHO CLASSIFICATION OF ANTIBIOTIC IMPORTANCE IN ORGANIC PIG HERDS. THE WHO CLASSIFICATION CONSISTS OF HIGHEST	

PRIORITY CRITICALLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (CIA*), CRITICALLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (CIA), HIGHLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (HIA) AND IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (AI).....	61
TABLE 5-10 CONVENTIONAL FREE-RANGE FARMS IN THE DANISH PIG CASE STUDY BASED WITH EIGHTER MORE THAN 50 SOWS OR 100 WEANERS OR 100 FINISHERS	62
TABLE 5-11 ANTIMICROBIAL USE IN ADJUSTED DAILY DOSES (ADD) PER 100 ANIMALS PER DAY FROM 2016 TO 2020 FOR THE THREE AGE GROUPS: SOWS AND PIGLETS, WEANERS AND FINISHERS IN THE CONVENTIONAL FREE-RANGE FARMS. THE AMU IS GIVEN AS AN OVERALL AVERAGE OF THE TOTAL USE DIVIDED BY THE TOTAL ANIMAL POPULATION. THE VALUES IN BRACKETS ARE THE HERD-MEDIAN AMU	63
TABLE 5-12 ANTIMICROBIAL USE IN ADD/100 ANIMALS/DAY IN CONVENTIONAL FREE-RANGE HERDS DISTRIBUTED ON THE DIFFERENT ORGAN SYSTEMS THE ANTIBIOTIC WAS PRESCRIBED FOR (ACROSS ALL YEARS)	63
TABLE 5-13 DISTRIBUTION OF THE ADJUSTED DAILY DOSES (ADD) IN PERCENTAGES WITHIN AGE GROUP AND YEAR ON THE WHO CLASSIFICATION OF ANTIBIOTIC IMPORTANCE IN CONVENTIONAL FREE-RANGE PIG HERDS. THE WHO CLASSIFICATION CONSISTS OF HIGHEST PRIORITY CRITICALLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (CIA*), CRITICALLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (CIA), HIGHLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (HIA) AND IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (AI).....	64
TABLE 6-1 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE DANISH CONVENTIONAL AND ORGANIC DAIRY HERDS BASED ON HERDS WITH MORE THAN 50 COW-YEAR ANNUALLY.....	67
TABLE 6-2 ANTIMICROBIAL USE IN GRAMS OF ANTIBIOTIC ACTIVE SUBSTANCE PER YEAR-ANIMAL FROM 2016 TO 2020 FOR TWO AGE GROUPS. THE AMU IS GIVEN AS AN OVERALL AVERAGE OF THE TOTAL USE DIVIDED BY THE TOTAL NUMBER OF ANIMAL YEAR. THE VALUES IN BRACKETS IS THE HERD-MEDIAN AMU	68
TABLE 6-3 ANTIMICROBIAL USE IN GRAMS OF ACTIVE SUBSTANCE PER ANIMAL YEAR DISTRIBUTED ON THE DIFFERENT ORGAN SYSTEMS THE ANTIBIOTIC WAS PRESCRIBED FOR.....	68
TABLE 6-4 DISTRIBUTION OF THE AMOUNT OF ACTIVE ANTIBIOTIC SUBSTANCES IN PERCENTAGES WITHIN AGE GROUP AND YEAR ON THE WHO CLASSIFICATION OF ANTIBIOTIC IMPORTANCE IN THE TWO PRODUCTION SYSTEMS. THE WHO CLASSIFICATION CONSISTS OF HIGHEST PRIORITY CRITICALLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (CIA*), CRITICALLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (CIA), HIGHLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (HIA) AND IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIALS (AI).....	69
TABLE 7-1 CHARACTERISTICS OF 8 DAIRY CONVENTIONAL FARMS SAMPLED IN FRANCE	78
TABLE 7-2 COW HOUSING SYSTEM AND MILKING SYSTEM OF CONVENTIONAL DAIRY FARMS IN FRANCE	79
TABLE 7-3 AREA AND FEEDING INDICATORS OF CONVENTIONAL DAIRY FARMS IN FRANCE	80
TABLE 7-4 CHARACTERISTICS OF 6 DAIRY ORGANIC FARMS SAMPLED IN FRANCE	80
TABLE 7-5 AREA AND FEEDING INDICATORS OF DAIRY ORGANIC FARMS IN FRANCE	81
TABLE 7-6 HEALTH INDICATORS OF CONVENTIONAL DAIRY FARMS IN FRANCE.....	82
TABLE 7-7 HEALTH INDICATORS OF ORGANIC DAIRY FARMS IN FRANCE	83
TABLE 7-8 ANTIMICROBIAL CONSUMPTION IN CONVENTIONAL AND ORGANIC FARMS	84
TABLE 7-9 GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FARMS INCLUDED IN THE SAMPLE.....	87
TABLE 7-10 NUMBER OF FARMS TREATING THEIR PIGS IN A PREVENTIVE OR METAPHYLACTIC WAY	89
TABLE 7-11 NUMBER OF FARMS DECLARING THAT THEIR AMU WILL STAGNATE, DECREASE, INCREASE	89
TABLE 7-12 NUMBER OF FARMS DECLARING IF A DECREASE OF AMU IN THE NEXT 3 YEARS IS POSSIBLE	90
TABLE 7-13 NUMBER OF FARMS WITH AN INTEREST IN THE CITED MEANS OF ACTION TO DECREASE AMU IN THE NEXT 3 YEARS	90
TABLE 7-14. AVERAGE PRODUCTION PERFORMANCES FOR CONVENTIONAL BROILER PRODUCTION IN FRANCE FOR 2019 – SOURCE: ITAVI	93
TABLE 7-15. PRODUCTION COST AT FARM GATE FOR CONVENTIONAL BROILER PRODUCTION (EXCLUDING LABOUR) – SOURCE: ITAVI.....	94
TABLE 7-16. FRENCH POULTRY MEAT SUPPLY-DEMAND TABLE. EXPRESSED IN 1000 T-CWE – SOURCE: ITAVI BASED ON SSP, CUSTOMS.....	94
TABLE 7-17. DISTRIBUTION OF THE FARMS INCLUDED IN THE STUDY ACCORDING TO THE TYPOLOGY OF POS IN RELATION TO "AM FREE LABEL MARKET" (80 FARMS SAMPLE)	96
TABLE 7-18. FARMS SIZE ACCORDING TO THE TYPOLOGY OF POS IN RELATION TO "ANTIMICROBIAL FREE LABEL MARKET" (80 FARMS SAMPLE).....	96
TABLE 7-19. SIZE OF FARMS ACCORDING TO THEIR BELONGING TO AN "ANTIMICROBIAL FREE LABEL" (15 FARMS SAMPLE).	97
TABLE 7-20. SURFACE AREA OF POULTRY HOUSES IN WHICH FLOCKS WERE MONITORED FOR THE PURPOSES OF THE AVIAN COLIBACILLOSIS SURVEY (80 FARMS SAMPLE)	97
TABLE 7-21. SURFACE AREA OF POULTRY HOUSES (15 FARMS SAMPLE).....	97

TABLE 7-22. AVERAGE PRODUCTION PERFORMANCES OF FLOCKS WERE MONITORED FOR THE PURPOSES OF THE AVIAN COLIBACILLOSIS SURVEY (80 FARMS SAMPLE)	98
TABLE 7-23. DISTRIBUTION OF 15 FARMS SAMPLE ACCORDING TO TYPE OF PRODUCTION.....	98
TABLE 7-24. AVERAGE PRODUCTION PERFORMANCES OF THE HEAVY BROILER PRODUCTION INTO THE 15 FARMS SAMPLE.....	99
TABLE 7-25. AMBIENT AIR PARAMETERS REGULATION SYSTEM OF POULTRY HOUSES IN WHICH FLOCKS WERE MONITORED FOR THE PURPOSES OF THE AVIAN COLIBACILLOSIS SURVEY (80 FARMS SAMPLE).....	99
TABLE 7-26. FLOOR AND BEDDING LITTER OF POULTRY HOUSES IN WHICH FLOCKS WERE MONITORED FOR THE PURPOSES OF THE AVIAN COLIBACILLOSIS SURVEY (80 FARMS SAMPLE)	100
TABLE 7-27. FLOOR AND BEDDING LITTER OF POULTRY HOUSES (15 FARM SAMPLE).....	101
TABLE 7-28. AMU OF MONITORED FLOCKS FOR THE PURPOSES OF THE AVIAN COLIBACILLOSIS SURVEY (80 FARMS SAMPLE).....	101
TABLE 7-29. AMU OF 15 FARMS SAMPLE IN THE LAST PAST YEARS (2020)	102
TABLE 7-30. TREND OF AMU FOR THE 15 FARMS SAMPLE.....	102
TABLE 7-31. SUM UP OF PRINCIPAL STRUCTURAL DATA AND PRODUCTION PERFORMANCES OF POULTRY FARMS, AS WELL AS PRINCIPAL CHARACTERISTICS OF POULTRY HOUSES OF THE TWO SAMPLES (80 FARMS AND 15 FARMS), ACCORDING TO THE ENGAGEMENT OR NOT IN AN "AM FREE LABEL"	105
TABLE 9-1 COSTS OF MEDICATION PER KG OF LIVE ANIMAL REARED IN CONVENTIONAL FARMS, 2016-2020	111
TABLE 9-2 COST OF MEDICATION PER KG OF LIVE ANIMAL REARED IN AB FREE FARMS, 2016-2020	111
TABLE 9-3 PRODUCTION PERFORMANCES AND TOTAL PRODUCTION COSTS OF CONVENTIONAL FARMS, 2016-2020.....	112
TABLE 9-4 PRODUCTION PERFORMANCES AND TOTAL PRODUCTION COSTS OF AB FREE FARMS, 2016-2020	112
TABLE 10-1: DESCRIPTION OF THE THREE GROUP ANTIBIOTIC USAGE PATTERN OBTAINED AFTER A MCA AND HC ON 18 AB USAGE VARIABLES.....	115
TABLE 10-2 DESCRIPTION OF THE THREE GROUP FARMING GROUP OBTAINED AFTER A MCA AND HCA AND THE ASSOCIATION WITH ABU PATTERNS.....	116

List of Figures

FIGURE 4-1 ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS REPORTED (MG)/ANIMAL BIOMASS (KG) TREND 2015 TO 2017	24
FIGURE 4-2 TOTAL ESTIMATED TONNES OF AMU AND BIOMASS OF ANIMALS IN THE WORLD. TREND 2015 TO 2017.	25
FIGURE 4-3 AMOUNTS OF ANTIMICROBIALS IN TERMS OF ACTIVE INGREDIENTS USED IN JAPAN PER SECTOR. TREND 2013 TO 2016 (SOURCE: JVARM).....	26
FIGURE 4-4 DOMESTIC SALES AND DISTRIBUTION OF MEDICALLY IMPORTANT ANTIMICROBIAL DRUGS FOR USE IN FOOD-PRODUCING ANIMALS IN USA (UPPER). REPORTED BY SPECIES-SPECIFIC ESTIMATED SALES (BOTTOM) (SOURCE: FDA)	28
FIGURE 4-5 ANTIMICROBIAL DRUGS APPROVED FOR USE IN FOOD-PRODUCING ANIMALS IN USA. ACTIVELY MARKETED 2010-2019. DOMESTIC SALES AND DISTRIBUTION DATA. REPORTED BY MEDICAL IMPORTANCE AND DRUG CLASS (SOURCE: FDA)	29
FIGURE 4-6 CONSUMPTION OF ANTIBACTERIALS FOR SYSTEMIC USE (ATC GROUP J01) IN THE COMMUNITY AND HOSPITAL SECTOR IN DDD PER 1000 INHABITANTS AND PER DAY. SOURCE ECDC.	33
FIGURE 4-7 SALES IN MG/PCU OF ACTIVE INGREDIENT OF VETERINARY ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS MARKETED MAINLY FOR FOOD- PRODUCING ANIMALS (INCLUDING HORSES). SOURCE EMA/ESVAC.	34
FIGURE 4-8 PERCENTAGE OF RESISTANT ISOLATES / TOTAL TESTED ISOLATES. SOURCE ECDC.	35
FIGURE 4-9 TOTAL MG OF ACTIVE SUBSTANCE USED PER KG BIOMASS PRODUCED IN BELGIUM (SOURCE: BELVET-SAC REPORT 2019)	41
FIGURE 4-10 TONNES ACTIVE SUBSTANCE OF PHARMACEUTICALS, MEDICATED PREMIXES AND ZNO USED IN 2019 PER SANITEL-MED ANIMAL CATEGORY	42
FIGURE 4-11 EVOLUTION OF THE MEDIAN OF THE BD100-DISTRIBUTION IN THE 2018-2019 CORE REFERENCE POPULATION OF EACH SANITEL-MED ANIMAL CATEGORY. ZERO-USE FARMS WERE EXCLUDED FOR THE ANALYSIS (SOURCE: BELVET-SAC REPORT 2019	43
FIGURE 4-12 NUMBER OF TREATMENT DAYS WITH THE DIFFERENT ANTIMICROBIAL CLASSES AND PERCENTAGE OF THE TOTAL NUMBER OF TREATMENT DAYS PER SPECIES IN 2018 AND 2019. NUMBERS/PERCENTAGES NOT SHOWN ARE CLASSES WHERE USE WAS BELOW 1% OF TREATMENT DAYS IN 2018 AND 2019 (SOURCE: BELVET-SAC REPORT 2019)	44
FIGURE 4-13 PRESCRIBED ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS FOR HUMANS AND ALL ANIMAL SPECIES, TONNES OF ACTIVE COMPOUND, DENMARK (SOURCE: DANMAP)	45
FIGURE 4-14 DISTRIBUTION OF LIVE BIOMASS AND ANTIMICROBIAL CONSUMPTION IN MAIN ANIMAL SPECIES, TONNES, DENMARK (SOURCE: DANMAP)	46
FIGURE 4-15 LONG-TERM DEVELOPMENTS IN ANTIBIOTIC USE ACCORDING TO LEI WAGENINGEN UR DATA (IN DD/AY, FOR 2004 TO 2010) AND SDA DATA (IN DDDANAT, FOR 2011 TO 2019), AS SPLINE CURVES WITH POINT ESTIMATES FOR EACH YEAR WITH 95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (SOURCE SDA)	49
FIGURE 4-16 DEVELOPMENTS IN SALES OF ANTIBIOTICS OVER THE 1999-2019 PERIOD, IN NUMBER OF KILOGRAMS OF ACTIVE SUBSTANCES SOLD (x1,000) (SOURCE: FIDIN, SDA), BY MAIN PHARMACOTHERAPEUTIC GROUP IN NETHERLANDS	50
FIGURE 4-17 LONG-TERM DEVELOPMENTS IN THE NUMBERS OF KILOGRAMS OF ACTIVE SUBSTANCES SOLD AND USED. THE NUMBERS OF KILOGRAMS USED IN THE INDIVIDUAL MONITORED LIVESTOCK SECTORS ARE SHOWN. ALSO INCLUDED ARE THE ANNUAL NUMBERS OF KILOGRAMS OF LIVE WEIGHT FOR THE LIVESTOCK SECTORS THAT WERE SUBJECTED TO SDA MONITORING IN 2019	51
FIGURE 4-18 SALES OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR ANIMALS EXPRESSED AS MG PER POPULATION CORRECTION UNIT (PCU)	52
FIGURE 4-19 SALES OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR PIGS EXPRESSED AS DCDVET/KG SLAUGHTERED PIGS AND DCDSE/KG SLAUGHTERED PIGS..	54
FIGURE 7-1 COMPARISON OF ALEA BY SPECIES (A) CATTLE, (B) PIGS, (C) POULTRY BETWEEN 2011 AND 2019 (ANSES, 2020)	73
FIGURE 7-2 COMPARISON OF ALEA BY SPECIES (A) CATTLE, (B) PIGS, (C) POULTRY BETWEEN 2011 AND 2019 (ANSES, 2020)	74
FIGURE 7-3 FRENCH MAP OF DAIRY PRODUCTION CONCENTRATION	77
FIGURE 7-4 CLASSES OF ANTIMICROBIALS PURCHASED BY THE DAIRY FARMS IN FRANCE	85
FIGURE 7-5 CONSUMPTION OF ANTIBIOTICS PER CLASSES (GODET, 2014-2015)	86
FIGURE 7-6. FRENCH PRODUCTION OF POULTRY MEAT BY SPECIES SINCE 1990 (SOURCE : ITAVI BASED ON SSP)	92
FIGURE 7-7. BROILER SLAUGHTERING BY PRODUCTION TYPE IN 2018 - SOURCE: ITAVI BASED ON SSP	93
FIGURE 7-8. DISTRIBUTION OF THE FLOCKS INCLUDED IN THE STUDY ACCORDING TO THE DATE OF THE BEGINNING OF REARING PERIOD (80 FARMS SAMPLE)	95
FIGURE 7-9. FREQUENCY OF ANTIMICROBIAL TREATMENT REASON	103
FIGURE 7-10. DISTRIBUTION OF THE AGE OF FLOCK AT THE START OF ANTIMICROBIAL TREATMENT	103
FIGURE 10-1: MAP OF THE STUDY ZONE HANOI PROVINCE (RED RIVER REGION) AND LONG AN (MEKONG DELTA REGION)	114

FIGURE 10-2: PROJECTION OF THE 111 VIETNAMESE CHICKEN FARMS THAT USE AB ON THE FIRST TWO DIMENSIONS WITHIN THE 3 GROUPS IDENTIFIED THROUGH HC REALIZED ON FARMING PRACTICES VARIABLES.....	117
--	-----

List of acronyms and abbreviations

AB	Antibiotic
AC	Active compound
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
AMU	Antimicrobial Use
F	Fattening unit
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FDA	United States Food and Drug Administration
GLASS	Global Antimicrobial Surveillance System from the WHO
HIC	High Income Countries
JVARM	Japanese Veterinary Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring System
LMIC	Low and Middle income Countries
NAP	National Action Plan
OIE	World Organisation for Animal Health
PRRS	Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
W	Weaning unit
WHO	World Health Organization
WTO	World Trade Organization

1 Summary

The OIE reports show an increasing number of countries committed to collect and report their data on antimicrobials use (AMU) in animal production. It also reveals that every year, more and more countries refine their methods and report increasingly detailed data by antimicrobial classes, type of use, animal group, and type of administration. Nevertheless, there are still huge limitations and barriers to achieve full coverage with detailed information at global level.

The same is true also at the regional level, where large differences are found among countries inside the European Union (EU), the aggregate that presents the largest proportion of countries monitoring their AMU levels. Data from the ESVAC and national statistics reveal that some countries will face a much bigger challenge than others in order to comply with the new legislation in force from 2022, and with the EU Farm-to-Fork strategy that targets a 50% reduction in sales of antimicrobials for farmed animals by 2030.

For the 102 countries where the last OIE estimations were performed (2017), data show a global AMU in the order of 117.48 mg/kg (adjusted by reported coverage), with a decreasing trend from 2015.

The ESVAC reports also show a decreasing trend for the EU countries in the same period: 135,5 mg/PCU (2015 n=30); 124,6 mg/PCU (2016 n=30); 107,0 mg/PCU (2017 n=31)

Globally, only 41 countries in 2019 reported that they still use antimicrobials as growth promoters, a 14% decrease from 2015: 20 in Americas; 8 in Africa; 12 in Asia and Oceania; 1 in Europe. Only 20 of these had specific legislation to regulate their use. HCIAAs such as Colistin, Bacitracin, and Tylosin are still being used as AGPs in some countries. The estimated biomass coverage of the responding countries represents about 83% of the total global animal biomass in 2017. In 2014 the coverage was only 36%. Only 38 countries out of 133 published online reports on AMU, 31 being from In Europe. 49 countries were able to distinguish the data by animal groups (food producing, companions, terrestrial and aquatic). 40 countries distinguished their data by routes of administration. The most common administration is via oral route, especially for tetracyclines. Tetracyclines was the antimicrobial class the most reported for use (33.9%), followed by polypeptides (11.1%), Penicillins (10.9%) and Macrolides (10.4%) The total estimated animal biomass from the 102 countries in 2017 are 793,921 (1000 tonnes) (Figure 4-2), with bovine (41%), swine (21%) and poultry (18%) the most representatives. Aquaculture biomass represents 8%. 93,092 tonnes (adjusted by estimated coverage) of Antimicrobial Agents Intended for Use in Animals (AMU) were reported in 2017 by the 103 countries. 9 countries reported antimicrobial quantities from 2015 to 2017. Their total animal biomass has increased 1.2% during this time, with 6% increase in poultry. These countries also reported a -34% decrease in the mg/kg of antimicrobials for use in animals.

In Europe, ESVAC data show that Spain, Italy and Belgium are the largest veterinary AM consumers, while Sweden, UK and Denmark the lowest. The higher decreases in the consumption along the total time series has taken place in the UK, Netherlands, and France. This translates their efforts in reducing the total consumption. In the past five years, the sharpest decreases are found in UK, France and Belgium.

We have also compared the effort to be made by the different EU countries to comply with the current target of the Farm-to-Fork strategy, taking into account the livestock liveweight in the country, the human population, and the country land area. According to our estimations, Germany, which is the country with the highest value of PCU of animals with respect to the population density should make the biggest efforts in AM sales reduction. Belgium, Italy, Spain and Poland also need to contribute with large reductions. Regardless of the weighting system considered, countries such as Spain, Italy, Poland

have in any case to make large efforts in reducing their AMU sales, because of the current high sales values compared to the PCU present in the country.

The case studies presented in this report bring elements and data to the debates on a more prudent AMU in livestock production. Although differences in methods do not allow a plain comparison between the case studies, there are interesting findings that can be highlighted.

Livestock production systems that favour higher standards of animal welfare and health seem leading to a more prudent and lower antimicrobial use. This is the case of organic production systems: e.g., in the dairy production of France and Denmark, the Pork sector in Italy, the poultry sector in Vietnam, the conventional free-range and organic pork systems in Denmark.

Such systems provide increased welfare standards to animals. In the Danish pig case study, for example, AMU in the conventional farms is substantially more important than in the organic herds, especially for weaners, where it is 8-10 times higher. However, large AMU variations are found in farms within the examined production systems, and especially for free-range and organic there is a large proportion of farms with low or no AMU. Within all the three pig production systems assessed in Denmark, the AMU was primarily driven by gastro-intestinal problems in weaners. However, AMU resulted the very low in organic systems. It is also important to notice that the Highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA*) were used in considerable extend (>30%) in weaners in all production systems (as a proportion of all the antimicrobial doses used), and also in conventional finishers.

Still in Denmark, the AMU for cows in the conventional farms are substantially (3 times) larger than in the organic ones. For the conventional and organic herds, the AMU is primarily associated with udder diseases and in calves and young stock with gastro-intestinal and respiratory disease. For example, the AMU in grams of active substance per animal-year for udder diseases in conventional dairy farms is 13.62, while only 4.11 in organic farms. At the same time the AMU for diseases related to joint, limbs, claws, central nervous system, and skin, which could be associated to animal welfare, is 2.26 in conventional farms and only 1.17 for organic farms. It is also important to notice a drastic decrease in the highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA*) in 2020 in the Danish dairy organic production system, which is related to agreement of an industrial code that restricted the use of antibiotics to narrow-spectrum antibiotics.

In intensive systems, practices aiming the provision of enhanced comfort and welfare to the animals might lead to similar results in terms of reduced antimicrobial use. For example, reducing thermal stress and population density, increasing space and time in outdoor areas are practices that can also be considered. In this regard, better husbandry practices can contribute to fewer incidence of diseases, lower mortality, and less AMU, as shown by the poultry CS in France. In this regard, advanced technologies can be very useful to create a better environment. Automatic systems based on several sensors (temperature, moisture, eventually carbon dioxide) allow to control air intake flap, extractor fans and temperature, for example, are already common in French AB-free poultry production systems and help enhancing farm management and decreasing the AMU. Practices of prophylactic or metaphylactic use also disfavour AMU reduction, as evidenced by the pork Case study in France. Vaccination campaigns, despite expensive, can also highly contribute to AMU reduction as shown by the poultry CS in Italy.

AB free labels led by the industry and retailers can be an important driver of AMU reduction, especially in countries where governmental controls/legislation are less strict. Therefore, this report also highlights the impact that the end users, or consumers have in the reduction of antimicrobial use in the supply chains, such as evidenced in the poultry CS of Italy for example. When consumers choose to buy antibiotic free products in the shelves of supermarkets, retailers became prone to demand such

products to their suppliers, the processing companies. These are directly linked to the farmers through contracts of integration or supply and require animals to be raised without (or limited use) of antimicrobials. Companies (and public institutes in many cases) can provide farmers with financial incentives, training, access to equipment and tools needed for this purpose. Indeed, it is important that producers have the tools for change before implementing a new law/regulation. Strategies must be followed by resources.

Health expenditure seems to be higher in the conventional farms as well, like the case of pork production in France (or at least similar, like the poultry Case study in Italy). The mortality rates in the antibiotic free systems indicates that some farms succeed in using few antibiotics without increasing mortality of pigs. The 'averaged daily gain' and the 'feed conversion ratio' indexes from antibiotic-free farms in the Italian poultry case study and the French pork case study, also evidence that competitiveness is not harmed at the expenses of reduction in antimicrobial use.

2 Introduction

In 2019, the WHO listed AMR as one of the top ten threats to global health. A major driver of AMR is antimicrobial overuse and misuse. Evidence suggests that antimicrobial use in agriculture contributes to antimicrobial resistance in the pathogenic bacteria of humans, but the chain from cause to effect is long and complicated (Smith, Dushoff, and Jr 2005; Taylor, Latham, and woolhouse 2001; Tang et al. 2017).

The worsening of the problem of antimicrobial resistance in various countries in both humans and animals is growing awareness of the society to the use of antibiotics on farms. Such awareness is leading an increasing political support for counteraction actions in different spheres of the public administration. At the international level, since 2010 the WHO, FAO and OIE (the Tripartite organisations) started to take action and define strategies to coordinate global activities addressing health risks at the human-animal-ecosystems interfaces. This culminated in 2015 with the development of a Global Action Plan on AMR that invites countries to establish National Action Plans on AMR (NAPs). NAPs can address areas that are cross-cutting or focus on specific, relevant sectors, depending on the individual country's needs, but should ensure consistency and compliance with existing guidance and international standards. NAPs should be aligned with the WHO Global Action Plan and the FAO Action Plan on AMR.

The way antimicrobials are being used in animal farming is also evolving worldwide. Lately, it was observed that the global antimicrobial consumption is showing an upward trend, particularly in the LMICs, and although consumption in HICs is still considerably higher, this gap is rapidly converging (Klein et al. 2020; 2018; Van Boeckel et al. 2014).

Antimicrobial use in food animals is responsible for the highest share of the world's antimicrobial consumption. Recent projections also estimated a 69% increase of AMU in animal production between 2010 and 2030 generated by LMICs' growing meat consumption (Van Boeckel et al. 2015). This, while the use of antimicrobials in food animals already accounts for the largest share of antimicrobial use in the world (ECDC/EFSA/EMA 2017).

Actions to reduce antimicrobial use in livestock production are not only coming from the political sphere. Downstream in the agri-food supply chains, individuals have also started to change their purchasing habits. Mainly pushed by retailers who saw an opportunity in product differentiation (new label), an increasing number of consumers are purchasing *antibiotic free* livestock products and especially fresh meat. Such consumers would be willing to pay a premium price to buy fresh meat from animals raised without the use of antibiotics (Brewer and Rojas 2008; Lusk, Norwood, and Pruitt 2006). It's therefore observed a growing number of labels claiming antibiotic-free production emerging in EU retailers' shelves. Such demand also affects the whole supply chain's practices, where retailers start compelling their suppliers to deliver antibiotic-free products (Sneeringer et al. 2015). Thus, industry and farmers should adapt to these requirements and proceed with the necessary changes in their production systems. Here it's important to notice that "antibiotic free" is a selling label, but also all products produced with adherence to withdrawal periods are antibiotic free.

Therefore, the objective of this deliverable is to assess the levels of antimicrobial use (AMU) in the different livestock production systems (LPS) of Europe and selected non-European countries. The primary assumption here is that different LPS will lead to different levels of AMU. Recent studies evidenced the organic production systems (Smith-Spangler et al. 2012), AB-free production systems, intensive or free-range production systems (Nielsen et al. 2021) all might lead to different AMU levels.

This can be further extended to different farming and management practices in the same LPS. For instance different practices in terms of biosecurity and animal welfare (Nielsen et al. 2021), or simply general farming management (Willis and Chandler 2019; Poizat et al. 2017), can reflect on different levels of AMU in livestock production.

One of the main issues highlighted in the action plans (global, regional, institutional, or national) is the urgent need for reliable and useful data on AMU and AMR. Data that shows the real situations in each country, region, sector, and even farms. Without such data, it becomes difficult to design targeted and effective measures to address the problem. Concerned about such lack of reliable and good quality data, some actions at global, regional, national, and sectorial scale started to take place and some already existed. In this regard, the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) launched in 2016 the OIE Annual Report on Antimicrobial Agents Intended for Use in Animals reporting global AMU. Today it's in its fifth report (OIE 2021) and the number of participating countries is increasing year by year. The detailing of the data is also improved in every report.

In Europe, the European Commission requested the European Medicines Agency (EMA) to develop a harmonized approach for the collection and reporting of data on the use of antimicrobial agents in animals from EU and European Economic Area (EEA) Member States. EMA then established in April 2010 the European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption (ESVAC) (ESVAC 2020) project to collect information on how antimicrobial medicines are used in animals. The number of countries participating and the quality of collected data is also enhanced in every report. National monitoring systems of AMU were also developed by some countries, such as Denmark, Netherlands, Belgium, and Sweden among others, for example. Some even before the OIE and ESVAC initiatives.

Nevertheless, the collection and reporting of this data is considered as very difficult, since it involves different sectors, professionals, and methods. The OIE survey (OIE 2021) asked directly which were the main barriers for data collections among the surveyed countries, and these reported primarily a lack of regulatory framework, human resource constraints and lack of information technology (IT) tools to collect the data, perform calculations and analyse the antimicrobial quantities as important barriers for reporting quantitative. A lack of coordination/cooperation between national authorities and with private sector was also mentioned as been a problem. Different national methodologies or capacity to collect such information are also hindering deeper assessments. For instance, the source of data widely varies among countries and poses a huge problem, with sales data from the 'Wholesalers' and 'Marketing Authorisation Holders' as the source most reported in the last OIE report, and only one country reported farm level data.

Concerned about such difficulties, the ROADMAP deliverable D1.2 intends to bring further evidence and knowledge to the debates around AMU and AMR in the different livestock production systems with field data collected in 13 country case studies, 12 in Europe and 1 in Vietnam. Background data from the OIE, ESVAC reports, and 3 non-European countries are also presented and discussed. Furthermore, the EU Farm to Fork strategy foresees a reduction of 50% in AMU in farmed animals by 2030, but it does not indicate if and which individual targets should be set. This issue is also addressed in this report with the intention to contribute to the achievement of this target in a fairly and effective manner.

3 The collection of antimicrobial use data in livestock production systems: methodological aspects

3.1 Literature review and collection of existing statistics and estimations at Global, European, and country levels

A) *Literature review.* The literature review analysed the methodologies developed to estimate AM use in the different countries and LPSs. The review covered the main regional contexts and types of animal production with a particular focus on the countries and livestock species in the ROADMAP case studies.

The ROADMAP case-study (CS) Leaders provided an English version (or summary) of the methodological guidelines for official reporting on veterinary AM use in the respective CS countries, and any other relevant publication investigating the assessment of veterinary AM use.

B) *AM use statistics.* Available statistics of AM use at global, European, and country levels were collected. The aim of statistic data collection at country level was to produce comparable data of AM use by species for the main food producing animals in the ROADMAP countries.

The ROADMAP CS Leaders provided an English version of the last five national reports on AM use issued by their own countries.

3.2 Characterization of case studies' livestock production systems and identification of data available

Available European statistics on AM use in animal production provide data on AM sales or prescriptions, depending on the countries, per animal biomass unit (mg of active principle per kg of animal biomass). Animal biomass is calculated from different Eurostat or national statistics (number of livestock, slaughtered animals, and import and export of live animals) through standard weights (animal population correction units or PCU) for the different livestock categories. This method delivers data on the level of consumption of the different active principles compared with the total livestock biomass in each country but does not provide information relating to consumption for the different livestock species.

The European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption (ESVAC), the project of the European Medicine Agency (EMA) which collects this information, is developing a collection system providing data on AM use by livestock species in view of the implementation of the new European legislation on animal health. EU member states are required to set up national statistics reporting data on AM use by species over the 2022-2030 period. The countries providing data to ESVAC statistics also issue national annual reports, but only a limited number of them are able to deliver data on AM consumption by livestock species.

On these premises, the aim of quantifying current AM use in different production systems could rely on official data sources only to a limited extent and the contribution of ROADMAP partners and case study leaders to data supply was therefore crucial.

The ROADMAP project’s research activity is based on 26 case studies (CSs) differentiated per animal species, type of products, and livestock production systems, as indicated in the below scheme (Table 3-1):

- Case-study cluster 1, intensive and conventional production systems;
- Case-study cluster 2, alternative production systems:
 - o Organic and/or sustainable labels;
 - o Intensive systems with quality labels, such as welfare or AM-free standards;
- Case-study cluster 3, marginal production systems:
 - o Marginalized rural areas (with poor access to veterinary services, etc.);
 - o Marginal animals and/or workers (not considered as a priority in the farm management);
 - o Marginal regulatory framework (poor implementation, relevant presence of informal drug distribution channels, etc.).

Table 3-1 ROADMAP Project case studies scheme

Species	Cs intensive production systems	Cs alternative production systems	Cs marginal production systems	Total case studies
Pig	1. Belgium 2. Denmark 3. France 4. Italy	5. Denmark 6. France 7. Italy 8. Switzerland	9. Netherlands	9
Poultry	10. France 11. Italy 12. Sweden	13. France 14. Sweden	15. Netherlands 16. Mozambique 17. Vietnam	8
Dairy	18. Sweden 19. France	20. Denmark 21. France 22. Sweden	23. United kingdom	6
Beef	-	24. Switzerland	25. Belgium 26. United kingdom	3
Total case studies	9	10	7	26

Obs.: In red colour are highlighted the CSs that provided data for this report.

A study objective was to achieve a technical-economic characterization of the farms involved the ROADMAP CSs, deepen the knowledge on the application of biosecurity, animal health and welfare practices favouring a reduced use of antibiotics, and obtain information on the type of data related to AM use in the farms that can be delivered by the different CSs depending on the existing data sources and on the available project resources.

3.3 Collection and analysis of AM use data in case studies’ farms

The information achieved allowed collection and analysis of CS farm data on AM consumption. This subtask was developed into three stages:

- Designing the CS farm data collection and analysis;

-
- CS farm data collection;
 - CS farm data elaboration and analysis.

The design of CSs' data collection and analysis was elaborated in cooperation with the CS leaders, based on the type of data and the resources available, as well as in the COVID-19 constraints. In each country section below, the details of the methodologies for each CS is described.

4 Data and trends of antimicrobial use in livestock production systems

4.1 Global data and trends

This section uses data from the OIE Annual Reports on the Use of Antimicrobial Agents in Animals (OIE 2020; 2021) and its database. Created in the framework of the Global Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance, since 2016 this database provides information for the OIE reports. It's considered a milestone in the combat against AMR because it regroups the efforts in data collection on the use of antimicrobials from 160 countries. Although the data must be interpreted with caution, which rises from several uncertainties associated to the data collection, the OIE is refining its methodologies, developing a software (Excel Calculation Tool) and assisting its members for a more accurate data collection. The indicator reported in (antimicrobial agents reported (mg)/animal biomass (kg)) remains relevant for the purposes of comparison (e.g., over time and between regions). However, this indicator is less reliable/useful than calculating defined doses (some substances, especially CIAs weigh less per dose).

In the last report represents the fifth round of surveys, which were conducted in 2019, but the quantitative AMU data from 2017 is presented. 133 countries provided quantitative data on antimicrobials (against 89 in 2015, the first round). The OIE reports the AMU in animals in mg of antimicrobials per kg of animal biomass. For only 102 countries the animal biomass was calculated. 23 countries reported primarily a lack of regulatory framework, human resource constraints and lack of information technology (IT) tools to collect the data, perform calculations and analyse the antimicrobial quantities. Lack of coordination/cooperation between national authorities and with private sector was also mentioned as an important barrier for reporting quantitative data. Out of these, three are taking action to provide the data in the near future. The source of data widely varies among countries, with sales data from the 'Wholesalers' and 'Marketing Authorisation Holders' as the source most reported, and only one country reported farm level data. We can summarize their main results as:

- For the 102 countries where the calculation was performed in 2017 (Figure 4-1), the estimations show a global AMU in the order of **117.48 mg/kg** (adjusted by reported coverage), with a decreasing trend from 2015.
- The ESVAC report also shows a decreasing trend for the EU countries in the same period:
 - **135,5 mg/PCU** (2015 n=30); **124,6 mg/PCU** (2016 n=30); **107,0 mg/PCU** (2017 n=31)¹
- **42** from the 160 countries in 2019 reported that they still use antimicrobials as growth promoters (**AGPs**), a 14% decrease from 2017. Six countries indicated not been sure if AGPs were used in the country. It's important to notice that AGPs are usually not included in the total usage figures reported.
 - 20 in Americas; 8 in Africa; 12 in Asia and Oceania; 1 in Europe
 - Only 20 of these had specific legislation to regulate their use.
 - HCAs such as Colistin, Bacitracin, and Tylosin are still being used as AGPs in some countries
- The estimated biomass coverage of the responding countries represents about 83% of the total global animal biomass in 2017. In 2014 the coverage was only 36%.

¹ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/veterinary-regulatory/overview/antimicrobial-resistance/european-surveillance-veterinary-antimicrobial-consumption-esvac#annual-report-on-sales-of-veterinary-antibiotics-section>

- Only 38 countries out of 133 published online reports on AMU, 31 being from In Europe.
- 49 countries were able to distinguish the data by animal groups (food producing, companions, terrestrial and aquatic)

Figure 4-1 Antimicrobial agents reported (mg)/animal biomass (kg) trend 2015 to 2017

- 40 countries distinguished their data by routes of administration. The most common administration is via oral route, especially for tetracyclines.
- Tetracyclines was the antimicrobial class the most reported for use (33.9%), followed by polypeptides (11.1%), Penicillins (10.9%) and Macrolides (10.4%)
- The total estimated animal biomass from the 102 countries in 2017 are 793,921 (1000 tonnes) (Figure 4-2), with bovine (41%), swine (21%) and poultry (18%) the most representatives. Aquaculture biomass represents 8%.
- 93,092 tonnes (adjusted by estimated coverage) of Antimicrobial Agents Intended for Use in Animals (AMU) were reported in 2017 by the 103 countries.
- 69 countries reported antimicrobial quantities from 2015 to 2017.
 - Their total animal biomass has increased 1.2% during this time, with 6% increase in poultry.
 - These countries also reported a -34% decrease in the mg/kg of antimicrobials for use in animals.

Figure 4-2 Total estimated tonnes of AMU and biomass of animals in the world. Trend 2015 to 2017.

4.2 Data and trends from relevant countries outside Europe

We selected three countries, Japan, Australia, and the USA to present their AMU monitoring system in animal production and some results. These were selected based on the availability of the information and on geographical spread. Both Japan and USA do not publish their AMU sales data reported to the animals (biomass or PCU) produced in the country, therefore it's not possible to compare their data with other countries or regions. Their total sale data by classes of antimicrobials is shown in the following sections. USA also reports data species-specific.

4.2.1 Japan

A systematic data collection on antimicrobial consumption and antimicrobial-resistant bacteria from humans, animals, food and environment was conducted in Japan through a systematic One Health Survey². It offers a very detailed perspective of the situation in the country, and we could not verify why this program was discontinued. The Figure 4-3 reports the amounts of veterinary antimicrobials in terms of active ingredients in Japan per sector from 2013 to 2016, the last year reported. In summary:

- Total usage in 2016 was 1,804.3 tons, comprising 591.0 tons for human use, 669.7 tons for food-producing animals, 155.1 tons for aquatic animals, 6.7 tons for companion animals, 228.2 tons for antibiotic feed additives, and 153.6 tons for agrochemicals (Figure 4-3).
- In the period from 2013 to 2016, the volume of sales of veterinary antimicrobials ranged between 749.47 t and 832.56 t.
- Tetracyclines took up largest share in the overall volume of sales, accounting for 39.8 to 43.6%.
- Third-generation cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones, though important drugs for human medicine, accounted for less than 1% of overall volume of sales.

² Japanese Veterinary Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring System ([JVARM](#)).

- Cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones are not used as drugs for aquatic animals or as antimicrobial feed additives or agrochemicals. As third-generation cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones are critically important antimicrobials for human medicine, they are positioned as a second-line drug for food-producing animals and used with great caution, based on assessments by the Food Safety Commission of Japan of their impact on human health via food. Accordingly, they account for only a small proportion of antimicrobials used in animals. Third-generation cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones also are positioned as second-line drugs for companion animals and are consequently used with caution.

Figure 4-3 Amounts of antimicrobials in terms of active ingredients used in Japan per sector. Trend 2013 to 2016 (source: JVARM)

4.2.2 United States of America

In USA, the marketing authorization holders of approved animal drug containing an antimicrobial active ingredient must report to the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) the amount of each such ingredient in these drug products sold or distributed for use in food-producing animals. The FDA publishes since 2009 the [reports](#) containing the data gathered from AMU at national level. Based on the 2019 report, we can summarize the information as:

- In USA, until 2016 it was allowed to use ‘medically important antimicrobials’ as growth promoters (AGPs), e.g. for increased rate of weight gain or improved feed efficiency. From 2017 only ‘not medically important antimicrobials’ are still allowed to be used for production purposes.
- Domestic sales and distribution of medically important antimicrobials approved for use in food producing animals increased by 3% between 2018 and 2019 (Figure 4-4).
- The trend over time indicates that ongoing efforts to support the reduction on antimicrobial usage are having an impact: sales and distribution are down 25% since 2010 and down 36% since 2015, which was the peak year of sales.
- Tetracyclines accounted for 67%, penicillins for 12%, macrolides for 8%, sulfas for 5%, aminoglycosides for 5%, lincosamides for 2%, cephalosporins for less than 1%, and fluoroquinolones for less than 1% (Figure 4-5).
- In 2019, an estimated 41% was intended for use in cattle, an estimated 42% intended for use in swine, an estimated 10% intended for use in turkeys, an estimated 3% intended for use in chickens, and an estimated 4% intended for use in other species/unknown (Figure 4-4).

Figure 4-4 Domestic Sales and distribution of medically important antimicrobial drugs for use in food-producing animals in USA (upper). Reported by species-specific estimated sales (bottom) (source: FDA)

¹ Includes antimicrobial drug applications that are approved and labeled for use in both food-producing animals (e.g., cattle and swine) and nonfood-producing animals (e.g., dogs and horses).
² kg = kilogram of active ingredient. Antimicrobial class includes drugs of different molecular weights, with some drugs labeled in different salt forms. Antimicrobials that are labeled in International Units (IU) (e.g., Penicillins) were converted to kg.
³ Not reported because there were fewer than three distinct sponsors actively marketing products domestically in 2009 through 2012.
⁴ Guidance for Industry #213 states that all antimicrobial drugs and their associated classes listed in Appendix A of FDA’s Guidance for Industry #152 are considered “medically important” in human medical therapy.
⁵ NIR = Not Independently Reported. Antimicrobial classes for which there were fewer than three distinct sponsors actively marketing products domestically are not independently reported. These classes include the following: Amphenicols, Diaminopyrimidines, Fluoroquinolones (excluding 2013 through 2019), Polymyxins (excluding 2012 and 2013), and Streptogramins.
⁶ Not Medically Important refers to any antimicrobial class not listed in Appendix A of FDA’s Guidance for Industry #152.
⁷ NIR = Not Independently Reported. Antimicrobial classes for which there were fewer than three distinct sponsors are not independently reported. These classes include the following: Aminocoumarins, Glycolipids, Orthosomycins (excluding 2010 through 2015), Pleuromutilins, Polypeptides, and Quinoxalines.

Figure 4-5 Antimicrobial drugs approved for use in food-producing animals in USA. Actively marketed 2010-2019. Domestic sales and distribution data. Reported by medical importance and drug class (source: FDA)

4.2.3 Australia

Australia has measures in place to prevent and manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in food producing animals. These include data collection by the government and industry to monitor AMR in pigs, chicken meat, chicken eggs and salmon. In 2014, the Australian Government commissioned a report on antibiotic resistance and use in Australian livestock and agriculture industries. The report provided direction for planning future surveillance and reporting of AMR in Australia. The Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority (APVMA) evaluates and registers antimicrobials for animal use in Australia. This involves a risk assessment, including the risk of AMR developing. The APVMA released a report on antibiotic resistance in animals in August 2017. The report addresses the major AMR issues associated with antibiotic use in animals. A [report](#) on antimicrobial products sold for vet use in Australia provides data on sales between 2005 and 2010, which despite outdated, offers a perspective of veterinary AMU in the country. We can summarize the results from this AMU report as:

- The sales data do not suggest any significant change in the total quantity of antimicrobial products sold from 2005 to 2010 (Table 4-1 Total sales of veterinary antimicrobials (tonnes of active constituent), by animal type as estimated (July 2005 to June 2010) in Australia (source: APVMA)).
- From 2005 to 2010, 98 per cent of the total antimicrobials sold in Australia for animal use were used in food animals. The remaining 2 per cent were used in non-food animals
- The antimicrobial coccidiostats used to prevent coccidiosis disease in chickens comprised over half of total veterinary antimicrobials sales. Coccidiostats belong to classes of antimicrobials not used in humans and are not considered to contribute to AMR risks in humans.
- AGPs made up 4 to 7 per cent of the total antimicrobials sold for use in Australian food animals.
- Polypeptides (39.1%), Tetracyclines (20.1%), Macrolides (18.8%) and Penicillins (9.2%) were the classes most consumed in 2009/10, but also in previous years.
- Feed (76%) and water (18%) administration are largely the most common routes, followed by injection (4%) and intramammary (0.7%).
- Poultry is by far the sector with the highest sales (Table 4-2 Total sales of veterinary antimicrobials (tonnes of active constituent) used in food animals, by species and year (July 2005 to June 2010) in Australia (source: APVMA)).

Table 4-1 Total sales of veterinary antimicrobials (tonnes of active constituent), by animal type as estimated (July 2005 to June 2010) in Australia (source: APVMA)

ANIMAL TYPE	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10
Food animals	655.0	571.5	580.0	481.5	644.0
Non-food animals	9.7	10.9	12.0	10.6	17.2
Total	664.8	582.4	592.0	492.0	661.2

Table 4-2 Total sales of veterinary antimicrobials (tonnes of active constituent) used in food animals, by species and year (July 2005 to June 2010) in Australia (source: APVMA)

SPECIES	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10
Cattle and sheep	163.8	149.7	125.0	106.9	133.3
Poultry	385.0	318.6	351.9	276.4	406.4
Pigs	106.1	103.1	103.0	98.0	104.2
Other food animal species	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
Total	655.0	571.5	580.0	481.5	644.0

4.3 Data and trends from European countries

In this section we present a set of indicators available in public databases allowing us to monitor and compare the progress of AMU and AMR in the ROADMAP's countries. Data were gathered from European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption (ESVAC), a project from the European Medicines Agency (EMA), and also from the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). Since these are European databases, information about Mozambique and Vietnam are not presented.

The last available data was collected concerning three indicators where data was available that allows us to compare countries. In an attempt to tackle the AMR problem from a One Health perspective, not only animal consumption of antimicrobials was considered here, but also human consumption. In this regard the first indicator shows the trend on consumption of antibiotics in the hospital and community sectors in DDD per 1000 inhabitants per day. The second indicator reports the consumption of antimicrobials in sales in Mg/PCU of active ingredient of veterinary antimicrobial agents marketed mainly for food-producing animals. With these two indicators we can have an idea on AMU and compare the trend among countries, but also relate the consumption trends in the countries to the percentages of resistant bacteria isolate of the third indicator. This indicator reports on the evolution of percentages of resistant isolates to total tested isolates in the combined eight bacterial pathogens commonly causing infections in humans reported by the EARS-Net and ECDC.

These three indicators are used to illustrate the efficacy and impacts of the national (and EU) policies and strategies on AMU and AMR compared over countries. These data are limited by its generalization since it's not separated by species, also by the missing information on few countries and years, who did not report their information. Thus, comparisons must be taken very carefully, since besides the above-mentioned limitations, the dataset also misses information on age (in some animal species a very large number of young animals can be treated with the same volume/weight as only a few adult animals, i.e. for some species the body weight and treatment dosage varies a lot with age) and substance (some substances such as penicillin weighs much more per dose than e.g. quinolones). In addition, % resistance must be specified by type of resistance (i.e., against what substances, specific transferable genes etc). However, even though such limitations are present, the indicators calculated here represent a first step in the monitoring and comparison from the type of available data, thus an instrument to monitor the countries' trends on AMU and AMR.

Figure 4-6 depicts the human consumption in the community and hospital sector combined since 1997 extracted from the ECDC database. In this figure (as well as in Figure 4-8) the year 2006 is highlighted as the year that came into force the European regulation n. 1831/2003 which banned the use of antibiotics as growth promoters (AGPs) on European Union farms. Figure 4-7 shows the consumption for veterinarian purposes on food-producing animals. This last was monitored only since 2010, the beginning of the ESVAC project in the EU.

The complete historical series on the countries of interest are shown, and in the subsequent supplementary tables, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR)³ is calculated. The CAGR is also calculated only since 2006, when the ban on antimicrobials as growth promoters was promulgated, and for the past 5 years (of available data), to give an idea on the most recent dynamics. Following we also calculated the correlation between the veterinary/animal consumption and the AMR, as well as the human

³ CAGR is a metric that smooths annual gains in a value over a specified number of years as if the growth had happened steadily each year over that time period. $CAGR = (Ending\ value/beginning\ value)^{1/t} - 1$

consumption and the AMR. This is an attempt to provide a numerical value to the relation between AMU and AMR (consumption and resistance), however such indicator should be interpreted with caution, not simply as a cause-consequence estimator.

Subsequently we also show the EU countries total consumption and calculate their individual targets for compliance with the Farm to Fork strategy of the EU, which foresee a reduction of 50% of antimicrobials by 2030. The last section reports the country comparison among the AMR laboratories surveillance systems in the ROADMAP's European countries.

4.3.1 Indicator 1 – AMU in the human sector

Figure 4-6 shows Spain, France, Belgium and Italy as the countries with the highest consumption of antimicrobials along the time in the community and hospital sectors. All countries are decreasing their total consumption in the past 5 years, however since 2006 Belgium, France and the Netherlands have increased the consumption (

Table 4-3). When considering the whole series, only Denmark and the Netherlands have increased total consumption. Individual country's aspects can be summarized as:

- Data from Spain is available only from 2016 and it's representing the highest consumption among all countries, with 26.3 DDD/1000 inhabitants/day.
- France has the second highest consumption, despite a sharp decrease from 1997 to 2006. It shows also a high CAGR decrease of -0.9% since 1997, but it's mostly stable since 2006.
- The Belgium consumption is marked by ups and downs, with a first decrease until 2004, then an increase wave until 2011 followed by a second decrease. Consumption remains mostly stable during the years according to its overall CAGR of -0.41%.
- The Italian consumption is mostly stable along the years of available data (only since 2007), with an important decrease in 2017 and 2018.
- Data from UK is only available since 2013, but it's representing a constant decrease along these years.
- Despite one of the lowest levels (15.6 DDD/1000 inhabitants/day), Denmark has increased its total consumption until 2011, followed by a decrease since then. Its overall CAGR is therefore positive since 1997, but negative since 2006 returning to its levels of the beginning of the series.
- Sweden has the second lowest level, with a decreasing trend along the years, with an overall CAGR of -0.98%.
- Netherlands has the lowest consumption overall among all European ROADMAP countries, which is basically stable along the years. From 2006 it shows a slight growth, however it's decreasing in the past 5 years.

Figure 4-6 Consumption of antibacterials for systemic use (ATC Group J01) in the community and hospital sector in DDD per 1000 inhabitants and per day. Source ECDC.

Table 4-3 Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) on Consumption of antibacterials for systemic use (ATC Group J01) in the community and hospital sector in DDD per 1000 inhabitants and per day for the whole series, since 2006 and the last 5 years

ROADMAP's countries	Belgium	Denmark	France	Italy	Netherlands	Spain	Sweden	UK
Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) series	-0,41%	0,87%	-0,90%	-0,28%	0,05%	-2,21%	-0,98%	-1,62%
CAGR 2006	0,04%	-0,37%	0,03%	-0,31%	0,26%		-2,17%	
CAGR 5 years	-1,62%	-2,27%	-0,47%	-3,22%	-1,57%		-2,36%	-1,62%

4.3.2 Indicator 2 – AMU in the animal sector

Figure 4-7 represents the national consumption of antimicrobials in food producing animals with the sales of active ingredients (all confounded) in mg/PCU. Together with Table 4-4, it gives us an idea about the veterinary antibiotic consumption trend in the selected countries. It shows Spain, Italy and Belgium among the largest consumers, while Sweden, UK and Denmark the lowest.

Figure 4-7 Sales in Mg/PCU of active ingredient of veterinary antimicrobial agents marketed mainly for food-producing animals (including horses). Source EMA/ESVAC.

The higher decreases in the consumption along the total time series (CAGR series) is found in the UK, Netherlands, and France. This translates the countries’ efforts in reducing the total consumption. In the past five years (CAGR 5 years), the sharpest decreases are found in UK, France and Belgium.

Table 4-4 Compound Annual Growth Rate Sales in Mg/PCU of active ingredient of veterinary antimicrobial agents marketed mainly for food-producing animals (including horses) for the whole series and the last 5 years

ROADMAP's countries	Belgium	Denmark	France	Italy	Netherlands	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	UK
Compound Annual Growth Rate - series	-5,65%	-2,69%	-8,76%	-6,59%	-9,29%	-5,91%	-2,41%	-8,26%	-9,90%
CAGR 5 years	-6,30%	-3,17%	-7,34%	-4,15%	-3,84%	-7,12%	-0,26%	-8,26%	-13,82%

4.3.3 Indicator 3 – AMR in the human sector

Although the focus of this report is on AMU, we believe it’s important to show some figures in AMR in order to provide a direct parallel between both and reinforce why the prudent AMU is fundamental. In Figure 4-8 (and Table 4-5) below we observe the evolution of percentages of total resistant isolates (all confounded) to total tested isolates in the combined eight bacterial pathogens commonly causing

infections in humans reported by the EARS-Net and ECDC. It's evidenced the high percentage of resistant isolates in Italy at around 30% and showing an increase in its CAGR since 2006. Spain presents the second highest percentage, also increased since 2006. Interestingly both countries are also responsible for the largest amount of sales of antibiotics for food-producing animals (see Figure 4-7) and Spain for human consumption as well (see Figure 4-6). Netherlands, Sweden and Denmark, despite showing continuous growth since 2006, have the lowest percentages among all countries under analysis, with Sweden lower than 10%.

Figure 4-8 Percentage of resistant isolates / total tested isolates. Source ECDC.

Table 4-5 Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) on percentage of resistant isolates / total tested isolates for the whole series, since 2006 and the last 5 years

ROADMAP's countries	Belgium	Denmark	France	Italy	Netherlands	Spain	Sweden	UK
Compound Annual Growth Rate - series	-2,16%	23,42%	-4,30%	-2,33%	2,32%	-2,11%	13,81%	-5,18%
CAGR 2006	-2,17%	0,41%	1,26%	1,63%	1,01%	1,24%	0,89%	-1,62%
CAGR 5 years	-3,73%	-0,68%	-1,61%	-2,71%	0,58%	-0,82%	4,18%	0,56%

Based on this evidence, we correlated the consumption of antimicrobials in both animals and humans with the percentage of resistant isolates in humans for the ROADMAP European countries. The results show a correlation of **84%** between sales of veterinary antimicrobials and percentage of resistant isolates in humans, and a correlation of **61%** between the consumption of antimicrobials for systemic use (ATC Group J01) in the community and hospital sector in DDD per 1000 inhabitants and per day (DDD) and percentage of resistant isolates in humans. A further correlation of 62% between antibiotic use in humans and in animals. These results corroborate those of the JIACRA reports (European Centre for

Disease Prevention and Control, European Food Safety Authority, and European Medicines Agency 2015).

4.3.4 ESVAC data and Farm to Fork targets of European countries

The EU Farm to Fork set the target of 50% in antimicrobials reduction by 2030, however it does not define indications on the country level, or the sector level targets. Such individual targets are, for instance, defined for the [EU 2030 CO₂ emissions](#) strategy, where countries and sectors have different targets based on their current emissions and GDP (for preserving a sustainable and equitable economic growth across the continent).

Based on the principle that the high AM consumers should make higher efforts to achieve the targets, we constructed the following individual targets for 2030 (Table 4-6). In the ‘red’ part of the table we consider that all countries should make an equal effort to achieve the target, which is only based on their current consumption and the common target. In the ‘blue’ part of the table we also consider the country’s GDP in the countries’ weighting for a matter of comparison. However, AM consumption is not directly linked to the GDP growth, like the CO₂ case. Thus, a reduction in the AM consumption can be done without harming or with little harm to the economy and competitiveness, as have been shown by the forerunners in the AM reduction.

For the calculation the following assumptions were made:

- I. In 2030 the countries will have the same PCU as in 2018. This will not necessarily be the case, but this does not affect the targeted sales in mg/PCU.
- II. Countries that are already below the individual target will not receive any “increasing bonus”, thus having to maintain the current sales for 2030.

The calculations are conducted in the following steps:

- a) Considering the last ESVAC data for the EU member states of 2018, the total sales are 6,179.2 tonnes, by 2030 the 50% reduction will lead to a total sale of 3,089.6 tonnes.
- b) The sales in mg/PCU will consequently decrease from 118.3 to 59.2 mg/PCU for all countries combined.
- c) According to the assumption II the least performing countries will “gain” a margin above the 59.2 mg/PCU, and still the 50% reduction target will be maintained. This happens because some of the good performing countries are already much lower than the 59.2 mg/PCU target. Therefore, the laggards need to achieve the target of 63.4 mg/PCU, while the forerunners will maintain the today’s level.
- d) This target was multiplied by the countries’ PCUs, and the total tonnes of AM sales calculated. In the last column it’s estimated the percentage reduction, or the effort of each individual country to achieve the EU Farm to Fork target.

For these calculations we used the last available data from ESVAC and EUROSTAT databases.

According to this method, the largest total sales’ reductions will need to come from countries such as Spain, Italy, Poland and Germany. Although at country level, the highest efforts must be done by Cyprus, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Hungary and Poland, where the highest percentage reductions are needed.

The same reasoning, and even targets, can be extended to the level of sector and farms. Sectors considered high consumers, such as the pork for example, must make higher efforts, and so do poorly performing farms.

In the ‘blue’ part of the table, we weighted the countries’ efforts based on their GDP per capita. The highest GDP per capita belongs to Luxembourg. We attributed the value of 12,5 mg/PCU as the 2030 target for this country, because a ‘zero’ target would not be reasonable since sick animals should receive antimicrobials for treatment anyway. This value is based on the current lowest consumption, which is found in Sweden. After this, all other countries are weighted based on their own GDP and the main changes to notice are those in Ireland, Luxembourg and Netherlands. Because of their high GDP per capita, these countries now belong to the group of countries that need to reduce their overall consumption, which was not the case without weighting. Countries such as Bulgaria, Romania and Greece received a sort of alleviation on the total amount of reduction targeted because of their lowest GDP. For the other countries, minor changes are verified.

Table 4-6 Countries 2018 AM sales and F to F targets for 2030. Efforts evenly distributed and countries weighted by GDP.

Country	Data 2018			2030 Efforts evenly distributed				2030 Efforts weighted by GDP per capita			
	Sales (tonnes) for food-producing animals	PCU (1,000 tonnes)	Sales in mg/PCU	Targeted Total sales 2030 (tonnes)	mg/pc in 2030 targeted	Total reduction (tonnes)	Percentage reduction	Sales (tonnes) for food-producing animals	Sales in mg/PCU	Total reduction (tonnes)	Percentage reduction
Austria	48,00	957,20	50,10	47,96	50,10			48,00	50,10		
Belgium	195,00	1724,40	113,10	109,29	63,38	-85,71	-44%	92,62	53,71	-102,38	-53%
Bulgaria	47,80	399,90	119,60	25,35	63,38	-22,45	-47%	33,37	83,45	-14,43	-30%
Croatia	19,60	293,00	66,80	18,57	63,38	-1,03	-5%	19,57	66,80		
Cyprus	53,40	114,50	466,30	7,26	63,38	-46,14	-86%	7,80	68,13	-45,60	-85%
Czechia	40,20	704,60	57,00	40,16	57,00			40,16	57,00		
Denmark	93,60	2446,70	38,20	93,46	38,20			93,46	38,20		
Estonia	6,10	114,00	53,30	6,08	53,30			6,08	53,30		
Finland	9,30	496,80	18,70	9,29	18,70			9,29	18,70		
France	456,20	7107,00	64,20	450,44	63,38	-5,76	-1%	415,69	58,49	-40,51	-9%
Germany	753,10	8517,60	88,40	539,85	63,38	-213,25	-28%	456,01	53,54	-297,09	-39%
Greece	113,00	1243,90	90,90	78,84	63,38	-34,16	-30%	93,77	75,38	-19,23	-17%
Hungary	150,20	831,80	180,60	52,72	63,38	-97,48	-65%	64,88	78,00	-85,32	-57%
Ireland	98,60	2142,10	46,00	98,54	46,00			61,86	28,88	-36,74	-37%
Italy	932,10	3819,30	244,00	242,07	63,38	-690,03	-74%	243,78	63,83	-688,32	-74%
Latvia	6,00	167,30	36,10	6,04	36,10			6,04	36,10		
Lithuania	10,70	323,80	33,10	10,72	33,10			10,72	33,10		
Luxembourg	1,80	54,70	33,60	1,84	33,60			0,68	12,50	-1,12	-62%
Malta	2,10	14,20	150,90	0,90	63,38	-1,20	-57%	0,95	66,92	-1,15	-55%
Netherlands	183,90	3200,80	57,50	184,05	57,50			158,28	49,45	-25,62	-14%
Poland	782,20	4672,60	167,40	296,15	63,38	-486,05	-62%	368,53	78,87	-413,67	-53%
Portugal	191,80	1028,10	186,60	65,16	63,38	-126,64	-66%	74,47	72,44	-117,33	-61%
Romania	230,70	2788,20	82,70	176,72	63,38	-53,98	-23%	226,22	81,13	-4,48	-2%
Slovakia	12,10	246,60	49,30	12,16	49,30			12,16	49,30		
Slovenia	7,80	179,80	43,20	7,77	43,20			7,77	43,20		
Spain	1724,10	7865,40	219,20	498,51	63,38	-1225,59	-71%	527,60	67,08	-1196,50	-69%
Sweden	9,80	782,70	12,50	9,78	12,50			9,78	12,50		
Total 27 countries	6.179,20	52.237	118,29	3.089,65	59,15	-3.089,49		3.089,53	59,14	-3.089,50	

Although representing the countries' individual efforts based on socio-economic criteria, these indicators might not offer the best weighting of countries in terms of AMR problem. Therefore, we conducted the calculation of three further indicators that might better represent the necessity of individual efforts in terms of AMR spread and control, since the objective is to avoid the spread of AMR in the population. Considering the dynamics of AMR propagation and a direct link between AMU sales and AMR, these indicators are based on the weighting of countries in:

- PCU of animals / Total Country Area in km²
- PCU of animals / Total Human Population
- PCU of animals / (1 / Human Population Density (in heads per km²))

The same reasoning as before is maintained, considering that antimicrobials are necessary and cannot be completely cut-off, we attributed the value of 12,5 mg/PCU (the current Swedish value) for the country showing the highest weighting in each indicator. Thus when weighted by 'PCU of animals / Total Country Area', the Netherlands had the highest weighting score and was attributed the value of 12,5 mg/PCU. When weighted by 'PCU of animals / Total Human Population', Ireland had the highest weighting score, and when weighted by 'PCU of animals / (1/Human Population Density)', Germany showed the highest weighting score.

The results are shown in Table 4-7, and they reveal when weighted by PCU/km² (yellow section of the table), countries with small area such as Belgium, Netherlands, Denmark and Ireland now have to pursue larger sales reduction, with Netherlands being the country with the highest PCU/km².

By the other side, when weighted by PCU/total population (grey section), Ireland show the highest PCU/man, needing to make a high sales reduction effort. With this weighting system, Denmark also needs to pursue a large reduction in sales.

The last indicator considers the PCU of animals, the total population and the area of countries (green section). Therefore, it might offer the most accurate measure for weighting countries in order to achieve an effective and fair effort in AMU sales reduction among the EU members (since this is the only comparable indicator of AMU so far among the 27 EU countries). With this system a huge burden is transferred to Germany, which is the country with the highest value of PCU of animals / (1 / Human Population Density (in heads per km²)), thus having a high density of human population as well as a high quantity of animals. Belgium, Italy, Spain and Poland also need to contribute with large reductions in sales of veterinary antimicrobials in order to achieve the 50% Farm-to-Fork target by 2030. Regardless of the weighting system considered, countries such as Spain, Italy, Poland have always to make large efforts in reducing their AMU sales, because of the current high sales values.

This exercise is a simplification of the issue and must be interpreted with caution. First of all, sales are not a good indicator of AMU, even less for AMR. Other indicators such as the DDD for example, offer a better information on the consumption, since some active ingredients can be applied in smaller doses than others. Thus, our first recommendation is to have a better indicator of AMU at EU level, for a more reliable comparison of countries, sectors and farms. Another caution is regarding the specific classification of certain antimicrobials. Those classified as "Highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials" by the WHO, need to have specific targets and regulation, as some of them are already in force from 2022 in the new EU regulations.

Table 4-7 Countries 2018 AM sales and F to F targets for 2030. Countries weighted by Area, Population, and Population density

Country	2030 Efforts ponderated by PCU/ Total Country Area				2030 Efforts ponderated by PCU/ Human population				2030 Efforts ponderated by PCU/population density			
	Sales (tonnes) for food-producing animals		Total reduction (tonnes)	Percentage reduction	Sales (tonnes) for food-producing animals		Total reduction (tonnes)	Percentage reduction	Sales (tonnes) for food-producing animals		Total reduction (tonnes)	Percentage reduction
	Sales in mg/PCU				Sales in mg/PCU				Sales in mg/PCU			
Austria	48,00	50,10			48,00	50,10			48,00	50,10		
Belgium	41,49	24,06	-153,51	-79%	105,99	61,46	-89,01	-46%	139,34	80,80	-55,66	-29%
Bulgaria	34,37	85,94	-13,43	-28%	32,61	81,55	-15,19	-32%	47,50	118,78	-0,30	-1%
Croatia	19,60	66,80			19,60	66,80			19,60	66,80		
Cyprus	8,66	75,67	-44,74	-84%	7,55	65,98	-45,85	-86%	13,70	119,63	-39,70	-74%
Czechia	40,20	57,00			40,20	57,00			40,20	57,00		
Denmark	57,39	23,46	-36,21	-39%	30,58	12,50	-63,02	-67%	93,60	38,20		
Estonia	6,10	53,30			6,10	53,30			6,10	53,30		
Finland	9,30	18,70			9,30	18,70			9,30	18,70		
France	456,20	64,20			456,20	64,20			456,20	64,20		
Germany	530,33	62,26	-222,77	-30%	611,26	71,76	-141,84	-19%	106,47	12,50	-646,63	-86%
Greece	98,43	79,13	-14,57	-13%	85,57	68,79	-27,43	-24%	113,00	90,90		
Hungary	66,28	79,69	-83,92	-56%	62,83	75,53	-87,37	-58%	95,66	115,00	-54,54	-36%
Ireland	98,60	46,00			26,78	12,50	-71,82	-73%	98,60	46,00		
Italy	287,81	75,36	-644,29	-69%	306,06	80,13	-626,04	-67%	284,68	74,54	-647,42	-69%
Latvia	6,00	36,10			6,00	36,10			6,00	36,10		
Lithuania	10,70	33,10			10,70	33,10			10,70	33,10		
Luxembourg	1,80	33,60			1,80	33,60			1,80	33,60		
Malta	0,53	37,58	-1,57	-75%	1,25	88,08	-0,85	-40%	1,69	118,90	-0,41	-20%
Netherlands	40,01	12,50	-143,89	-78%	172,84	54,00	-11,06	-6%	124,52	38,90	-59,38	-32%
Poland	339,54	72,67	-442,66	-57%	314,25	67,25	-467,95	-60%	401,27	85,88	-380,93	-49%
Portugal	79,27	77,11	-112,53	-59%	74,36	72,32	-117,44	-61%	116,52	113,33	-75,28	-39%
Romania	213,20	76,47	-17,50	-8%	174,66	62,64	-56,04	-24%	230,70	82,70		
Slovakia	12,10	49,30			12,10	49,30			12,10	49,30		
Slovenia	7,80	43,20			7,80	43,20			7,80	43,20		
Spain	566,01	71,96	-1158,09	-67%	455,10	57,86	-1269,00	-74%	595,00	75,65	-1129,10	-65%
Sweden	9,80	12,50			9,80	12,50			9,80	12,50		
Total 27 countries	3.089,54	59,14	-3.089,66		3.089,29	59,14	-3.089,91		3.089,85	59,15	-3.089,35	

4.3.5 National AMU monitoring in EU countries

Some EU countries have their own monitoring system of AMU with different measures, detail of data collection and reporting (farm, species, vets, etc.) and thus do not rely on the ESVAC for monitoring their country AMU. In the following we present some of these systems and their results:

4.3.5.1 Belgium

The [BelVet-SAC](#) report 2019 is the last report released in Belgium and it corresponds to the 11th edition, calculating the evolution of AMU in animals since 2011. This is the second year where sales data is combined to farm-level data, reported by the Sanite-Med, making it possible to assess farm and species-specific data in Belgium. The main results are illustrated in Figure 4-9; Figure 4-10; Figure 4-11; Figure 4-12 as well as in Table 4-8 and Table 4-9 and can be summarized as:

- In 2019 a consumption of 87,4 mg antimicrobial/kg biomass represents a decrease of -7.6% compared to the previous year. Belgium also achieved a cumulative reduction of -40.3% since 2011.

- The Sanitel-Med in Belgium calculates the number of treatment days (BD_{100})⁴, offering a better representation of the ‘use’ data. In 2019 it covered 80% of the AM sales in the country. It shows reductions of -5,8% for pigs and poultry and -21,3% for veal calves in 2019 compared to the previous year.
- Despite good results in the pig sector, the weaners are still showing a high consumption, even though a 10% decrease was reported from 2018.
- The veal remains the highest consumer of all sectors and must be targeted in further actions.
- In the poultry sector a moderate reduction was achieved, but there is still a continued high use of fluoroquinolones, and further action also need to target this sector.
- The use of antimicrobial dry cow applicators continues increasing since 2015, and so as the quantity of applicators for the treatment of mastitis in the past 3 years.
- Antibacterial premixes show a cumulative reduction of -71,1% in comparison to 2011.
- Critically important antimicrobials (classified ‘red’ by the AMCRA) increased for the second year in a row (+8%) after a drop in 2016 and 2017. Although they accumulate a reduction of -77,3% in comparison to 2011.

⁴ Express the treatment days out of 100 days based on the total amount of antimicrobials used per species and the total mass animals at risk per species

Class AB mg/kg biomass	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	'13 » '14	'14 » '15	'15 » '16	'16 » '17	'17 » '18	'18 » '19	2019%
Penicillins	39,88	39,91	38,09	42,03	40,96	35,78	34,63	0,1%	-4,6%	10,3%	-2,6%	-12,6%	-3,2%	39,61
Sulphonamides & trimethoprim	36,79	37,39	35,08	31,64	21,56	17,49	16,69	1,6%	-6,2%	-9,8%	-31,8%	-18,9%	-4,5%	19,10
Tetracyclines	30,80	29,92	28,49	24,16	27,66	23,96	18,35	-2,8%	-4,8%	-15,2%	14,4%	-13,3%	-23,4%	20,99
Macrolides	8,64	11,27	10,80	9,57	9,18	8,12	8,09	30,5%	-4,2%	-11,4%	-4,0%	-11,5%	-0,4%	9,25
Polymyxins	3,89	2,74	2,25	2,03	1,76	1,69	1,50	-29,6%	-17,6%	-9,9%	-13,3%	-4,1%	-11,2%	1,72
Aminosides	3,99	4,34	4,47	4,48	4,49	3,93	4,71	8,8%	3,1%	0,2%	0,3%	-12,6%	20,0%	5,39
Quinolones	1,64	1,69	1,92	0,82	0,29	0,44	0,48	3,2%	13,7%	-57,5%	-64,2%	50,0%	10,0%	0,55
Other**	0,90	0,61	0,57	0,55	0,50	1,05	0,82	-32,3%	-6,1%	-3,8%	-9,4%	109,5%	-21,4%	0,94
Phenicol	0,75	0,78	0,99	1,46	1,50	1,59	1,56	4,6%	26,5%	47,3%	3,0%	6,1%	-1,8%	1,79
Cephalosporins 1° & 2° G	0,35	0,39	0,37	0,44	0,41	0,37	0,52	12,7%	-4,4%	16,3%	-6,7%	-7,8%	38,1%	0,59
Cephalosporins 3° & 4° G	0,41	0,38	0,35	0,25	0,09	0,07	0,07	-7,0%	-9,5%	-28,3%	-65,9%	-19,2%	-2,6%	0,08
Total mg/kg biomass	128,02	129,42	123,39	117,43	108,40	94,50	87,43	1,09%	-4,66%	-4,83%	-7,69%	-12,83%	-7,48%	100
Total biomass cfr. Grave et al., 2010)*	2.026.565	2.068.815	2.109.520	2.065.040	2.052.300	2.087.735	2.022.450	2,08%	1,97%	-2,11%	-0,62%	1,73%	-3,13%	

** zink bacitracin, rifaximin, metronidazol, tiamulin

Figure 4-9 Total mg of active substance used per kg biomass produced in Belgium (source: BelVet-SAC report 2019)

Figure 4-10 Tonnes active substance of pharmaceuticals, medicated premixes and ZnO used in 2019 per Sanitel-Med animal category

Table 4-8 Total tonnes per antibacterial class sold in 2019 (Sales 2019) and total tonnes used in pigs, poultry and veal calves (Use 2019). Next to the tonnes used by each species the % this covers of the sales data (% sales) is shown (source: BelVet-SAC report 2019)

	Sales 2019	Use 2019							
	Tonne	Total tonne	% sales	Pig tonne	% sales	Poultry tonne	% sales	Veal tonne	% sales
Penicillins	70,0	57,9	83	44,0	63	9,5	13	4,4	6
Tetracyclines	37,1	33,6	91	26,3	71	1,6	4	5,7	15
Trim-sulfa	33,8	22,7	67	17,8	53	3,9	12	1,0	3
Macrolides	16,4	15,8	97	7,1	43	5,0	30	3,8	23
Aminosides	9,5	6,5	68	2,8	30	2,5	26	1,1	12
Polymixins	3,0	2,6	84	2,3	76	0,2	6	0,1	3
Phenicols	3,2	1,6	51	1,4	45	<0,1	<1	0,2	5
Other	1,7	1,1	65	1,1	65	0	0	0	0
Quinolones	1,0	0,4	36	<0,1	<1	0,3	33	<0,1	3
Cephalosporins	1,2	<0,1	<1	<0,1	<1	0	0	<0,1	<1

Table 4-9 Antimicrobial use (BD100-species) in 2018 and 2019 in pigs, poultry and veal calves (source: BelVet-SAC report 2019)

	Species-level DDDA _{bel} *LA _{bel} (x10 ⁶)		Species-level kg at risk (x 10 ³)		BD ₁₀₀ -species		% Δ 18-19
	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019	
PIGS	8 300	7 646	318 867	311 901	7,13	6,72	-5,8%
POULTRY	1 140	1 092	54 921	55 860	5,69	5,36	-5,8%
VEAL CALVES	1 408	1 115	13 629	13 717	28,31	22,27	-21,3%

Figure 4-11 Evolution of the median of the BD100-distribution in the 2018-2019 core reference population of each Sanitel-Med animal category. Zero-use farms were excluded for the analysis (source: BelVet-SAC report 2019)

Figure 4-12 Number of treatment days with the different antimicrobial classes and percentage of the total number of treatment days per species in 2018 and 2019. Numbers/percentages not shown are classes where use was below 1% of treatment days in 2018 and 2019 (source: BelVet-SAC report 2019)

4.3.5.2 Denmark

In Denmark the Danish integrated Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring and Research Programme ([DANMAP](#)) reports the use of antimicrobial agents and occurrence of antimicrobial resistance in bacteria from food animals, food and humans, and the 2019 report is the last one available.

It was founded in 1995, providing one-health surveillance system for the continuous surveillance and research of AMU and AMR. Medstat (mid-90s) and Vetstat (2000) are the databases recording the data for subsequent analysis (by the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) for animals). In DANMAP, the AMU in animals is estimated first as kg active compound and further as the number of standardised maintenance doses per day (DADDs⁵). AMU in pigs, cattle, and fur animals are presented in DAPD⁶, which is the “proportion of population in treatment per day” estimated as number of DADD per 1,000 animals per day. The main results are illustrated in Figure 4-13; Figure 4-14 and Table 4-10 and can be summarized as:

- A 3% decrease in total tonnes in 2019 is achieved in comparison to 2018, the lowest since 2002, and presenting a consistent decrease since 2013.
- The pig sector corresponds for 75% of total AMU. 2.3% of all pigs received antimicrobial treatment per day (23 DAPD), similar to the previous year. In weaners, this number was 91 DAPD.
- The use of medical zinc decreased by 7% in 2019 compared to 2018 targeting the EU withdrawal of 2022.

⁵ DADD is the average maintenance dose per day for the main indication of a drug in the appropriate animal species

⁶ DAPD is equal to DADD per 1,000 animals per day, where “animals” are represented by their live biomass and adjusted for lifespan.

- Tetracyclines showed a sharp decrease in the 2016-19 period because of the differentiated Yellow Card initiative (see D1.3). Small increases in the use of macrolides and aminoglycosides were noticed in the same period. Colistin was phased out in 2017.
- The AMU in cattle has been stable in the past five years, and in 2019 around 66% of the AM quantities were used to treat older animals with 3.2 DAPD, a -18% decrease in the past decade. 4% of use in 2019 was for intramammary treatment. In younger cattle it's notices an increase of 39% in the past decade, achieving 7.3 DAPD in 2019.
- A constant decrease of AMU in poultry is reported since 2015, however there was a small increase in 2019. In aquaculture the AMU also presents decrease from 2018 to 2019. In fur animals there is a 32 DAPD, with a small increase from 2018, but sharp decrease from 2017.

Figure 4-13 Prescribed antimicrobial agents for humans and all animal species, tonnes of active compound, Denmark (source: DANMAP)

Figure 4-14 Distribution of live biomass and antimicrobial consumption in main animal species, tonnes, Denmark (source: DANMAP)

Table 4-10 Antimicrobial use by animal species and age group, kg active compound, Denmark (source: DANMAP)

Therapeutic group	Aminoglycosides	Amphenicols	Cephalosporins ^(a)	Fluoroquinolones	Lincosamides	Macrolides	Other AB	Other quinolones	Penicillins, b-lactamase sensitive	Penicillins, others ^(b)	Pleuromutilins	Sulfonamides and trimethoprim	Tetracyclines	Total 2019	Total 2018
Pigs	8253	436	<1	0	1873	11874	<1	0	16973	8485	7203	5790	11745	72632	74658
Sows and piglets	1895	283	0	0	434	504	<1	0	8702	3404	845	4407	1087	21560	22331
Finishers	161	11	<1	0	619	3322	0	0	6059	752	3668	207	2990	17790	18479
Weaners	6197	142	<1	0	820	8048	0	0	2211	4329	2690	1177	7668	33282	33848
Cattle	844	886	88	<1	15	190	<1	0	7097	828	0	808	1592	12350	12865
Intramammaries	9	0	81	0	13	0	<1	0	163	257	0	<1	0	523	534
Cows and bulls	212	12	7	<1	<1	74	<1	0	6308	447	0	693	854	8607	9093
Calves <12 months	590	853	<1	0	1	113	<1	0	501	116	0	110	699	2985	2978
Heifers and steers	32	21	<1	0	<1	3	0	0	125	9	0	6	39	236	261
Poultry	55	<1	0	<1	28	228	0	0	333	215	<1	64	689	1612	1326
All poultry excl. turkeys	55	<1	0	<1	28	228	0	0	333	215	<1	64	689	1612	1326
Other production animals	274	342	<1	<1	92	483	<1	447	14	2085	<1	2308	463	6510	7274
Aquaculture	0	293	0	0	0	0	0	447	0	39	0	1721	22	2522	3557
Fur animals	270	50	0	<1	91	482	<1	0	7	2039	0	580	436	3955	3689
Other ^(c)	5	<1	<1	<1	1	1	<1	0	7	7	<1	7	5	33	28
Companion animals	6	<1	93	14	63	9	38	0	28	662	<1	1473	36	2423	2418
Pets ^(d)	5	<1	93	14	63	9	38	0	20	662	<1	246	32	1183	1224
Horses	<1	<1	<1	<1	0	<1	<1	0	8	<1	0	1227	4	1240	1194
Unspecified^(e)	361	5	3	1	10	36	1	-6	922	131	4	143	154	1766	1541
Total	9793	1671	185	16	2081	12820	40	441	25367	12406	7208	10587	14679	97293	100082

Note: Data for 2019 were extracted from VetStat on 3 March 2020. Combination products are split into active compounds

a) In 2019, the use of 3rd and 4th generation cephalosporins in cattle, pets, pigs, and horses was 7.5 kg, 1.1 kg, 0.2 kg, and 0.1 kg, respectively

b) Penicillins with extended spectrum and combination penicillins, incl. beta-lactamase inhibitors

c) Mainly sheep and goats

d) Where no animal species are given, antimicrobial agents were allocated to pets based on relevant type of preparation (e.g. tablets, capsules, eye - and eardrops, etc.) or registration (3rd generation cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones only). Approximately 220 kg of the sulfonamides and trimethoprim registered for pets are products (oral paste) typically used for horses. Other AB comprise mainly metronidazole

e) Includes data where the animal species were not registered or where the age group do not apply to the designated animal species

4.3.5.3 Netherlands

The Netherlands Veterinary Medicines Institute (SDa) reports every year the ‘Usage of Antibiotics in Agricultural Livestock in the Netherlands Trends and benchmarking of livestock farms and veterinarians’ since 2012. The last report was released in 2019. The ‘use’ data is reported in defined daily dose animal (DDDA_{NAT})⁷ used to express the amount of antibiotics used within a particular livestock sector in the Netherlands. For farms it’s expressed by the defined daily dose animal used to express the amount of antibiotics used at a particular livestock farm (DDDA_F). For the veterinarians there is the

⁷ Depends on the total number of treated kilograms within a particular livestock sector for a specific year, and then dividing this number by the average number of kilograms of animal present within the livestock sector concerned

defined daily dose animal used to express the antibiotic prescription pattern of a particular veterinarian in one of the livestock sectors or subsectors for a particular year ($DDDA_{VET}$). The main results of the sector use ($DDDA_{NAT}$) are illustrated in Figure 4-15; Figure 4-16 and Figure 4-17 and can be summarized as:

- The broiler and the dairy cattle AMU have been stable in the past four years achieving reductions in the order of -2.2% ($0.2 DDDA_{NAT}$) and -1.7% ($0.05 DDDA_{NAT}$), respectively, compared to 2018.
- The veal farming sector reduced by -22% ($4.6 DDDA_{NAT}$) its AMU over the past five years, and 11.3% ($2.1 DDDA_{NAT}$) was achieved in 2019.
- Antibiotic use the pig farming sector is low, and declined by $0.7 DDDA_{NAT}$ (8.2%) in 2019.
- In 2019 there was a decline by -16% in the kilograms of active substances sold in Netherlands and a total of -69.6% decrease since 2009, the government-specified reference year. From the total 2.3% of sales were not reported as use in 2019.
- Close to 80% of the total number of kilograms sold is used in the veal and pig farming sectors.
- In the pig farming sector and the cattle farming sectors, first-choice antibiotics accounted for about 80%, second-choice antibiotics accounted for about 20%, and third-choice antibiotics (primarily polymyxins) accounted for 0.1% to approximately 4% of overall antibiotic use in 2019.
- In 2019, the broiler and turkey farming sectors both were able to reduce the relative amount of third-choice antibiotics used, resulting in relative contributions of 0.9% and 2.7%, respectively. The poultry farming sector managed to reduce its fluoroquinolone use from 183 kg to 64 kg.
- Fluoroquinolone use and use of third- and fourth-generation cephalosporins remained low in most of the livestock sectors.
- Colistin use rose by 16.5% during the 2019 reporting year. The 2019 usage level represents a 47.0% increase from the 2017 level. Colistin use increases in the pig farming sector and the “Other poultry farming subsectors” category were the main drivers for this rise.

Purple: turkey farming sector; blue: veal farming sector; orange: broiler farming sector; light green: pig farming sector; dark green: dairy cattle farming sector.

Figure 4-15 Long-term developments in antibiotic use according to LEI Wageningen UR data (in DD/AY, for 2004 to 2010) and SDa data (in DDDANAT, for 2011 to 2019), as spline curves with point estimates for each year with 95% confidence interval (source SDa)

Figure 4-16 Developments in sales of antibiotics over the 1999-2019 period, in number of kilograms of active substances sold (x1,000) (source: FIDIN, SDa), by main pharmacotherapeutic group in Netherlands

Figure 4-17 Long-term developments in the numbers of kilograms of active substances sold and used. The numbers of kilograms used in the individual monitored livestock sectors are shown. Also included are the annual numbers of kilograms of live weight for the livestock sectors that were subjected to SDA monitoring in 2019

4.3.5.4 Sweden

Data on AM sales in Sweden is collected and reported since 1980. The Public Health Agency of Sweden and the National Veterinary Institute (SVA) have a collaboration that started in 2002, where analysis of data with regards to sales of antibiotics as well as AMR in animals, humans and food is gathered and presented in an annual report called the Swedres-Svarm report⁸. In 2020 it was published the last report containing the data of 2019 and the main results are illustrated in Figure 4-18; Figure 4-19; Table 4-11; Table 4-12; Table 4-13 and can be summarized as:

- Since the ban on AGPs in 1986 the sales of antimicrobials in Sweden have decreased by around 2/3. During the 1990s the AMU for group treatments decreased, and in the past decade the AMU for individual treatment is also decreasing.
- Compared to 2010, the number of pigs slaughtered in 2019 has decreased by 12%, while the number of broilers has increased by 35%. The number of dairy cows decreased by 12% during the same period.
- Sales of antibiotics for animals are stable at a low level, reaching 9601 kg, of which 58% were penicillins with narrow-spectrum. In 2010 these figures were 14 117 kg and 53%, respectively.
- Of the total sales, around 90% are products formulated for individual animal treatment and the remaining for groups or flocks.

⁸ <https://www.sva.se/djurhalsa/antibiotika/overvakning/swedres-svarm/>

- Since 2014 the sales of aminopenicillins, aminoglycosides and macrolides and lincosamides have been relatively unchanged, while the other classes decreased by more than 10%.
- The reported incidence of treatment of clinical mastitis in dairy cows has decreased over the last ten years and was 9.0 recorded treatments per 100 completed/interrupted lactations in 2018/2019. Treatment with fluoroquinolones for any indication in dairy cows has decreased from 2.38 recorded treatments per 100 completed/interrupted lactations in 2010 to 0.14 in 2018.
- In 2010 and 2019 the sales of antibiotics for pigs were 12.8 and 12.1 mg/kg slaughtered pig.
- Antibiotics are rarely used for treatment of bacterial diseases in commercially reared poultry. Localized outbreaks in a specific year may be the responsible for increasing in AMU. Over the last ten years, the yearly sales of fluoroquinolones for slaughter chickens and hens have been below or much below 1 kg, mostly below 0.25 kg. Cephalosporins or colistin are never used. The use in 2019 corresponds to 0.41 mg active substance/kg slaughtered chicken
- In pigs, the proportion of sales of products for treatment of groups of animals of the total sales has decreased over time, while for individual treatment has increased. Expressed in mg/kg, such sales were 35% of the total in 2010, compared to 18% in 2019.
- In pigs, Benzylpenicillin for medication of individual animals dominate and has increased
- The time trend shows a constant decrease of AM sales and most of the decrease derives from cattle and use in veterinary practice.

Figure 4-18 Sales of antibiotics for animals expressed as mg per population correction unit (PCU)

Table 4-11 Yearly sales of antibiotics for veterinary use expressed as kg of active substance per class^a in Sweden

ATCvet code		2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017 ^b	2018 ^b	2019
QJ01AA, QG01A	Tetracyclines	1115	1073	881	935	787	685	515	529	516	522
QJ01CE, -R, QJ51	Benzylpenicillin ^c	7546	6696	6362	5954	5509	5861	5997	5921	5961	5579
QJ01CA, QJ01CR	Aminopenicillins	907	723	649	645	635	642	677	640	683	648
QJ01D	Cephalosporins	575	498	410	330	299	267	242	210	187	161
QA07AA, QJ01G, -R, QJ51R	Aminoglycosides	462	427	408	264	298	322	312	302	376	343
QA07AB, QJ01E	Sulphonamides	1998	1867	1812	1707	1699	1634	1643	1678	1539	1445
QJ01E	Trimethoprim & derivatives	357	338	329	320	314	313	318	326	297	281
QJ01F	Macrolides & lincosamides	739	648	632	564	484	485	472	515	578	486
QJ01MA	Fluoroquinolones	148	120	106	52	45	34	30	25	29	20
QA07AA, QJ01BA, QJ01XQ	Others ^d	270	216	174	205	201	224	337	147	237	115
	Total sales	14 117	12 606	11 763	10 975	10 270	10 468	10 543	10 293	10 404	9 601

^aData from 2010-2015 are uncertain because of a lack of completeness mainly affecting injectable products. ^bUpdated following the discovery of some errors in previous calculations. ^cAlso includes small amounts of phenoxymethylpenicillin and penicillinase stable penicillins. ^dOthers include: amphenicols, pleuromutilins and polymyxins, grouped for confidentiality reasons.

Table 4-12 Number of broiler flocks treated with antibiotics, and total number of flocks slaughtered per year

Year	Number of flocks treated	Total number of flocks
2011	6	3 185
2012	1	2 853
2013	4	3 133
2014	4	3 138
2015	28	3 191
2016	14	3 300
2017	1	3 300
2018	4	3 223
2019	54	3 368

Table 4-13 Sales of antibiotics for pigs in mg/kg slaughtered pigs by mode of administration

	Individual treatment		Group treatment		Total	
	2010	2019	2010	2019	2010	2019
Tetracyclines	0.24	0.42	1.83	0.56	2.07	0.98
Benzylpenicillin ^a	4.86	6.17	0.00	0.00	4.86	6.17
Aminopenicillins	0.34	0.55	0.31	0.22	0.64	0.77
Trimethoprim & sulphonamides	1.85	1.51	0.00	0.00	1.85	1.51
Macrolides & lincosamides	0.33	0.48	1.41	0.94	1.74	1.42
Fluoroquinolones	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	0.00	0.07	<0.01
Others ^b	0.60	0.61	0.95	0.63	1.55	1.24
Total	8.27	9.74	4.50	2.35	12.77	12.09

Figure 4-19 Sales of antibiotics for pigs expressed as DCDvet/kg⁹ slaughtered pigs and DCDse/kg¹⁰ slaughtered pigs

⁹ Defined by the ESVAC https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/report/categorisation-antibiotics-european-union-answer-request-european-commission-updating-scientific_en.pdf

¹⁰ Defined on basis of Summary of product characteristics for products authorised in Sweden

5 Case study analysis: pig production in Denmark

5.1 Conventional indoor pig production

5.1.1 Background

The vast majority (98-99%) of Danish pigs are born and raised in conventional indoor systems. In these systems, pigs are born in crated pens (only a minority of conventional farrowing stables are with loose housing). Pigs are castrated (with local anaesthetics) and tail docked. Pigs are weaned at 4 weeks of age. After weaning, they are typically raised in indoor pens with partly slatted floors without bedding material. Feeding of weaners is typically with dry feed. Roughage is not required but there is a requirement for rooting material. A wooden stick attached to the wall is often used for this purpose. Examples on requirements regarding stocking density for different types of pigs: From 10 to 20 kg of weight: 0.2 m² per pig. From 85 to 110 kg of weight: 0.65 m² per pig. Farmer's use of antibiotics is permitted if he/she has a formal agreement with a veterinarian, who visits the farm regularly. At these visits, the veterinarian prescribes medicine for the coming (1-2 months) based on his/her knowledge of the farm and clinical judgement at the visit. If batch medication is prescribed for diarrhoea or airway-related problems, at least once a year, diagnostic samples have to be taken for identification of pathogens.

5.1.2 Methods

All use of antibiotics prescribed by a veterinarian is recorded in a national database named **VetStat**. Data of the use of antibiotics can come from three different sources –the pharmacies that deliver the prescribed antibiotics to the farmer, the veterinarian that use or hand over antibiotics on the farm, and feed mills for the occasions where the antibiotics is delivered to the farm in premixed feed. Every record in VetStat should include the unique farm identification number, the age group of pigs and the organ system the antibiotics is prescribed for. Three age groups are possible for pig: Adult animals (sows, boars), weaners (between 7 and 30 kg) and finishers (above 30 kg). This have the implication that antibiotic treatment intended for the piglets are recorded for the sows. For each antibiotic product a defined daily dose is defined base on the principles provide by the EMA¹¹ and with slight modifications adapted as the 'Danish defined daily doses'¹².

The herd size should be reported bi-annually to the Central Husbandry Register (**CHR**) by the farmer. Based on these population sizes, we classified herds with more than 50 sows or 100 weaners on stable or 100 fattening pigs on stable in 2018 as being professional farmers. Based on this group of farmers we draw a random sample of 300 farms as the study population. On these 300 farms we extracted data from VetStat on the antimicrobial use and from the CHR on animal population in these farms for the 5-year period 2016-2020. A descriptive table of the farms and number of animals included in this sample can be seen in Table 5-1.

¹¹https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/scientific-guideline/principles-assignment-defined-daily-dose-animals-dddvet-defined-course-dose-animals-dcdvet_en.pdf

¹²<https://www.danmap.org/-/media/Sites/danmap/Downloads/Reports/2019/DANMAP-2019-DADD-description.ashx?la=da&hash=3666F480FCA7283420435AF2AAE41F6CA3687F3D>

The population sizes within the three age groups are estimated as simple averages. Based on the AMU in the different age groups and the farmers recording of the animal population within farm, the adjusted daily doses (ADD) per 100 animals per day is calculated. This measure of AMU is essentially a treatment incidence that describes the proportion of animals treated each day with a standardised dose of antibiotics.

Table 5-1 Conventional indoor farms in the Danish pig case study based on a random sample of pig herds with eighter more than 50 sows or 100 weaners or 100 finishers

Year	Stages	Conventional Indoor	
		Farms (N°)	Average herd size within stage
2016	1 st stage (sows)	79	721
	2 nd stage (weaners)	141	2378
	3 rd stage (finishers)	258	1297
2017	1 st stage (sows)	76	708
	2 nd stage (weaners)	133	2840
	3 rd stage (finishers)	259	1347
2018	1 st stage (sows)	77	792
	2 nd stage (weaners)	132	2727
	3 rd stage (finishers)	255	1319
2019	1 st stage (sows)	61	823
	2 nd stage (weaners)	104	2861
	3 rd stage (finishers)	194	1292
2020	1 st stage (sows)	62	817
	2 nd stage (weaners)	107	2983
	3 rd stage (finishers)	209	1417

Note: Data extracted from the Central Husbandry Register (CHR)

5.1.3 Results

The development in AMU within each age group is presented in Table 5-2 for the years 2016-2020. The AMU is calculated based on the total number of doses within age group and the total number of animals within age group and results are shown in ADD/100 animals/day. The herd median is also given in brackets. The results show that the AMU is unchanged in the 5-year period for sow/piglets and finishers. For weaners, results show a minor decrease in the AMU in 5-year period. For all years and age groups, the herd medians are lower than then overall average, indicating some skewness in the distribution of AMU in the herds.

Table 5-2 Antimicrobial use in adjusted daily doses (ADD) per 100 animals per day from 2016 to 2020 for the three age groups: Sows and piglets, weaners, and finishers in a random sample of 300 farms. The AMU is given as an overall average of the total use divided by the total animal population. The value in brackets is the herd-median AMU

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sows and piglets	2.20 (1.98)	2.41 (1.96)	2.31 (1.90)	2.12 (2.04)	2.27 (2.21)

Weaners	9.53 (9.06)	8.40 (8.22)	8.30 (7.13)	9.01 (7.14)	8.21 (7.50)
Finishers	1.98 (1.32)	1.76 (1.03)	1.81 (1.06)	1.84 (1.12)	1.87 (1.28)

Information on the actual diagnoses that the antibiotics are prescribed for is not available and veterinarians and farmers are allowed to use the prescribed antibiotics for more than one specific disease. However, the veterinarian is obliged to inform the organ system the antibiotics are prescribed for. For instance, it can be assumed that antibiotics classified as being used for a disease in the gastro-intestinal system are related to the diagnosis of enteritis. The AMU in ADD/100 animals/day related to the different organ systems can be seen in Table 5-3.

Table 5-3: Antimicrobial use in ADD/100 animals/day distributed on the different organ systems the antibiotic was prescribed for (across all years)

Organ system	Sows/piglets	Weaners	Finishers
Reproduction, Urogenital system	0.43	<0.01	<0.01
Udder	0.25	<0.01	<0.01
Gastro-intestinal	0.23	6.66	1.27
Respiratory	0.47	0.93	0.13
Joint, limbs, claws, central nervous system, skin	0.87	1.01	0.49
Metabolic and circulatory system	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

The results clearly shows that most treatments with antimicrobials are for weaners with gastro-intestinal disease (post-weaning diarrhoea). Treatments for disease in the gastro-intestinal tract is also the most of daily doses used for finishers. For sows and piglets, joint and limb lesions are the most predominant followed by diseases related to the reproductive system and udder (the mastitis, metritis,agalactia complex).

In Table 5-4 the distributions of the doses of antibiotics in percentages within age group and year can be seen. The results show that for Sows and piglets around 35-40% of the doses used are Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA and CIA*). For weaners this is about 40-50% and for finishers around 30% of the doses are CIA and CIA*. There are minor fluctuations in the different groups of antimicrobials over the years.

Table 5-4: Distribution of the Adjusted Daily Doses (ADD) in percentages within age group and year on the WHO classification of antibiotic importance. The WHO classification consists of Highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA), Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA), Highly Important Antimicrobials (HIA) and Important Antimicrobials (IA).*

Age group	WHO classification	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sows and Piglets	CIA*	18.1	17.6	17.3	16.3	21.7
	CIA	18.9	18.3	21.5	22.5	20.4
	HIA	57.8	51.7	46.4	58.8	54.6
	IA	5.2	12.4	14.7	2.4	3.2

Weaners	CIA*	29.8	36.8	37.4	40.2	31.2
	CIA	10.7	12.0	11.8	10.3	13.9
	HIA	52.4	42.0	37.0	33.0	39.2
	IA	7.2	9.2	13.7	16.5	15.6
Finishers	CIA*	24.3	26.5	30.8	31.4	29.2
	CIA	2.2	1.8	2.1	1.8	1.6
	HIA	54.5	47.7	58.8	42.7	43.2
	IA	18.9	24.6	24.4	24.1	25.9

The group of High Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA*) is generally represented by macrolides and lincosamides (like tylosin, tilmicosin, tulathromycin and gamethromycin). There were only two ordinations of cephalosporins in the data and none of fluoroquinolones.

5.2 Organic pig production system

5.2.1 Background

Approximately 1% of Danish pigs are raised in organic systems. In these systems, farrowing sows live outdoor on fields with huts for farrowing. Thus, all pigs are born outside. At weaning (minimum 7 weeks of age) pigs are typically moved to indoor pens with outdoor access. Outdoor access is required throughout their entire life. Bedding material is required, and straw is provided for this purpose. Roughage is required during the whole life and is typically provided as silage. Examples on requirements regarding stocking density for different types of pigs: From weaning until 30 kg of weight: 0.6 m² indoor area + 0.4 m² outdoor area per pig. From 85 to 110 kg of weight: 1.1 m² indoor area + 0.8 m² outdoor area per pig. There are strict regulations on the use of AB: e.g., pigs that do not reach one year of age can only have one treatment period in their lifetime. If more treatments are needed, these pigs must be sold as conventional. For a summary of legal requirements and comparison with the two other systems of this Case study, see Table 5-5.

Table 5-5 For comparison of the three systems: Legal requirements for housing and medical treatment in Danish organic, Conventional free-range and Conventional indoor pig production (adopted from Nielsen et al. 2021)

	Organic	Conventional free-range	Conventional indoor
Housing during suckling period	Born outdoor in huts of min. 3.8 m ² . Bedding material. Total area: Min. 300 m ² per litter.	Born outdoor in huts of min. 3.8 m ² . Bedding material. Total area: Min. 300 m ² per litter.	Indoor. Normally crates
Housing during growing and finishing period	Housed indoor with outdoor access. Bedding and rooting material required.	Housed indoor with outdoor access. Bedding and rooting material required. Solid floor: min. 50%.	Indoor. Rooting material required. 100% drained floor* allowed

	Organic	Conventional free-range	Conventional indoor
	Solid floor: min. 50%. Natural ventilation.	Natural ventilation.	
Stocking density (100 kg)	2.3 m ² per pig	1.2 m ² per pig	0.65 m ² per pig
Age at weaning (min.)	40 days	30 days	21 days
Access to roughage	Access	Access	No access
Antibiotic treatment	Veterinarian must initiate. Withdrawal period is doubled compared to conventional indoor herds. Max one treatment during lifetime per finisher. Max three treatments per sow per year	Farmer can initiate (requires herd health agreement with veterinarian). Withdrawal period is doubled compared to conventional indoor herds.	Farmer can initiate (requires herd health agreement with veterinarian).
Zinc oxide mixed in feed	Max. 2500 ppm 0-14 days after weaning.	Max. 2500 ppm 0-14 days after weaning.	Max. 2500 ppm 0-14 days after weaning.

5.2.2 Methods

The two national databases VetStat and CHR are also used for this data collection on organic farms and with the same selection criteria as for the conventional indoor production systems. However, due to the limited number of organic farms, all organic farms that fulfilled the inclusion criteria for professional farmers were included in the data. In Table 5-6 we present an overview of the number of organic farms and the farm size averages for each age group in the 5-year period.

Table 5-6 Organic farms in the Danish pig case study based with either more than 50 sows or 100 weaners or 100 finishers

Year	Stages	Organic	
		Farms (N°)	Average herd size within stage
2016	1 st stage (sows)	38	177
	2 nd stage (weaners)	43	612
	3 rd stage (finishers)	73	799
2017	1 st stage (sows)	39	180
	2 nd stage (weaners)	54	1060
	3 rd stage (finishers)	83	781
	1 st stage (sows)	46	160

2018	2 nd stage (weaners)	61	664
	3 rd stage (finishers)	94	676
2019	1 st stage (sows)	32	164
	2 nd stage (weaners)	43	532
	3 rd stage (finishers)	60	601
2020	1 st stage (sows)	30	186
	2 nd stage (weaners)	39	553
	3 rd stage (finishers)	62	707

5.2.3 Results

The development in AMU can be seen in Table 5-7 for the years 2016-2020 categorised by the different age groups in the organic herds. The AMU is calculated based on the total number of doses within age group and the total number of animals within age group. The herd median is also given in brackets. The results show that the AMU is slightly decreasing in the 5-year period for all age groups. However, the numbers are influenced by major contributions from a few herds with very substantial AMU that are not present (classified as organic) for all the five years. For all years and age groups, the herd medians are way lower than then overall average, indicating high skewness in the distribution of AMU in the herds, with a substantial proportion of the herds with no AMU.

Table 5-7 Antimicrobial use in adjusted daily doses (ADD) per 100 animals per day from 2016 to 2020 for the three age groups: Sows and piglets, weaners, and finishers in the organic farms. The AMU is given as an overall average of the total use divided by the total animal population. The values in brackets are the herd-median AMU

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sows and piglets	1.20 (0.00)	2.03 (1.13)	2.57 (1.23)	0.65 (0.28)	0.70 (0.21)
Weaners	1.95 (0.20)	1.46 (0.00)	3.41 (0.00)	1.29 (0.13)	1.10 (0.34)
Finishers	1.67 (0.15)	1.44 (0.19)	1.84 (0.31)	1.23 (0.34)	0.71 (0.33)

Information on the actual diagnoses that the antibiotics are prescribed for is not available but are the organ system the antibiotics is prescribed for. The AMU in ADD/100 animals/day divided on the different organ systems can be seen in Table 5-8.

Table 5-8 Antimicrobial use in ADD/100 animals/day in organic herds distributed on the different organ systems the antibiotic was prescribed for (across all years)

Organ system	Sows/piglets	Weaners	Finishers
Reproduction, Urogenital system	0.31	0.11	<0.01

Udder	0.02	<0.01	<0.01
Gastro-intestinal	0.06	1.46	1.27
Respiratory	0.05	0.05	0.13
Joint, limbs, claws, central nervous system, skin	1.09	0.41	0.49
Metabolic and circulatory system	0.02	<0.01	<0.01

The results clearly show that most treatments with antimicrobials are for weaners and finishers with gastro-intestinal disease (post-weaning diarrhoea). For sows and piglets, joint and limb lesions are the most predominant.

In Table 5-9, the distributions of the doses of antibiotics in percentages within each age group and year can be seen. The results show that for Sows and piglets more than 90% of the doses used are Highly Important Antimicrobials (HIA). For weaners more than 50% of the doses are CIA and CIA* in 2017-2020. For finishers less than 20% of the doses are CIA and CIA*. There are some fluctuations in the different groups of antimicrobials over the years, which most likely is related to the low number of farms and influenced from a few large farms.

Table 5-9 Distribution of the Adjusted Daily Doses (ADD) in percentages within age group and year on the WHO classification of antibiotic importance in organic pig herds. The WHO classification consists of Highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA), Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA), Highly Important Antimicrobials (HIA) and Important Antimicrobials (AI)*

Age group	WHO classification	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sows and Piglets	CIA*	5.5	8.0	6.6	4.2	7.7
	CIA	2.0	0.8	0.3	0.3	0.9
	HIA	92.2	91.1	92.9	95.5	91.3
	IA	0.3	0.1	0.02	0	0.1
Weaners	CIA*	16.2	60.8	66.7	51.4	52.2
	CIA	0.7	0.6	1.2	4.8	10.5
	HIA	82.3	37.4	31.1	35.1	37.0
	IA	0.8	1.2	1.0	8.6	0.3
Finishers	CIA*	4.3	6.8	16.6	16.1	9.8
	CIA	3.2	0.3	4.2	0.1	1.5
	HIA	70.0	74.1	75.9	79.1	77.0
	IA	22.5	18.8	3.3	4.7	11.6

The group of High Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA*) is generally represented by macrolides and lincosamides (like tylosin, tilmicosin, tulathromycin and gamethromycin).

5.3 Conventional free-range system

5.3.1 Background

Approximately 1% of Danish pigs are raised in conventional free-range systems. In these systems, farrowing sows live outdoor on fields with huts for farrowing. Thus, all pigs are born outside. At weaning (minimum 5 weeks of age) pigs are typically moved to indoor pens with outdoor access. Outdoor access is required throughout their entire life. Bedding material is required, and straw is provided for this purpose. Roughage is required during the whole life and is typically provided as silage. Examples on requirements regarding stocking density for different types of pigs: from weaning until 25 kg of weight: 0.23 m² indoor area + 0.17 m² outdoor area per pig. From 95 to 110 kg of weight: 0.7 m² indoor area + 0.5 m² outdoor area per pig. Regulations on AMU are the same as in indoor-conventional: Farmer’s use of antibiotics is permitted if he/she has a formal agreement with the vet, who visits the farm regularly. At these visits, the vet prescribes medicine for the coming (1-2 months) based on his/her knowledge of the farm and clinical judgement at the visit. If batch medication is prescribed for diarrhoea or airway-related problems, at least once a year diagnostic samples have to be taken for identification of pathogens. For a summary of legal requirements and comparison with the two other systems in the Case study, see Table 5-5.

5.3.2 Methods

The two national databases VetStat and CHR are also used for this the data collection on conventional free-range farms and we applied the same selection criteria as for the conventional indoor production systems. However due to the limited number of conventional free-range farms, all the farms that fulfilled the inclusion criteria were included in the data. Table 5-10 presents an overview of the number of conventional free-range farms and the averages farm size for each age group in the 5-year period.

Table 5-10 Conventional free-range farms in the Danish pig case study based with eighter more than 50 sows or 100 weaners or 100 finishers

Year	Stages	Conventional free-range farms	
		Farms (N°)	Average herd size within
2016	1 st stage (sows)	17	301
	2 nd stage (weaners)	20	1094
	3 rd stage (finishers)	29	793
2017	1 st stage (sows)	20	303
	2 nd stage (weaners)	15	1066
	3 rd stage (finishers)	28	973
2018	1 st stage (sows)	19	316
	2 nd stage (weaners)	20	1195
	3 rd stage (finishers)	30	1066
2019	1 st stage (sows)	13	277
	2 nd stage (weaners)	11	1375

Year	Stages	Conventional free-range farms	
		Farms (N°)	Average herd size within
2020	3 rd stage (finishers)	19	1063
	1 st stage (sows)	14	283
	2 nd stage (weaners)	13	1435
	3 rd stage (finishers)	21	1189

5.3.3 Results

The development in AMU can be seen in Table 4-11 for the years 2016-2020, categorised by the different age groups in the conventional free-range herds. The AMU is calculated based on the total number of doses within age group and the total number of animals within age group. The herd median is also given in brackets. The results show that the AMU is increasing in the 5-year period for sows and piglets. However, the numbers are influenced by major contributions from a few herds with very substantial AMU that are not present (classified as conventional free-range) for all the five years. For all years and age groups, the herd medians are lower than the overall average, indicating skewness in the distribution of AMU in the herds, with a substantial proportion of the herds with low AMU.

Table 5-11 Antimicrobial use in adjusted daily doses (ADD) per 100 animals per day from 2016 to 2020 for the three age groups: Sows and piglets, weaners and finishers in the conventional free-range farms. The AMU is given as an overall average of the total use divided by the total animal population. The values in brackets are the herd-median AMU

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sows and piglets	1.32 (0.65)	1.63 (0.58)	1.46 (0.58)	3.39 (2.04)	3.23 (0.83)
Weaners	11.22 (6.34)	11.11 (9.00)	9.58 (4.07)	20.80 (4.11)	18.66 (4.12)
Finishers	1.72 (0.84)	2.14 (1.30)	2.06 (1.00)	3.58 (1.13)	2.55 (1.85)

Information on the actual diagnoses that the antibiotics are prescribed for is not available, but are the organ system the antibiotics is prescribed for. The AMU in ADD/100 animals/day divided on the different organ systems can be seen in Table 5-12.

Table 5-12 Antimicrobial use in ADD/100 animals/day in conventional free-range herds distributed on the different organ systems the antibiotic was prescribed for (across all years)

Organ system	Sows/piglets	Weaners	Finishers
Reproduction, Urogenital system	0.54	<0.01	<0.01
Udder	0.08	<0.01	<0.01
Gastro-intestinal	0.07	8.93	1.05
Respiratory	0.06	2.04	0.04
Joint, limbs, claws, central nervous system, skin	1.28	2.73	1.26

Metabolic and circulatory system	<0.01	0.01	<0.01
----------------------------------	-------	------	-------

The results clearly shows that most treatments with antimicrobials are for weaners and finishers with gastro-intestinal disease (post-weaning diarrhoea). For sows and piglets as well as finishers, joint and limb lesions are the most predominant.

In Table 5-13, the distributions of the doses of antibiotics in percentages within age group and year can be seen. The results show that for Sows and piglets more than 60% of the doses are Highly Important Antimicrobials (HIA) in the period 2017-2020. For weaners, generally more than 50% of the doses are CIA and CIA*. For finishers less than 30% of the doses are CIA and CIA*. There are some fluctuations in the different groups of antimicrobials over the years, which most likely is related to the low number of farms and influence from a few large farms.

Table 5-13 Distribution of the Adjusted Daily Doses (ADD) in percentages within age group and year on the WHO classification of antibiotic importance in conventional free-range pig herds. The WHO classification consists of Highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA), Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA), Highly Important Antimicrobials (HIA) and Important Antimicrobials (AI)*

Age group	WHO classi-	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sows and Piglets	CIA*	13.9	1.8	7.1	11.6	12.0
	CIA	27.6	23.3	23.6	17.1	16.8
	HIA	58.1	74.7	68.9	69.6	70.7
	IA	0.3	0.2	0.4	1.7	0.5
Weaners	CIA*	43.1	36.9	37.1	53.5	36.0
	CIA	16.1	12.6	15.0	15.6	13.1
	HIA	28.7	38.3	31.7	24.6	36.0
	IA	12.1	12.2	16.2	6.3	14.9
Finishers	CIA*	8.6	17.2	25.3	22.5	7.8
	CIA	5.7	5.7	2.8	4.2	6.2
	HIA	69.7	65.3	50.4	58.1	55.6
	IA	16.0	11.8	21.5	15.1	30.4

The group of High Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA*) is generally represented by macrolides and lincosamides (like tylosin, tilmicosin, tulathromycin and gamethromycin).

5.4 Comparison of Pig production systems in Denmark

The farm sizes of the three different production systems are systematically different, where the average organic herd was around 170 sows, the conventional free-range farms around 330 sows and the conventional herds around 700 sows. There are differences in the access to antimicrobials, where the veterinarian must initiate treatments in the organic farms, whereas in the conventional farms the farmer can initiate treatments if there is a formal agreement between farmer and veterinarian. In this case study we have chosen to present the AMU as adjusted daily doses (ADD) per 100 animals/day.

This is a treatment incidence and the link to the actual amount antimicrobial used is lost. AMU in the conventional farms is substantially larger than in the organic herds, especially for weaners where it is 8-10 times larger. For both conventional, organic, and conventional free-range production systems there are large variations between farms within the production systems and especially for free-range and organic there is large proportion of the farms with low or no AMU. The number of farms representing organic (<62) and free-range conventional herds (<30) are low, which make it difficult to interpret possible trends over time.

Within all three production systems, the AMU was primarily driven by GI-problems in weaners. Note, however, the very low usage in organic systems.

In this data set no use of fluoroquinolones was found and only a few prescriptions of cephalosporins. All other use of High Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA*) was represented by macrolides and lincosamides (like tylosin, tilmicosin, tulathromycin and gamethromycin). The CIA* were used in considerable extend (>30% in weaners) in all production systems (as a proportion of all the antimicrobial doses used), but also in conventional finishers. It seems to exist differences in the antimicrobial types used in the different production systems but also some fluctuation over time. Further and more detailed analyses are needed to address this issue.

Note: Comparing treatment incidents between systems (Table 5-2; Table 5-7 and Table 5-11) is tricky as the averages do not say much because of many “non-users” and “very-low-users” in free-range and organic systems. Median values should probably be used for comparison.

6 Case study analysis: dairy production in Denmark

6.1 Background

6.1.1 Conventional dairy production

More than 85% of the Danish milk production comes from conventional production systems, which means that they only should comply with national and EU legislation on stable design, population density and management procedures (minimum requirements). Most of the cows are housed in free stalls with cubicles and feed with partial or total mixed rations of grass and corn silage. Tie stalls are still allowed but will be abandoned in 2027. Even though it is not mandatory to have conventional cows on pasture, some farmers still choose to do so. Heifer calves and heifers are in most cases kept on the herd whereas bull calves are sold to special fattening units at early age. The average milk production for conventional cows is just above 10.000 kg milk/year.

In conventional herds, farmers can have access to initiate and complete treatments on cows and young stock/calves for specific diseases if the farmer has a herd health contract with the veterinarian. The herd health contracts set the framework for access to prescription medicine and the number of herd visits the farmer needs to have by his veterinarian.

6.1.2 Organic dairy production

Organic herds need to comply with the same minimum requirements as the conventional herds in addition to the stricter rules on several aspects of production. Cows should have access to pasture at least 6 hours a day from April 15th to November 1st, if the weather makes it possible. Also calves have to stay at least 24 hours with the cow after birth (compared to 12 hours in conventional herds). The average milk production for organic cows is around 9.000 kg milk/year. Organic herd sizes are approaching conventional herd sizes, but requirement of pasture sets a size limit for this production systems.

The Danish regulations on organic dairy production state that the veterinarians must perform all treatments on cows and initiate all treatments on calves and young stock. The withdrawal period for milk and meat after treatment with antibiotics is set to be twice as for the conventional withdrawal period. Organic dairy herds are encouraged to maintain a low antimicrobial use due to the restrictions set by EU regulations for organic livestock production, which limit antimicrobial treatment courses for breeding animals to a maximum of three times per year, and for slaughter animals to a maximum of once per year.

6.2 Methods

All use of antibiotics prescribed by a veterinarian is recorded in a national database named **VetStat**. Data of the use of antibiotics can come from three different sources –the pharmacies that deliver the prescribed antibiotics to the farmer, the veterinarian that use or hand over antibiotics on the farm, and feed mills for the occasions where the antibiotics is delivered to the farm in premixed feed. In comparison with the data on prescribed antibiotics in Danish pig production, this data is more diverse,

because there are far more records that come from (many different) veterinarians and instead of primarily from a limited number of pharmacies. Every record in VetStat should include a unique farm identification number, the age group of cattle and the organ system the antibiotics is prescribed for. Three age groups are possible for cattle: Adult animals (cows, bulls (>24 mo.)), young stock (between 6 and 24 mo.) and calves (<6 mo.). In this study the two latter (young stock and calves) have been aggregated.

For each antibiotic product prescribed the amount of antibiotic active substance (AB_{as}) was calculated and used as a measure of antimicrobial use (AMU). For products where the concentrations were given in international units (iU) these were converted using the website: <https://mypharmatools.com/othertools/iu>.

Cattle in Denmark is individually recorded, and all movements are recorded as well. Based on these basic recordings the 12-mo. herd size (1 cow for 365 days = 1 cow-year) is calculated and available from the Central Husbandry Register (**CHR**). The population size is provided within two age groups, cows and young stock/calves. Based on the AMU in the different age groups and recording of the animal population within farm, we calculated the grams of active substance divided by 100 animal-year.

Based on these populations sizes we classified herds with more than 50 cow-year/year and declared to be producing milk as being professional farmers in 2016-2020. This selection of herds gave between 1937 and 2100 conventional herds and between 271 and 286 organic herds depending on the year. It is possible that some of the herds have changed the production system in the period. On these herds and years, we extracted data from VetStat on the antimicrobial use and from the CHR on animal population in these herds for the 5-year period 2016-2020. A descriptive table of the herd and number of animals included in this subset of the Danish cattle population can be seen in Table 6-1.

Table 6-1 Descriptive statistics of the Danish conventional and organic dairy herds based on herds with more than 50 cow-year annually

		2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Conventional	Number of herds	2096	2100	2085	2016	1937
	Avg. number of cows in herd (1.-3. Quartile)	200 (119-248)	207 (120-256)	213 (120-262)	221 (122-274)	228 (124-283)
	Number of calves/young stock (1.-3. Quartile)	178 (106-218)	183 (107-225)	185 (106-223)	189 (108-226)	194 (107-236)
Organic	Number of herds	286	281	277	280	271
	Avg. number of cows in herd (1.-3. Quartile)	174 (107-200)	183 (112-213)	190 (116-216)	191 (117-212)	199 (121-229)
	Number of calves/young stock (1.-3. Quartile)	162 (106-193)	172 (109-205)	184 (110-227)	184 (110-218)	185 (110-219)

Note: Data extracted from the Central Husbandry Register (CHR)

Table 6-1 shows an increase in the average number of cows in both production systems over the 5 year period and a simultaneous decrease in the number of herds.

6.3 Results

The development in AMU can be seen in Table 6-2 for the years 2016-2020 split on the different production systems and age groups. The AMU is calculated based on the total amount of antibiotics (AB_{as}) in grams divided by the total number of animal-year within age group and production system. The herd median is also given in brackets. The results show that the AMU is almost unchanged in the 5-year period with a slight tendency to decrease in both production systems. For all years and age groups, the herd medians are lower than then overall average, indicating some skewness in the distribution of AMU in the herds.

Table 6-2 Antimicrobial use in grams of antibiotic active substance per year-animal from 2016 to 2020 for two age groups. The AMU is given as an overall average of the total use divided by the total number of animal year. The values in brackets is the herd-median AMU

		2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Conventional	Cows	19.3 (15.3)	18.4 (14.6)	18.8 (14.4)	18.6 (14.4)	18.5 (14.3)
	Calves/youngstock	1.8 (1.0)	1.7 (0.9)	1.8 (1.0)	1.8 (1.0)	1.8 (1.0)
Organic	Cows	6.5 (5.0)	6.4 (4.7)	6.7 (4.6)	6.4 (4.4)	6.2 (4.2)
	Calves/youngstock	1.7 (0.9)	1.6 (0.9)	1.8 (0.9)	1.6 (0.9)	1.2 (2.4)

Information on the actual disease that the antibiotics are prescribed for is not available. However, the veterinarian is obliged to provide the organ system the antibiotics is prescribed for. For instance, it can be assumed for example that antibiotics classified as being used for a udder disease is related to mastitis or dry cow treatments. The AMU in grams of antibiotic substance per animal-year can be seen in Table 6-3.

Table 6-3 Antimicrobial use in grams of active substance per animal year distributed on the different organ systems the antibiotic was prescribed for.

Organ system	Conventional		Organic	
	Cows	Calves/ young stock	Cows	Young Stock
Reproduction, Urogenital system	2.22	0.09	0.69	0.08
Udder	13.62	0.06	4.11	0.18
Gastro-intestinal	0.12	0.30	0.14	0.20
Respiratory	0.20	0.92	0.15	0.85
Joint, limbs, claws, central nervous system, skin	2.26	0.35	1.17	0.47
Metabolic and circulatory system	0.18	0.31	0.11	0.03

The results clearly show the majority of treatments with antimicrobials are being used for diseases related to udder in both conventional and organic herds.

Table 6-4 presents the distributions of antibiotics according to the WHO classification of antibiotic importance in percentages within age group and year in the conventional and organic production system.

The results show that for cows, less than 1.2% of the amount of antibiotics used are Highest priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA*) and less than 5% for the calves. CIA* and CIA together account for around 10% of the total amount used for conventional dairy cows, but around 15%-20% of the organic cows.

Generally, there are minor fluctuations in the different groups and production systems over the years, except for the organic production system in 2020. The reason for this substantial drop in CIA and CIA* was the acceptance of an industry code, that restricted the use of antibiotics to narrow-spectrum antibiotics.

Table 6-4 Distribution of the amount of active antibiotic substances in percentages within age group and year on the WHO classification of antibiotic importance in the two production systems. The WHO classification consists of Highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA), Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA), Highly Important Antimicrobials (HIA) and Important Antimicrobials (AI)*

Age group		WHO classification	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Conventional	Cows	CIA*	1.2	1.1	1.2	0.9	0.9
		CIA	8.9	9.3	9.9	10.6	9.7
		HIA	89.9	89.6	88.9	88.5	89.4
	Calves and young stock	CIA*	3.7	3.6	3.9	3.2	4.1
		CIA	31.5	34.0	30.8	30.1	28.7
		HIA	64.8	62.4	65.2	65.6	67.2
Organic	Cows	CIA*	1.2	1.1	1.1	1.0	0.4
		CIA	14.2	13.7	17.4	18.9	2.7
		HIA	84.6	85.3	81.5	80.1	96.9
	Calves and young stock	CIA*	3.9	3.6	2.0	1.9	0.8
		CIA	33.7	27.5	30.0	27.3	4.6
		HIA	62.3	68.9	68.0	70.8	94.6

The group of Highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA*) concerns mostly of cephalosporins for the cows and macrolides and lincosamides (like tulathromycin). There were only 5 entries of fluoroquinolones in the data (from 2016).

6.4 Comparison of cattle production systems in Denmark

Over the analysed period, the overall herd size increased. The farm sizes of the two different production systems are slightly different with the organic average herd size being 30 cows lower than the conventional herds on average. There are differences in the access to antimicrobials, where the veterinarian must initiate treatments in the organic herd, whereas in the conventional herds the farmer can initiate treatments if there is a formal agreement between farmer and veterinarian. In this case study we have chosen to present the AMU in grams of active antimicrobial component per animal-year. This provides a clearer information on the actual amount of antibiotic used on herds, the production systems, and the national consumption. However, the drawback lies on the fact that different antibiotics

have different dosages, so changes in prescription pattern to less critical antibiotics can lead to an increase in total amount (grams) of antibiotics used.

AMU for cows in the conventional farms are substantially (3 times) larger than in the organic herds. For calves and offspring there are no systematic differences. For both conventional, organic production systems, there is large variation between herds within the production systems. Over the 5-year period, there is no clear trends of reduction or increase in the average AMU in both production systems.

For the conventional and organic herds, the AMU is primarily associated with udder diseases and in calves and young stock with gastro-intestinal and respiratory disease.

Very little use of fluoroquinolones was found in this data set. The use of Highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials (CIA*) was entirely cephalosporins in cows and mostly macrolides and lincosamides (like tulathromycin). The CIA were used in considerable extent (30% in calves and young stock) in both production systems (as a proportion of the amount of antibiotics used). It does not seem to have differences in the antimicrobial types used in the different production systems, with the exception of 2020 in the organic production system, which is related to agreement of an industrial code limiting the use of anything but narrow spectrum antibiotics.

7 Case study analysis: pig, poultry, and dairy cows production in France

7.1 Monitoring AMU in French farms

7.1.1 AMU reduction targets for farms

The fight against antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a major public health issue. In France, animal production sectors have fully committed to the [Ecoantibio](#) plan, which has resulted in a wide contribution to reduction of antimicrobial uses (AMU). Indeed, this plan is a public policy set up by the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry in 2012. It concerns all animal sectors (including pets) and covers all French territories. Its aim is to reduce the risks of AMR in veterinary medicine and to preserve the effectiveness of antimicrobials as recommended by the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE), the World Health Organisation (WHO), the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) and various European institutions.

The law on the future of agriculture, food, and forestry (LAAAF of 13 October 2014) reinforced the target of AMU reduction, focusing on a reduction of 25% over three years (2014-2016) in the exposure of animals to critically important antimicrobials, i.e., new generation fluoroquinolones and cephalosporins. This objective was achieved and even greatly exceeded in 2016. Thus, the first plan from 2012 to 2016 proved to be a real success with a 37% reduction over five years. Now, the next plan ([EcoAnti-bio2](#), 2017-2021) encourages prudent and reasoned use of antimicrobials. It mainly focuses on incentives to reduce AMU rather than on quantified objectives. Communication and training play a major role to reduce AMU, as do useful alternatives to antimicrobials, improvements in preventive measures for infectious diseases and provision of the best tools for diagnosis, monitoring sales of antimicrobials and tracking resistance to them.

7.1.2 The ANSES reporting

Monitoring of AMU and the prevalence of bacterial resistance are essential elements to assess the risks linked to AMR and facilitate the management of support measures. The need of accurate data on the AMU by species and animals' categories is a crucial issue, which is regularly recalled at European level.

In France, the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health Safety (Anses) has been monitoring sales of antimicrobial-based medicines since 1999¹³. This work is based on the World Health Organisation's recommendations (OIE). Thus, Anses uses annual sales reporting made by pharmaceutical companies marketing these antimicrobials. The information collected from pharmaceutical companies covers 100% of authorized veterinary medicinal products. The breakdown of sales of medicines by species of destination (cattle, pigs, poultry, etc.) is based on an estimate provided by the laboratories.

Based on this data collection, Anses provides an annual report in November each year describing the monitoring of veterinary antimicrobial sales for the year n-1, with a historical comparison of the results

¹³ Anses, 2019. Suivi des ventes de médicaments vétérinaires contenant des antibiotiques en France en 2018 Rapport annuel.

since the beginning of the implementation of this collection system. This report presents two types of indicators:

- **sales indicators** that make it possible to monitor changes in the weight quantities of antimicrobials sold over time : tonnage of active ingredient sold (tonnes)
- **indicators of animal exposure** to better represent the use of antimicrobials to treat animals. Indeed, the different antimicrobials used in veterinary medicine have different dosages and activities. Newer antimicrobials are often more active and are therefore administered at lower doses. The dosage and duration of treatment are important to consider, as well as fluctuations in the animal population over time. The report therefore presents two types of indicators of animal exposure:
 - The weight of active ingredient sold in relation to the animal biomass (mg/kg live weight),
 - and three indicators of animal exposure at the population level:
 - **Treated live weight-day**, which consists of dividing the weight of active ingredient of each drug by the daily dose value required for all drug presentations sold for that species.
 - **Treated live weight**, which consists of dividing the weight of active ingredient of each drug by the dose value for a complete treatment of one kg of animal live weight for all drug presentations sold for that species. The dose for a complete treatment of one kg of animal live weight is therefore the daily dose multiplied by the duration of the treatment.
 - **The Animal Level of Exposure to Antimicrobials (ALEA)** is calculated by dividing the treated live weight by the biomass of the animal population potentially using antimicrobials.

The calculation of these indicators is based on data available in the [Index of Veterinary Medicinal Products Authorized in France](#). The Anses report, published in 2020, states that the changes of data presented in Summaries of Product Characteristics (SPCs), that took place during 2019 for certain veterinary medicinal products were included in the analysis of sales for the year 2019, but this correction was not included in the historical data of the system.

The following points aims to summarize the main results of the 2020 report:

- The tonnage of active ingredient sold amount to 422 tonnes in 2019. It decreased by around 11% compared to the previous year and it is the lowest ever recorded since the monitoring began (1999). This drop can be mainly attributed to the sharp decrease in oral administration.
- Concerning the indicators of animal exposure, there has been an overall decrease of 45.3% over the 2011-2019 period, the reference year considered by the French national reduction plan "Ecoantibio". We can also underline that the main objective of the first plan was met, with a 36.5% decrease in animal exposure to antibiotics during this five-year period (2012-2016). Thus, the total ALEA calculated in 2019 amounts to 0.329, (0.328 for cattle, 0.396 for poultry and 0.508 for pigs).
 - This decrease is particularly significant for medicated feeds (-74.4%), as well as for powder and oral solution (-51.4%).

- This decrease applies to all species: -25.5% for cattle, -54.0% for pigs, -60.5% for poultry, -41.4% for rabbits and -13.9% for domestic carnivores (Figure 7-1).Figure 7-1
- The year 2019 is the lowest level of animal exposure since the beginning of the monitoring, but there is a stabilization trend over the last 3 years except for Tetracyclines and Polypeptides (Figure 7-2).

Figure 7-1 Comparison of ALEA by species (A) cattle, (B) pigs, (C) poultry between 2011 and 2019 (Anses, 2020)

Figure 7-2 Comparison of ALEA by species (A) cattle, (B) pigs, (C) poultry between 2011 and 2019 (Anses, 2020)

Concerning antimicrobials considered "critical" (fluoroquinolons, 3rd and 4th generation of cephalosporins, colistin): a significant drop is observed for Fluoroquinolons (-86% for all species) and the latest generation of Cephalosporins (-94.1%) compared to 2013. Here too, a stabilization trend is observed which encourages us to remain vigilant about the future evolution of these indicators. For colistin, exposure decreased significantly in 2019 (-64.2%) compared with the reference year 2014-2015. Anses states that the objective of -50% set by the Ecoantibio2 plan has been achieved for the pig, poultry,

and beef sectors. The level of exposure expressed in the European unit (according to European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption) is 1.40 mg/PCU (below the recommended threshold of 5 mg/PCU).

We can notice that the indicators of animal exposure presented in this annual report, and in particular the ALEA, are based on the hypothesis that all the antimicrobial products sold during the year were administered to animals reared on the national territory during that year. In its 2015 report, the Anses points out that this hypothesis may not be fully verified for sales in 2014. Indeed, a change in the regulations affecting the rules of distribution and/or dispensing of antimicrobials products in France could have generated a stockpiling effect, which would imply a significant gap between sales and real use.

Another constraint highlighted by Anses is that these data do not allow the production of precise references reflecting the diversity of species, animal's categories, and production sectors, particularly for livestock production. For poultry, for example, it is currently not possible to make the distinction between the exposure of broilers, turkeys or laying hens.

The transmission of data by the entitled parties on the sell-off medicines containing antimicrobials used in veterinary medicine to direct users, should make it possible to remedy this problem. For example, in 2019, Anses has published a first report on the sell-off medicated animal feeds containing antimicrobials in France (Chevenance et al, 2019). This report concerns only the first two quarters of 2018 but already allows some conclusions about the uses for different species and categories of animals. This report highlighted very different patterns between species/categories of animals, concerning the administration of antimicrobials via animal feed. This result argues in favour of a more precise monitoring system that will ultimately provide a better understanding of the uses and a more precise steering of the accompanying measures.

Furthermore, a comparison between data on divestment of medicated animal feeds containing antimicrobials and those on sales of veterinary antimicrobials leads to consider an under evaluation of minor species productions' AMU. Indeed, laboratories don't sufficiently take into account the amount of antimicrobials prescribed as part of the therapeutic "waterfall" (i.e. outside of the recommendations of the marketing authorization). On the contrary, this would lead to slightly overestimating the use of antimicrobials for pigs and poultry and underestimating it for sheep, goats, rabbits, and other species. However, this remains to be confirmed later.

7.1.3 Improving AMU monitoring in French farms

In France, several projects have been initiated during the first Ecoantibio plan to better estimate AMU by species, animals' categories, or physiological stage. In particular, the Ecoantibio plan (2012-2016) recommended the creation of self-assessment tools for farmers and veterinarians on the use of antimicrobials in animal husbandry.

In this context, IFIP (The French Pig and Pork Institute) and Anses have set up the GVET approach ([Management of VETerinary Treatments](#)). This approach meets two complementary objectives: to modernize the records treatments and to measure the AMU in pork farms. IFIP and Anses proposed to software publishers a specific set of specifications for collecting and monitoring AMU at farms level. This computerized farm register makes it possible to provide farmers with a follow-up of their antimicrobial use through indicators such as the number of treatments and the number of days of treatment per pig for each animals' categories.

In the French pig Production, another tool provides accurate, reliable, and detailed references in terms of antimicrobial use in swine production: its name is INAPORC PANEL (Hémonic et al., 2019). This tool consists in surveys of representative samples of farms. Up to now, three surveys have been done in 2010, 2013 and 2016 and a fourth survey is now in progress. The farms are randomly selected from the French Database (BDPORC). From 2010 to 2016, the decrease in ALEA estimated by Anses (-47%) and the INAPORC panels (-52%) was similar. However, the ALEA estimated by the IN-APORC panels in 2010, 2013 and 2016 were always lower than those of Anses, suggesting overestimation of the volume allocated to pigs during the stratification of sales by species. Over the six years, the mean number of treatment days significantly decreased for all age categories of animals. However, for sows the decrease was less marked (-7%) than for suckling piglets (-28%), weaned piglets (-70%) and fatteners (-71%). Other major results included a considerable decrease in the use of critically important antibiotics (kept in priority for human medicine), premixes and colistin. This did not result in increased use of other digestive antibiotics or in a massive use of zinc oxide (16% of farms using zinc oxide in 2016).

In 2016, Anses-ANMV and IDELE (Institut de l'Élevage) have also set up a permanent observatory on AMU in veal calf farms has been set up by at the request of the [INTERBEV Veaux interprofession](#). Deployed among a panel of volunteer breeders, this approach has enabled for the first time, the calculation of various standardized indicators that are both simple and comparable. This observatory provides complementary data regarding the annual sales monitoring report. A computer tool specifically developed by Anses, allows analysing data and enabling farmers to assess their AMU with the help of breeding technicians and veterinarians. The first results of the observatory were published in [2018](#).

For the poultry sector, from 2001 to 2008, Anses implemented farm surveys and monitoring tools to provide references on the AMU at farm level (Chauvin et al, 2005). A survey was renewed in 2012 for conventional broiler and turkey productions at the request of the inter-professional association. This work permitted to improve references on the AMU in the poultry sector but did not last over time. The only permanent AMU monitoring system concerned the "Label Rouge" poultry production, which is conducted by the Union of quality poultry production (Synalaf). A quarterly indicator of the frequency of antimicrobial use is generated (Adam, 2017), however these data are not published and remain for internal monitoring among Synalaf members.

The Ecoantibio2017 plan has led to the emergence of the RefA²vi project, which aims to formalize a professional network for the collection of computerized data on the AMU for poultry farms (Rousset et al, 2019). The RefA²vi network is a national and professional network, which aims to produce regular references on indicators of animal exposure to antimicrobials. These indicators are calculated with a common method and are expressed by poultry species, in particular turkeys and broilers. A working group composed by ITAVI, Anses and the inter-professional association "ANVOL" oversees the data collection. The method that is used to calculate indicators is generally based on that of the ALEA and provides references by poultry species, particularly turkeys and broilers

Based on the French agricultural statistics [data](#), the network represents 39% of the volume of broilers and turkeys slaughtered in France in 2018, of which 33% is broilers and 43% turkey. In 2018, the "treated live weight-day" divided by the total mass of broiler slaughtered over the same period is 0.677. The "treated live weight" divided by the total mass of broilers slaughtered is 0.135. For turkeys, the "treated live weight-day" divided by the total mass of turkeys slaughtered is 1.469. The "treated live weight" divided by the total mass of turkeys slaughtered is 0.336. As a reminder, for the same year, the ALEA calculated by dividing the "treated live weight" by the biomass of the animal population potentially using antimicrobials, was estimated at 0.454.

According to the RefA²vi network, broilers are treated mainly with Polypeptids, Penicillins, then with Sulfonamides-trimethoprim and Tetracyclins. Turkeys are mainly treated with polypeptids, penicillins, tetracyclins and then with sulfonamide-trimethoprim. These results are consistent with the data published by Anses for the year 2018.

7.2 AMU in French dairy production

7.2.1 Methods

In France, for the dairy sector, there is no national database regarding antibiotic uses. Therefore, for this analysis, the data were collected through the qualitative surveys conducted for the project WP2. Eight conventional and six organic dairy farms were interviewed. Each interview lasted around 2 hours and were conducted directly on the farm or by videoconference.

Farms were identified by BCEL Ouest (Brittany Farms Advice, a milk control structure) and GDS Bretagne (Health Protection Group of Brittany). They were all located in Brittany (Figure 7-3), which concentrates the highest share of the French of dairy farms (20% of the breeding herd is in Brittany, *Source: “Key figures Cattle 2020” SPIE-BDNI base, processing French Livestock Institute*). There were no specific selection criteria (except to try to have as much conventional as organic farms).

Figure 7-3 French map of dairy production concentration

Source: [CNIEL, 2021](#)

This, the sample is not representative of the French situation and the diversity of practices of health management because of two reasons:

- a) Farmers selected by advisers were volunteers;
- b) Farmers were probably used to answer surveys and to talk about use of AM or health management.

Besides qualitative data about health management and AMU of farmers, we collected some technical indicators. Moreover, with the approval of each farmer, we obtained from their respective veterinarians the invoices of quantity and commercial name of the AM sold to the farmer on the year 2020.

To evaluate antibiotics sold in each farm, we use a tool developed for another project (IdEA, 2021). It permits to sum the total amounts (in g/dairy cows) of active ingredient of all antibiotics purchased, whether the initial concentrations were expressed in IU or in grams.

The Data collected represent quantities of AM sold by veterinarians to the farmers. This is probably not exactly the quantity used by each farmer because a part of AM purchased may not have been administered to animals. Moreover, in farms with other animal production species, the AM sold to the farm are not differentiated from a herd to another. Therefore, quantity of AM used by each farmer is probably overestimated.

As we don't have for the French dairy sector any reference about AMU in farms, we compared our results with results of two projects:

- IDEA: "Innovation for a better support of the Normandy dairy farmers to the use of antibiotics". This project aims at a continuous improvement of the practices of use of antibiotics in the Normandy dairy farms, to preserve the effectiveness of those treatments (Deschamps, 2020).
- "Factors associated with the use of antibiotics in dairy cattle. Example of the Orne (Normandy)" (Godet, 2015).

7.2.2 Conventional production systems

7.2.2.1 Description of the sample – conventional farms

The Case study Intensive production system is composed of eight conventional farms; that means they are not answering to any specification, neither organic, nor Protection Designation of Origin. The eight conventional farms are described and characterized with the following Table 7-1:

Table 7-1 Characteristics of 8 dairy conventional farms sampled in France

Farms Id	Milk production/year (litres/year)	Milk production/dairy cows (litres/cows/year)	Other production	Proportion of dairy production in sales revenue (%)	Dairy cows number	UAA (ha)
2	1007500	8000	Pigs	68%	126	140
3	350000	8400	Pigs	45%	42	54
4	1700000	9000	?	80%	205	240
7	1 000 000	8750		x	120	100

8	590000	8000	80 suckler-cows + Poultry for meat production	60%	80	80
9	670000	8700	235 calves for slaughter	60%	80	100
10	330000	10000	X	X	37	40
11	1700000	10000	200 young cattle (meet production) + 35 suckler-cows	60%	180	240
Sample average	918437	8856	X	62%	109	124
French average*	385300	7106	X	X	66	92
Inosys average**	730 300	7855	X	X	92	175

UAA: Utilized Agriculture Area

*French average, all systems included.

**Average of all conventional systems in 2019 located in land area of the INOSYS¹⁴ network (200 farms)

The eight conventional farms surveyed (Table 7-2) are on average larger than the French average. Rather intensive, they have an average productivity higher than the French average and higher than the average of the 302 farms of the INOSYS network. All eight have Prim Holsteins (the most represented dairy breed in France with 31%).

Table 7-2 Cow housing system and milking system of conventional dairy farms in France

Farms Id	Housing system	Milking parlour
2	Open straw bedded-pen and slatted floor	Milking parlour
3	Open straw bedded-pen	Milking parlour
4	Free stalls barn	Milking robot
7	102 Free stalls barn and slatted floor	?
8	Free stalls barn on straw	Milking parlour
9	Free stalls barn	Milking robot
10	Free stalls barn	Milking parlour
11	200 Free stalls barn	Milking robot

¹⁴ The purpose of INOSYS network of farms is to produce references on the functioning and sustainability of French livestock production systems. Deployed in all herbivore productions, it relies on a network of 1600 farmers (with more than 15% are organic) monitored by about 200 advisors from the Chambers of Agriculture and various technical organizations run by the French livestock Institute (IDELE). The monitoring of the farms is based on a global approach to the systems, with a collection of data covering a wide range of technical and economic fields, allowing the evaluation of their environmental impact and the analysis of their collective trajectories over time.

Among the eight farms, three have a milking robot (Table 7-3). In France, 8% of the dairy farms have a milking robot (Source: IDELE, 2018). Six have free stalls barn. In 2015 in Brittany, almost 50% of dairy cows are housed in free stall barns against almost 50% in open area (Source: Agreste Bretagne - Février 2019 – 1)

Table 7-3 Area and feeding indicators of conventional dairy farms in France

Farms Id	UAA (ha)	Forage area (hectare)	Proportion of Forage area in the UAA (%)	Quantity of feed purchased (g/l)
2	140	40	28.6	120
3	54	22	40.7	116
4	240	170	70.8	147
7	100	90	90	?
8	80	67	83.8	136
9	100	60	60	167
10	40	30	75	191
11	240	130	54.2	275
Sample average	124.3	76.1	62.9	164.5
Inosys* average	175	111	63.5	218.3

* Average of all conventional systems 2019 located in land area of the INOSYS network (200 farms)

7.2.3 Organic production systems

7.2.3.1 Description of the sample – organic farms

In France, organic dairy production represents 2.4% of the entire milk collection. The territory of Brittany supply 22% of the national organic milk. Organic production shows an increase trend in terms of organic farms number, organic milk production and farms conversion (Agreste Bretagne - Les cahiers régionaux - Janvier 2018 - N°2).

We surveyed six organic dairy farms in Brittany in order to collect information about their systems and to understand their perceptions about AM utilization using the same method described above. These farms are not representative of the diversity of organic production in France for two reasons: our sample is small and the territory chosen is the most specialized/intensified in dairy production in France. Our results must be treated with caution. The six organic farms are described and characterized with the following Table 7-4.

Table 7-4 Characteristics of 6 dairy organic farms sampled in France

Farms (numbered)	Milk production/year (litres/year)	Milk production/dairy cows (litres/cows/year)	Other production	Proportion of dairy production in sales revenue (%)	Dairy cows number	UAA (Utilized Agriculture Area - hectare)
1	450000	6500	Vegetables	69%	65	96

5	200000	5000	Poultry for meat production	X	40	62
6	108000	7200	Pigs and beef cattle	60%	40	130
12	440000	7000	Beef cattle	93%	65	115
13	220000	5000	beef cattle	80%	43	86
14	237000	5500	X	X	50	56

In Brittany, the average herd size is about 59 cows. Our sample is between 40 and 65 cows which corresponds to this average. The surveyed farms seem to correspond to the farms network Inosys which, regroups 40 organic and specialized dairy farms:

- Inosys farms average size is about 90 cows which is higher than the average size of farms interviewed in this study
- The main breed raised in our farms is the Prim'Holstein, but two farms raised also Normande cows.
- In average, the farms from the Inosys network produce 5680 litres per cows and per year. In our sample, it goes from 5000 litres to 7200 litres with an average of 6033 litres produced.
- The average UAA of the Inosys network is 132 hectares. In our sample, the utilized area varies from 56 to 130 hectares.

All interviewed farms were equipped with open straw and milking parlour. We can go into more details by comparing the proportion of pastures in the UAA and the quantity of feed purchased outside the farm with the following Table 7-5.

Table 7-5 Area and feeding indicators of dairy organic farms in France

Farms id	Forage area (hectare)	Proportion of Forage area in the UAA (%)	Quantity of feed purchased (tons)
1	50	52%	0
5	40	64.5%	0
6	110	84.6%	5
12	105	91%	19.5
13	86	90.7%	0
14	45.5	81.25%	6

Farms surveyed in this study seem to correspond to the organic and specialized dairy systems found in lands territory in France regarding the Inosys network. The difference between those farms are high and we can consider two types: the most intensive ones (1, 6 and 12) with the highest production and

utilized area and the less intensive ones (5, 13 and 14) with lowest production and utilized area. It will be helpful for the next comparison about AM utilization.

7.2.4 Health indicators of farms in conventional and organic dairy production systems

Table 7-6 and Table 7-7 summarize the main health indicators from the sampled conventional and organic farms respectively.

Table 7-6 Health indicators of conventional dairy farms in France

	Number of dairy cows	Milk production/year (litres/year)	Number of month with outdoor access	Average age at first calving	Mortality rate of fairy cows (adult) in 2020	Veterinary expenses (€/1000L) in 2020
2	126	1007500	11	25	3,0%	7,6
3	42	350000	8	?	2,4%	15,6
4	205	1700000	8	26	4,0%	11,8
7	120	1000000	8,5	25,5	?	5,0
8	80	590000	6	27,5	5,0%	?
9	80	670000	8	26	10%	7,5
10	37	330000	8	25	5,4%	10,3
11	180	1700000	2	24	2%	9,4
Sample average	109	918438	7,4	25,6	4,5%	9,6
Inosys* average	92	730 300	x	x	x	11,7

continuation... Health indicators of conventional dairy farms in France

	Health expenditure (hygiene, antibiotics,...)	Do you think you use less/as much/more antibiotics (than 5 years ago)	Which health problem uses the most antibiotics?	Does he use alternative treatments to AM?	Systematic treatments for drying period?	Is it easy for you to manage the health of you herd?
2	Stable	Less	Mastitis	No	Yes	Yes
3	stable	Less	Mastitis	No	No	Yes
4	stable	Less	Mastitis + lameness + calves cough + cryptosporidiosis	No	Yes	Yes
7	Decrease	Less	Mastitis	No	Yes	Yes
8	Stable	Less	Mastitis + breathing problem (grazing calves)	No	Yes	Yes
9	Decrease	As much	Mastitis + infection post calving	No	Yes, except summer	Yes
10	Stable	As much	Treatment for drying period + calves diarrhea	No	Yes	Yes and not

11	Decrease	Less	Mastitis + Treatment for drying period	No	Yes	Yes
-----------	----------	------	--	----	-----	-----

* Average of all conventional systems 2019 located in land area of the INOSYS network (200 farms)

To be noticed: the only restriction in terms of use of antibiotics in organic systems is a maximum of 3 treatments per animal and per year.

Table 7-7 Health indicators of organic dairy farms in France

	Number of dairy cows	Milk production/year (litres/year)	Number of month with outdoor access	Average age at first calving	Mortality rate of dairy cows (adult) in 2020	Veterinary expenses (€/1000L) in 2020
1	65	450000	8,5	24	0%	16,7 €
5	40	200000	10	24	3%	5,4 €
6	40	108000	12	27	8%	20,4 €
12	65	440000	9	29	1,5%	13,6 €
13	43	220000	8,5	30	3,5%	2,7 €
14	50	237000	9	27	1,3%	4,6 €
Sample average	50.5	275833	9,5	26,8	3%	11 €
Inosys Average*	90	524000	x	x	x	10€

continuation... Health indicators of organic dairy farms in France

	Health expenditure (hygiene, antibiotics,...)	Do you think you use less/as much/more antibiotics (than 5 years ago)	Which health problem uses the most antibiotics?	Does he use alternative treatments to Antibiotics?	Systematic treatments for drying period?	Is it easy for you to manage the health of you herd?
1	Decrease	Less	Mastitis + dermatitis	Homeopathy, essential oils, acupuncture	No	Stressful
5	stable	As much	Mastitis	Homeopathy, essential oils, acupuncture	No	Yes
6	stable	Less	Mastitis + metritis + calves diarrhoea	Essential oils, osteopathy	No	Yes
12	Decrease	?	Mastitis	Essential oils	No	Yes
13	Stable	Less	Mastitis	Homeopathy	No	Yes
14	Decrease	Less	Mastitis + lameness	Homeopathy, essential oils, acupuncture	No	Yes

* Average of all organic systems 2019 located in land area of the INOSYS network (40 farms)

The six organic farms surveyed have lower mortality rate and lower veterinary expenses than the eight conventional systems surveyed in this study. On average, conventional systems of our sample have

lower veterinary expenses than farms of Inosys network. The organic farms have higher veterinary expenses than the organic farm of Inosys network. Whether in organic or conventional systems, mastitis is the health problem that requires the most antibiotics. Seven out of eight conventional farms use systematically antibiotics at dry off. All organic and conventional farmers said that they use less or as much antibiotic as before, none said it was increasing. All the six organic farms use alternatives to antibiotics (homeopathy, essential oils...). This is not an obligation in organic farms, but farmers are encouraged to use them.

7.2.5 Results

Table 7-8 summarizes the global AM purchase in eight dairy farms surveyed, three organic and five conventional. For the six other farms we didn't manage to collect AMU invoices data. The average purchase is about 21.1g/dairy cows (DC). The median is 14.5 g/DC, which is lower than the global mean. We can explain these difference by the results obtained in farm N°4: the global AM purchase is about 112.6 g/DC which is a lot higher than the results of the other farms of the sample.

Table 7-8 Antimicrobial consumption in conventional and organic farms

	Organic or conventional	Nb of cows (more than 24 month)	Global AM purchased/cows*	Consumption intra mammary/cows*	Critical antibiotic purchased/cows*	Is there another herd on the farm concerned by those AB results?
1	O	65	10	0	0	No
3	C	42	14.5	0.6	0.2	No
4	C	205	112.6	2.6	0.1	No
5	O	40	1.2	0	0	No
8	C	80	7.4	0.7	0	Yes, 80 sucklers cows
9	C	80	16.1	0.6	0.1	No
11	C	180	21.0	1.6	0	Yes 200 young cattle + 35 suckler cows
13	O	43	0.02	0	0	Yes, 16 beefs
Mean		95	21.1	0.8	0.04	X
Median		x	14.5	0.6	0	x

*grams of active ingredient

The purchase of critical antibiotic is nearly equal to 0 (Figure 7-4), whether for conventional and organic farms. Only three organic farms allowed us to collect their AM invoices. Those farms seem to purchase less antibiotics than the five conventional farms (respectively 10 g/DC, 1.2 g/DC and 0.02g/DC vs a median of 16.1 g/DC in average for the five conventional farms). In our study, there were no link between AM purchased and mortality rate in the eight surveyed farms. Aminoglycosides, penicilines and sulfamides are the 3 families with the highest AM purchase (in average) with respectively 3.4, 2.6 and 1.7 g/DC (fig 7).

Figure 7-4 Classes of antimicrobials purchased by the dairy farms in France

7.2.6 Discussion

Our results are limited for several reasons:

- The sample is very small and not representative of the French situation and the diversity of practices of health management. It's not relevant to compare and conclude on the level of consumption of antibiotics between conventional and organic farms
- Farmers selected by advisers were volunteers;
- Farmers were probably used to answer surveys and probably to talk about use of AM or health management; maybe they are farmers well informed about AM use and risks?

In our case study, because it's not relevant to compare and conclude on the level of consumption of antibiotics between conventional and organic farms, we will just compare with results of other projects.

The global AM purchase median in our study is about 14.5 g/DC with is consistent with the results obtained by Deschamps (2020) after a survey conducted among 15 dairy farmers in Normandy. The median AM purchase was about of 10,5g/DC for seven farms specialized in dairy production and 15,7g/DC for eight farms with another animal production on the farm. These results are lower than those collected by Godet (2015). They obtained an average AM purchase of 54,74g/DC for 44 farms surveyed.

Regarding the results obtained by antimicrobials classes (Figure 7-5), we observed that macrolids (21.7g/DC) was the most purchased class in Godet (2015), which is not the case in our study (0.7g/DC). Penicillin and aminoglycosides were the second and third most purchased classes of AM in dairy farms surveyed by Godet (2015) and they were the most purchased in our case study (2020).

Figure 7-5 Consumption of antibiotics per classes (Godet, 2014-2015)

Differences between those studies can be explained by the entry in force in 2016 of a new decree about the use of antibiotics, which introduced:

- a ban of the use of critical antibiotics for preventive purposes
- the obligation to carry out a clinical examination of the animal followed by an antibiogram before prescribing a critical antibiotic for curative or metaphylactic purposes (except in some situations).
- The obligation to have a preliminary complementary examination to identify the bacterial strain.

The decree implied a decrease in critical antibiotics sales in France: -86% (all species) for the Fluoroquinolones and 94.1% (all species) for the Cephalosporines since 2013 (ANSES, 2020). Moreover, technical actions conducted by all the dairy sector in the EcoAntibio plan resulted in a global decrease of AMU in bovine sector of 25.5% (ANSES, 2020).

7.3 AMU in French pig production

7.3.1 Methods

In France, as explained before, there is no national public database that would allow to analyse AMU according to the pig production systems (alternative and conventional one). Moreover, data from private companies are not:

- Systematic (many private companies don't calculate AMU of their farmers and have no specific indicator to monitor it);

- published (no private company has published its AMU, with the average and variability between farms, that would have allowed us to use these data);
- Comparable (companies who have this kind of indicator calculate AMU in different ways, so nothing is exploitable and comparable).

Thus, our last option to study AMU according to the production systems was to select a sample of farms (for which we were sure to know their production system and hopefully their AMU) and to survey them. To do that, we decided to work with 15-20 farms also involved in T2.3. That was the best option because we took advantage of contacting these farms for T2.3 to ask them more questions concerning AMU for T1.2. And, conversely, we thought that the knowledge of their AMU will be useful to interpret correctly their answers in T2.3. Besides these advantages, we were also aware of the limit of this method: such a small sample of farms is not representative of the French Pig production and it would not be relevant to perform any statistical tests on our results to compare the production systems, but it can give us some hints about the farming practices.

The recruitment of the farmers was carried out in early September 2020. Each of the five producers organizations surveyed in tasks 1.3 and 1.4 agreed to transmit the name and contact details of 4 farrow-to-finish farmers (2 under conventional system and 2 under antibiotic-free system). The interviews of the farmers were done between September and November 2020. At the end, 18 in 20 farmers were included in the study because 2 didn't respond.

The questionnaire allowed us to collect quantitative and qualitative data on:

- **General characteristics of the farms:** identification (anonymised), number of sows, age at weaning, castration or not;
- **Technical indicators:** indicator for AMU (presence or not; used or not), indicators about pig performances (got from the producers organisation : health expenditure (€/sow), mortality rate from weaning to slaughter (%), Average Daily Gain (standardized indicator from 8 to 115 kg, g/day), Feed Conversion Ratio (standardized indicator from 8 to 115 kg);
- **Reasons why antibiotics are used and percentage of treated animals** by age group;
- Description of the **evolution of AMU** over the past 3 years and in the next 3 years;
- **Interest in integrating an antibiotic-free system** in the next 3 years for farms currently in a conventional system // **Opinion on the antibiotic-free system** for farmers that are already involved in such a system.

7.3.2 Results

7.3.2.1 General characteristic of the farms

Table 7-9 shows the main characteristics of the farms included in the sample:

Table 7-9 general characteristics of the farms included in the sample

9 Conventional farms		9 Antibiotic-free farms		Average in the farrow-to finish French farms in 2016
Minimum	Maximum	Minimum	Maximum	

Number of sows	110	750	120	1500	230
Age at weaning (days)	21	28	21	28	
Health expenditure (€/sow) in 2019	97	220	39	131	110
Mortality rate (%) from 8 to 115 kg in 2019	1,7	7,8	3,8	11,3	5,3
ADG (g/day) from 8 to 115 kg in 2019	664	738	628	724	706
Feed Conversion Ratio from 8 to 115 kg in 2019	2,34	2,59	2,39	2,95	2,49

To include a farm in an antibiotic-free system, it appears here that:

- the number of sows is not an essential criteria because our sample includes small farms (< 150 sows) and big farms (>500 farms), like in the conventional samples.
- Age at weaning can be either 21 or 28 days.

Health expenditure seems to be higher in the conventional farms, surely because their more complicated sanitary situation doesn't allow them to decrease vaccines and antibiotic purchase.

The mortality rates in the antibiotic free systems indicates that some farms succeed in using few antibiotics without increasing mortality of pigs, which surely needs a very good health situation in these farms. Concerning ADG and FCR, some antibiotic-free farms have best results than conventional ones and the French average, which is encouraging to prove that good technical-economic performances are possible with a low AMU. This observation was already done in previous studies ([Collineau et al, 2018](#); [Collineau et al., 2017](#)).

A specific indicator to monitor antibiotic is still not common both in conventional and antibiotic-free systems. In conventional farms, only one farm gets this indicator from the veterinarian. The five other farms only know their "health expenditure" based on the costs of the medicines (vaccines, antibiotics, anti-inflammatory, vermifuge...). As purchase of antibiotics is not in a specific category, AMU monitoring is not accurate in these farms. In antibiotic-free farms, only 5/8 farms can correctly monitor there AMU thanks to an indicator calculated by the veterinarians. Farmers know that they have a good traceability of treated pigs (ear-tag, tattoo) to exclude them from the label. But they don't have an electronic book where they register all their veterinary treatments. This registration is performed manually so that it's hard to use the data.

Finally, it's here impossible to conclude if/how much AMU in conventional farms is higher than in antibiotic-free farms because farmers have either no indicator at all, or only health expenditure which is not specific of AMU, or an indicator that is private and not standardized at a national level

It will surely be easier in the future to get this information because

- → for farmers : electronic veterinary books are available with specific indicators (the GVET tool, as explained before)
- → for veterinarians : their sales of antibiotics should soon be declared at a national level (evolution of the regulation)

7.3.2.2 Type of treatment

Table 7-10 presents the results on the type of treatment, metaphylactic or preventive, in the sampled farms:

Table 7-10 Number of farms treating their pigs in a preventive or metaphylactic way

Type of treatment		9 Conventional farms	9 Antibiotic-free farms
Sows	Preventive	3	1
	Metaphylactic	1	0
Suckling piglets	Preventive	1	0
	Metaphylactic	1	1
Weaned piglets	Preventive	2	1
	Metaphylactic	4	0
Fattening pigs	Preventive	0	0
	Metaphylactic	2	0

In our sample, antibiotic-free farms use less preventive and metaphylactic treatments than conventional ones, which seems logical to get the label. Here again, this means that antibiotic-free farms need a good health situation to avoid these kinds of treatment. In the majority of these farms, only curative treatments are done but concern sometimes up to 30-35% of suckling piglets, which is a lot of course, but less than treating all the pigs of all the batches.

7.3.2.3 Evolution of AMU over the past 3 years and in the next 3 years

Evolution of AMU over the past 3 years was quite similar between the two systems: a stable AMU or a decrease was very common (Table 7-11), which is similar to the general trend in French pigs farms ([Anses, 2020](#)). Only two conventional farms declare an increase of AMU because of reproductive problems on sows.

Table 7-11 Number of farms declaring that their AMU will stagnate, decrease, increase

Evolution of AMU over the past 3 years, considering each age group in the farm	9 Conventional farms	9 Antibiotic-free farms
Stable	13	15
Decrease	21	20
Increase	2	0

Moreover, independently of the system, mostly all the farmers imagine that they can't decrease their AMU anymore in the next 3 years because it's already very low (Table 7-12). The only cases where farmers declared that AMU could still decrease are when health problems could be solved or when hygiene practices are not at the top level.

Table 7-12 Number of farms declaring if a decrease of AMU in the next 3 years is possible

Is a decrease of AMU possible in the next 3 years ?		9 Conventional farms	9 Antibiotic-free farms
Sows	Yes	3 (2 by tackling reproductive problems and 1 thanks to general hygiene practices that can still be improved)	2 (1 by stopping systematic treatments and 1 thanks to depopulation/repopulation)
	No	6 (5 have already low AMU and 1 because of reproductive problems)	6 (already low AMU)
Suckling piglets	Yes	1 thanks to general hygiene practices that still can be improved	3 (2 by tackling diarrhea and 1 thanks to depopulation/repopulation)
	No	8 have already low AMU	5 have already low AMU
Weaned piglets	Yes	3 (2 by stopping preventive treatments and 1 thanks to general hygiene practices that still can be improved)	1 thanks to depopulation/repopulation
	No	6 have already low AMU	7 have already low AMU
Fattening pigs	Yes	1	1
	No	8 have already low AMU	7 have already low AMU

7.3.2.4 Means of actions to decrease AMU in the next 3 years

There were interested farmers in all the proposed means of action (Table 7-13). The question with the most negative answers was about the help of automata/sensors to detect sick animals : a majority of farmers think it’s their job and that nothing will replace their eyes.

Table 7-13 number of farms with an interest in the cited means of action to decrease AMU in the next 3 years

	8 Conventional farms	9 Antibiotic-free farms
Setting up vaccines against diseases present in your farm	7	6
Putting in place biosecurity measures to reduce the spread of pathogens in your farm	6 (2 « no » because many things have already been improved to prevent African swine fever)	9
Trying new “alternative” products such as herbal medicine / yeast / algae / acid	6	8
Trying new feed strategies (formulation / plan)	7	5
Improving your livestock buildings (renovation, expansion, etc.)	3	9
Implementing automata/sensors that send alerts in the event of sick animals	3	3

Participating in trainings on health management and animal welfare	6 (1 « no » because soon retired)	8
--	-----------------------------------	---

A) For conventional farms, any interest in integrating an antibiotic-free system in the future ?

Generally, farmers are interested if this commitment is linked to a sufficient economic added-value. Some think that they could already integrate an antibiotic-free system but their producers organization has not this kind of label or has not proposed it to them because the market already fulfil the consumers demand.

B) For antibiotic-free farms, opinion on this system

The main motivation is the economic added-value. Some farmers regret that it's too low in comparison with the extra work and investments and other farmers consider it's enough.

7.4 AMU in French poultry production

7.4.1 Sector characteristics

7.4.1.1 Production trends for poultry meat in France

The French poultry production accounts for 1.8 Mt of carcass weight equivalent (cwe), with 1.2 Mt for broiler (67%), 0.3 Mt for turkey (18%), 0.2 Mt for duck (11%). The total poultry production remains stable during 2007-2020 (-0.2% per year), with substitutions across species with broiler production growing (+1.2% per year), while turkey (-2.8% per year) and duck (-2.0% per year) production are decreasing (Figure 7-6).

Figure 7-6. French production of poultry meat by species since 1990 (source : ITAVI based on SSP)

7.4.1.2 Broiler segmentation

The French poultry production is mainly made of conventional production (75%) and slow-growing indoor production (8 % labelled as “certifié conformité produit” or “CCP”). France has the highest free-range chicken production level in the EU with 15% sold under Label Rouge in 2018, which are either traditional free-range, or total freedom free range chickens as defined in EU commission regulation (EC) No 543/2008. According to ITAVI estimates, second and third producers of free range would be Italy (6% of national production) and the UK (7% of national production) both mostly on simple “free range” or organic specification (Leroy *et al.*, 2020).

ITAVI also estimates that France is the first producer of organic chicken in the EU with about 15 000 tons produced yearly, Italy and UK being second with roughly 11 000 tons each, however no reliable

data were found for EU organic production, which is often accounting for less than 2% of national production, except for Austria (>5%). In France, most Label Rouge chickens are also sold with a protected geographical of indication (PGI), but some, such as “Poulet de Bresse” are not sold under Label Rouge but hold a protected designation of origin (PDO).

This market segmentation doesn’t fully reflect the conventional broiler production which can be further spread between light chickens (1.4 kg LW) of breed JA 87 raised 34 days mainly for export to the middle east as whole carcasses (8 % of the production in 2020), standard broiler weight (1.6 – 2.0 kg) and heavy production (>2.0kg) (Figure 7-7).

Figure 7-7. Broiler slaughtering by production type in 2018 - Source: ITAVI based on SSP

7.4.1.3 Broiler performances

Every year, ITAVI conduces a survey among several poultry production’s organizations (PO) to collect data on technical and economical performances by species and production systems (ITAVI, 2020). Within this survey, average performances and production costs are calculated, allowing for annual national comparison (Table 7-14). In 2019, eight PO answered the survey for conventional broiler production systems, representing 23% of the French production (based on the number of heads slaughtered).

Table 7-14. Average production performances for conventional broiler production in France for 2019 – source: ITAVI

Variable	Unit	2019
Stocking density	head / m ²	22
Mortality	%	3.9
Feed conversion ratio	kg / kg	1.6
Slaughtering age	days	36

Liveweight at removal	kg	1.9
The average reported performances corresponds to the average of each respondent, weighted by production level		

These performances allow for the production cost calculation hereafter (Table 7-15).

Table 7-15. Production cost at farm gate for conventional broiler production (excluding labour) – source: ITAVI

Variable	Unit	2019
Fixed costs	€ / kg LW	0.11
Variable costs	€ / kg LW	0.08
Feed	€ / kg LW	0.48
Day-old chick	€ / kg LW	0.17
Production cost	€ / kg LW	0.84

Production costs for broilers at farm gate are 5% higher in France compared to the EU average, and much higher compared to exporting countries such as Poland (15%) (Van Horne, 2018). This lack of competitiveness from the French broiler industry has been shown to be the result of lower and less cost-effective processing units but also linked with a lower average live weight at slaughter, and thus a lower breast meat yield. Therefore, the trend in the French industry is moving towards growing heavier bird more suited for the cut market.

7.4.1.4 Broiler market

The average individual consumption of poultry meat in 2019 was 27.8 kg / cap, with 20.3 kg / cap for broiler. Since the beginning of the years 2000, imports of broiler are rising and account for 44% of the chicken meat consumption in 2019 (see Table 7-16 below).

Table 7-16. French poultry meat supply-demand table. Expressed in 1000 t-cwe – source: ITAVI based on SSP, customs

	Total poultry	Broiler	Turkey	Duck
Production	1 756	1 176	327	221
Export	467	346	72	36
Import	660	587	46	17
Consumption	1 864	1 332	294	209
Cons. per cap (kg/cap)	27,8	19,9	4,4	3,1
% import / consumption	35%	44%	16%	8%
% export / production	27%	29%	22%	16%

This situation is the result higher production costs compared to other EU countries or international exporters (Brazil, Thailand, Ukraine) as explained in the previous section. Industrial reports in France show that the main path for import is the food service sector which account for about 25% to 30% of total consumption of poultry meat. The processing of meat to produce preparations (nuggets, sausages, chicken ham...) is also an important source of import. In 2019, France main providers of chicken meat were Belgium (24%), Poland (20%), the Netherlands (18%) and Germany (15%).

7.4.2 Methods

The data collection for the French poultry case study was based on a previous study carried out in 2017-2018 on the control of avian colibacillosis in conventional broiler production (Puterflam et al., 2019). This study involved 80 volunteer farms in contract with four different POs, with a collection of structural data concerning the poultry farms, and breeding practices. For each farm, one flock was monitored from May 2017 to January 2019 (Figure 7-8), making it possible to record all the treatments administered and the sanitary events that occurred, as well as certain production performance indicators (stocking density, mortality rate, Slaughtering age).

Figure 7-8. Distribution of the flocks included in the study according to the date of the beginning of rearing period (80 farms sample)

Among these four POs, one of them has engaged all their farmers in an “antimicrobial free label market” (with an objective of 90% of flocks reared without antimicrobials on the totality of the production of the PO). Two of them have an intermediate status, with a part of the farmers under contract engaged in an "antimicrobial free label market" (restriction on fluoroquinolons and colistin uses mainly). The fourth is not engaged in “antimicrobial free label” market. The 80 farmers included in the study are distributed in the following way according to the typology of POs relating to the commitment to an “antimicrobial free label market” (Table 7-17).

Table 7-17. Distribution of the farms included in the study according to the typology of POs in relation to "AM free label market" (80 farms sample)

	PO totally engaged in "AM free label market"	POs engaged in a "AM free label market" for a part of its production	PO not engaged in "AM free label market"	All
Number of farms included in the survey	22	34	24	80

Within the framework of the ROADMAP project, 15 farmers were reinterviewed in connection with WP2’s qualitative survey. Additional data on AMU were collected: percentage of treated flocks over the last year (i.e 2020), average number of treatments per flock in 2020 and the trend of AMU evolution over the five past years (qualitative indication based on the farmer's declarations: upward, downward, or stable trend).

Additional structural data were also collected: total surface area of poultry houses of the farm, and if the poultry production is the main source of incomes for farmer. The average production performances were requested for 2020: Stocking density, Mortality rate, Feed conversion ratio, Slaughtering age and liveweight at removal. We can notice that among the 15 farmers interviewed a second time, 9 of them are in a “antimicrobial free label”, and 6 not.

7.4.3 Results

7.4.3.1 Structural data of poultry farms

The average number of poultry houses per farm is 1.65 considering the total sample of 80 farms (Table 7-18). However, the range between the minimum and maximum is very large (from 1 to 5 poultry houses per farm). This average is slightly lower than the national average of 1.81 poultry houses per farm, estimated by ITAVI (Hercule, 2020).

There are some disparities (but not significant) according to the typology of POs. Thus, the POs engaged in an “antimicrobial free label market” for a part of their production, are close to the national average with 1.82 poultry houses per farm. While the two other types of POs have a lower average: 1.50 poultry houses per farm for PO not engaged in a “antimicrobial free label market”, and 1.55 poultry houses per farm concerning the PO totally engaged in an “antimicrobial free label market”.

Table 7-18. Farms size according to the typology of POs in relation to "antimicrobial free label market" (80 farms sample)

		PO totally engaged in "AM free label market"	POs engaged in a "AM free label market" for a part of her production	PO not engaged in "AM free label market"	All
Number of poultry houses in the farm	Average	1.55	1.82	1.50	1.65
	min	1	1	1	1
	max	4	5	5	5

For the 15 farms, interviewed in connection with WP2’s qualitative survey, the average number of poultry houses per farm amount to 2.11 for farms in an “antimicrobial free label”, and 2.33 for conventional farms. These averages are slightly upper than the national average of 1.81 poultry houses per farm, estimated by ITAVI (Hercule, 2020). Poultry production is the main incomes source for 56% of farmer in an “antimicrobial free label”, and 67% of conventional farms (Table 7-19).

Table 7-19. Size of farms according to their belonging to an “antimicrobial free label” (15 farms sample).

	Farms in a "AM free label"	Conventional farms
Number of farms	9	6
main source of income	56%	67%
Number of poultry houses in the farm	2.11	2.33

The average surface area of the poultry houses in which flocks were monitored for the purposes of the avian colibacillosis survey is 1 223 m² (Table 7-20). This is slightly upper than the national average of 1 071 m², but consistent considering variability (Hercule. 2020). There is there is little difference according to the typology of POs, but not significant.

Table 7-20. Surface Area of poultry houses in which flocks were monitored for the purposes of the avian colibacillosis survey (80 farms sample)

		PO totally engaged in "AM free label market"	POs engaged in a "AM free label market" for a part of her production	PO not engaged in "AM free label market"	All
Surface area of the monitored poultry house (m²)	Average	1 299	1 194	1 194	1 223
	min	970	400	960	400
	max	1 818	1 800	1 806	1 818

For the 15 farms sample, the total surface area of the poultry houses is in average 3 027 m², and 2 933 m² (Table 7-21). This is largely upper than the national average of 1 942 m² (Hercule. 2020). There is no difference between the two types of farms. As well, the average surface area per poultry house is 1 349 m² for farms in an “antimicrobial free label” and closely the same for conventional farms (i.e., 1 256 m²).

Table 7-21. Surface Area of poultry houses (15 farms sample)

	Farms in a "AM free label"	Conventional farms
Average total surface area of poultry farms (m²)	3 028	2 933
Average surface area per poultry houses in the farms (m²)	1 349	1 256

7.4.3.2 Production performances of the poultry farms

The average stocking density of the 80 flocks monitoring (22 head / m²) (Table 7-22) is consistent with the one for conventional broiler production in France for 2019 (Table 7-14), and varies between POs. The average slaughtering age is slightly higher (42 d vs 36 d) than national reference table, as well as the mortality (4.36% vs 3.9%). This survey focuses on medium and heavy broiler production, which explain these data. 98% of monitored flocks are “Ross 308” broilers (“Cobb” broilers for only 2 flocks). The flocks of farmers under contract with PO **not** engaged in an "AM free label market" seem to have slightly higher mortality (4.62%), but also higher slaughtering age (45 d) which could explain that. The flocks of farmers under contract with PO totally engaged in an "AM free label market" have the lower average mortality (4.21%), but also the lower slaughtering age (36 d). We notice that a significant difference is observed between POs on slaughtering ages (p<0.01), but this is not the case for mortality.

Table 7-22. Average production performances of flocks were monitored for the purposes of the avian colibacillosis survey (80 farms sample)

	PO totally engaged in "AM free label market"	POs engaged in a "AM free label market for a part of his production"	PO not engaged in "AM free label market"	All
number of farms	22	34	24	80
stocking density (head / m ²)	23	22	22	22
Mortality (%)	4.21%	4.28%	4.62%	4.36%
Slaughtering age (days)	36	43	45	42

Concerning the 15 farms sample, they all raise “Ross” broilers. The majority of farms is concerning by heavy broiler production: 78% of farms in an “antimicrobial free label” (i.e., 7 farms out of 9), 100% of conventional farms (i.e. 6 farms). There are only two farms involved in medium broiler production among farms in an “antimicrobial free label” (Table 7-23).

Table 7-23. Distribution of 15 farms sample according to type of production.

	Farms in a "AM free label"	Conventional farms
number of farms	9	6
heavy broiler production	78%	100%
medium broiler production	22%	

Considering heavy broiler production only, the average stocking density is 21 head / m² for farms in an “AM free label”, and 20 heads / m² for conventional farms (Table 7-24), that is slightly lower than the one for conventional broiler production in France for 2019 (Table 7-14).

The average slaughtering age is upper (40 d for farms in an “AM free label”, and 42 d for conventional farms, vs 36 d for conventional broiler production in France). In fact, females and males are slaughtered at two different ages. For farms in an “AM free label”, the average slaughtering age for females is 38 days, and 42 days for males. For conventional farms, the average slaughtering age for females is 36 days, and 46 days for males.

The average liveweight at removal is 2.5 kg for farms in an “AM free label” (1.9 for females and 3.0 for males), and 2.6 kg for conventional farm (1.9 for females and 3.4 for males). The slight difference between the two types of farms is therefore explained by an upper slaughtering age of the males for conventional farms, which involves an upper average liveweight at removal. Mortality reaches 4.14 % for farms in an "AM free label", and 3.45 % form conventional farms.

Table 7-24. Average production performances of the heavy broiler production into the 15 farms sample

	Farms in an "AM free label"	Conventional farms
Stocking density at the beginning of the flock (head / m²)	21	20
Mortality (%)	4.14	3.45
Feed conversion ratio	1.67	1.69
Average slaughtering age (days)	40	42
Liveweight at removal (kg)	2.5	2.6

7.4.3.3 Ventilation management and bedding practices

Considering the total 80 farms sample, a dynamic ventilation system allows to regulate the ambient air parameters (temperature, humidity, oxygen supply etc.) in the majority of poultry houses (76% of cases) (Table 7-25). That is to say, fans artificially extract ambient air to create negative pressure into the poultry houses. Automatic systems based on several sensors (temperature, moisture, eventually carbon dioxide) allow to control air intake flap, extractor fans and heater. This observation is particularly true for POs totally or partially engaged in a "AM free label market” (respectively 82% and 79% of the poultry houses with dynamic ventilation system.

The other poultry houses have a static ventilation system. In this case, the heat difference between inside and outside is responsible for the generation of airflows, which allows ambient air renewal. Dynamic ventilation system is known to facilitate breeding management allowing to assure animal comfort with a better precision, and as a result of better production performances (Chevalier et al. 2015). In a review, Chevalier et al. (2015) estimate that 70% of production performances are ensured by a good management of the “ventilation/heating” couple. In 2011, the annual technical-economic survey of Chambers of Agriculture, estimates that around 70% of the poultry houses park is equipped with dynamic ventilation system.

Chevalier et al. (2015), also precise that recent equipment as heat exchanger-collector system allows to optimize energy consumption necessary to reach ideal temperature, and to respect maximum rates of moisture and carbon dioxide concentration. We observe that only 24% of poultry houses included in this survey are fitted with this type of equipment, with few differences according to the types of POs. According to Dezat et al (2015), while the interest of this type of equipment on energy savings is certain, the impact on production performances remains to be demonstrated. This uncertainty could explain why such equipment are currently not widely used.

Table 7-25. Ambient air parameters regulation system of poultry houses in which flocks were monitored for the purposes of the avian colibacillosis survey (80 farms sample)

	PO totally engaged in "AM free label market"	POs engaged in a "AM free label market” for a part of her production	PO not engaged in "AM free label market"	All
--	--	--	--	-----

Number of farms		22	34	24	80
Type of ventilation system	dynamic	82%	79%	67%	76%
	static	18%	21%	33%	24%
Number of poultry house equipped of a heat exchanger-collector system		14%	38%	25%	28%

The majority of the poultry houses have a clay floor (76%), the others have a concrete or asphalt floor (Table 7-26). Dezat et al. (2013) precise that it is a historical feature of the French poultry houses park. Thus in 2011, only 8% of French poultry houses for broilers and turkey production had a concrete floor. However, Nicolas (2019) indicates a trend towards the concreting of floors for the majority of constructions and renovated poultry houses.

The motivations of livestock farmers to use this type of floor are mainly the prevention of pododermatitis, as well as in the improvement of working conditions and the control of building hygiene (Nicolas. 2019). Nevertheless, the investment may slow down some farmers, especially as uncertainties persist about good practices in terms of implementation, management and technical and economic benefits (Dezat et al. 2013).

Finally, the type of litter used is mainly straw (76% of cases). Woodchips are the second most used type of litter material, but there is also a diversification of materials (sawdust, buckwheat hulls...). Dezat (2020) emphasizes that litter is a key factor in the success of poultry production. Litter management practices have evolved considerably in recent years, in particular with a view to better prevention of pododermatitis. Indeed, this expense item is constantly increasing.

Although the use of shavings seems technically more advantageous, this material remains quite expensive. Many farmers therefore prefer to use straw, which remains an easily available and affordable material. However, different strategies seem to be adapted between the different typologies of POs. Thus, the PO totally engaged in an "AM free label market" seems to encourage the use of woodchips in comparison to the other POs. The POs engaged in an "AM free label market" for a part of their production seems to adopt another strategy with an important percentage of farmer who use other litter material as buckwheat hulls.

Table 7-26. Floor and bedding litter of poultry houses in which flocks were monitored for the purposes of the avian colibacillosis survey (80 farms sample)

		PO totally engaged in "AM free label market"	POs engaged in a "AM free label market" for a part of her production	PO not engaged in "AM free label market"	All
number of farms		22	34	24	80
type of floor	concrete or asphalt floor	18%	32%	17%	24%
	clay floor	82%	68%	83 %	76%
bedding litter material	straw	77%	68%	88%	76%
	woodchips	23%	9%	8%	13%
	other		23%	4%	11%

Concerning the 15 farms sample, a dynamic ventilation system is present in a majority of conventional farms (83%), a little bit less for farms in an “AM free label” (Table 7-27). However, a higher percentage of farms in an “AM free label” have a poultry house with concrete or asphalt floor (33%), in comparison with conventional farms (17%). The prevention of pododermatitis is often an important indicator integrated in the "AM free label” with an indexation on the economic results. Finally, straw is the main bedding litter material used by the two types of farms.

Table 7-27. Floor and bedding litter of poultry houses (15 farm sample)

		Farms in an "AM free label"	Conventional farms
number of farms		9	6
type of ventilation system	dynamic	56%	83%
	static	33%	17%
type of floor	concrete or asphalt floor	33%	17%
	clay floor	56%	83%
bedding litter material	straw	89%	83%
	woodchips	11%	
	other		17%

7.4.3.4 AMU according to different typologies of POs and farms

55% of monitored flocks received at least one antimicrobial treatment (Table 7-28). Although percentage of treated flocks with at least one antimicrobial treatment seem higher (67%), there is no significant differences between POs ($p > 0.1$), which can be possibly explained by the small sample size. It can also be pointed out that no significant influence on AMU could be found concerning the surface area of poultry houses, the number of poultry houses per in the farm, the type of ventilation system, the presence of heat exchanger-collector system, the type of floor, or the type of bedding litter materiel. However, we notice that treated flocks have a significantly higher mortality (5.05%) than untreated flocks (3.67%) ($p < 0.01$). This result is consistent with a previous survey realized in 2012 (Chauvin, 2012). Nevertheless, there is no significant relationship with slaughtering age or stocking density.

The average number of treatment per flocks (calculated for the whole sample including not treated flocks) is 0.7, and we can observe no differences between POs. For comparison purposes, in 2012, Anses showed that the percentage of treated broiler flocks with at least one antimicrobial treatment reached 51%, but average number of treatment per flock (calculated for the whole sample including not treated flocks) is higher than our results (i.e. 0.9) (Chauvin, 2012).

Table 7-28. AMU of monitored flocks for the purposes of the avian colibacillosis survey (80 farms sample)

	PO totally engaged in "AM free label market"	POs engaged in a "AM free label market for a part of his production"	PO not engaged in "AM free label market"	All
percentage of treated flocks with at least one antimicrobial treatment	55%	47%	67%	55%

average number of treatments per flock (calculated for the all sample including note treated flocks)	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.7
--	-----	-----	-----	-----

Regarding the sampled 15 farms, results show that farms in an “AM free label” had treated 37% of their flock the last year (2020) (from 0% to 67%), vs 45% for conventional farms (from 10% to 100%) (Table 7-29). The average number of treatments per flock (calculated only for treated flocks) amounted to 1.0 for farms in "AM free label" vs 1.2 for conventional farms.

Table 7-29. AMU of 15 farms sample in the last past years (2020)

	Farms in an "AM free label"		Conventional farms
percentage treated flock with at least one antimicrobial treatment	average	37%	45%
	min	0%	10%
	max	67%	100%
number of treatments per flock (calculated only for treated flocks)	average	1.0	1.2
	min	1	1
	max	1	2

However, the majority of farmers of the two types of farms declare a downward trend for their AMU over the last five years: 71% of farms in an “AM label” and 83 % for conventional farms. Respectively 14% and 17% of farmers declare a stable trend for their AMU, 14% of farmers in an “AM free label” declare an upward trend of their AMU (Table 7-30).

Table 7-30. trend of AMU for the 15 farms sample

	Farms in an "AM free label"	Conventional farms
downward trend	71%	83%
stable trend	14%	17%
upward trend	14%	

7.4.3.5 Characteristics of antimicrobial treatment

Avian colibacillosis represent the principal reason of antimicrobial treatment in this survey (**Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**). As the study of Gery-Choquet et al. (2019) remind us, avian colibacillosis is a major disease in broiler production. It is the main reason of antimicrobial treatment, which is currently the most widely used means of control for curative purposes (Anses, 2018). Then, *enterococcus* lameness and enteritis appear to be affecting pathologies, often causes of treatment. There are also less specific reasons such as an abnormally high mortality, non-specific digestive disorders, zoo-technical problems (e.g. related to feeding transitions).

Figure 7-9. Frequency of antimicrobial treatment reason

The Figure 7-10 shows that majority of antimicrobial treatment are administered during the first week of rearing period. This observation is consistent with unpublished data from M. Paul (see ROADMAP DELIVERABLE D6.2 “Impact assessment case studies selected and documented”, § 4. “Long ex-ante impact assessment case-studies”, 4.3 France). She precise that in broiler chickens, two critical age periods have been identified regarding antimicrobial treatments: (i) 0-5 days (early mortality), (ii) 20-30 days (digestive and locomotor problems).

Figure 7-10. Distribution of the age of flock at the start of antimicrobial treatment

7.4.4 Discussion: Comparison of poultry production systems in France

We can sum up the comparison between POs and farms engaged or not in an “AM free label” with the

Table 7-31 below. Regardless of the PO or type of farm, we observe similar average farm ‘size (number of poultry houses per farms or, average surface area per poultry houses), high level of poultry houses with a dynamic ventilation system, and slightly high with concrete floor. ITAVI’s survey on the French poultry houses area (Hercule, 2020) shows a relative stability of the stock of poultry buildings with few constructions of new houses and few destructions as well (less than 2% yearly).

Although, the renovations of old poultry houses were important from 2009 and 2018 mainly for standard and certified poultry production, the broiler houses are structurally old in France, which could influence the management of welfare and animal health and thus the use of antibiotics. Our results from the 80 flocks don’t show a significant impact of the floor type on AMU. But interviews with farmers in

the framework of WP2, suggest that the level of labour needed to maintain a good quality of litter (e.g.) can vary greatly amongst different farms according to the poultry building configuration (concrete floor / clay floor) or the farmer investment capacity (manual bedding / straw blower). We will develop more widely this item in the WP2 report.

Within the 80 flocks, stocking density and slaughtering age don't differ according to the engagement in an "AM free label" but rather according to the production system (medium or heavy broiler production). The poultry production with an "AM free label" is basically the same production than standard poultry production but with extra-specifications to be reached for the farmers in terms of AMU or welfare indicator such as food pad dermatitis. This last point also explains the difference about bedding litter material used by farmer in an "AM free label", but that does not appear to have a strong influence on AMU.

If mortality rate does not appear different (at least statistically, considering the small sample size) according to the engagement into an "AM free label", we can observe a positive link with AMU, that is consistent with a previous study (Chauvin, 2012). As we mentioned above, avian colibacillosis is the principal reason for antimicrobial treatment in this survey. This disease is caused by *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) bacteria, a common host in the digestive tract of poultry.

Colibacillosis is a multifactorial disease that can be triggered by unfavourable husbandry factors, a state of immunosuppression in poultry or a particular virulence of *E. coli* strains (Guabiraba et al, 2015). The *E. coli* bacterium has a wide variety of strains, most of which are non-pathogenic. However, strains known as APEC (Avian Pathogenic *E. coli*) can be responsible for clinical manifestations in poultry farms, leading to high mortality. It is therefore not surprising to observe a link between AMU and mortality here.

However, most farmers feel a global downward trend for their AMU which is consistent with the results of the two Ecoantibio successive plans. Our survey mainly highlights a decrease in the number of treatments per flock (i.e comparison with a previous study, Chauvin, 2012). But we don't observe a significant difference between POs according to their involvement in "AM free label".

The focus on the 15 farms allows to observe more homogeneity between farmers involved in an "AM free label" regarding the average percentage treated flock. Moreover, the lower number of treatments per treated flock for farmers in an "AM free label" suggest a later use (when the animals are older) of antimicrobial treatments, that could be consistent with the trend of slightly higher mortality (although no significant) observed above in the POs **not** engaged in "AM free label".

The in-depth analysis of the interviews carried out within the framework of WP2 will allow for a better understanding of the differences in farm practices, farmers insights and perception of AMU and AMR that could explain these results.

Table 7-31. Sum up of principal structural data and production performances of poultry farms, as well as principal characteristics of poultry houses of the two samples (80 farms and 15 farms), according to the engagement or not in an "AM free label"

		"AM free label"			conventional farms		National Average ITAVI
		<i>PO totally engaged (80 farms sample)</i>	<i>POs partially engaged (80 farms sample)</i>	<i>Farms in a "AM free label" (15 farms sample)</i>	<i>PO not engaged (80 farms sample)</i>	<i>Conventional farms (15 farms sample)</i>	
Average number of poultry houses in the farm		1.55	1.82	2.11	1.50	2.33	1.81
average surface area per poultry houses (m ²)		1 299	1 194	1 349	1 194	1 256	1073
type of ventilation system	dynamic	82%	79%	56%	67%	83%	-
	static	18%	21%	33%	33%	17%	-
type of floor	concrete or asphalt floor	18%	32%	33%	17%	17%	-
	clay floor	82%	68%	56%	83 %	83%	-
bedding litter material	straw	77%	68%	89%	88%	83%	-
	woodchips	23%	9%	11%	8%	-	-
	other	-	23%	-	4%	17%	-
stocking density (head / m ²)		23	22	21	22	20	22 (20.4-22.9)
Slaughtering age (days)		36	43	40	45	42	36 (33.3 – 38.3)
Mortality (%)		4.21	4.28	4.14	4.62	3.45	3.9 (2.5 – 7.9)

8 Case study analysis: pig production in Italy

8.1 Introduction

In a franchising-like association with the farmer, the most common production system in the Italian pork and poultry sectors, the integrated company provides most of the inputs and uptakes the related costs, including those related to veterinary medical products. The integrated company veterinarian manages the health status of the farm and the choices related to the medication. The integrated company can also produce medicated feed, having an even stronger influence in the AMU.

In such integrated system, the farmer provides labour, the buildings and energy/electricity, having very low decision power over the AMU and other production practices. Together with the institutional action, the request of retailers for pork and poultry meat produced with specific claims or labels (e.g. welfare, antibiotic free, organic), coexist in the process of reduction of the AMU in the food chain. Farms included on this process are usually associated to large cooperative groups or part of the integrated groups that can guarantee to the retailers a constant provision of the meat.

Sales of antimicrobials for animals in Italy remain high compared to most other European Union Member States according to the European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption (ESVAC) project, despite ESVAC data showing a 42% reduction during the period 2010-2018. In this trend a significant contribution was related to the reduction of the use of quinolones and fluoroquinolones, polimixins and macrolides. However, the 2018 value is still the second most relevant in Europe with the majority of sales to be attributed to Tetracyclines (72,6 mg/PCU) and Penicillines (68.7 mg/PCU).

The national One Health action plan (NAP) on AMR was adopted in November 2017 in Italy. However, several of the measures proposed in the NAP are still voluntary. A compulsory Electronic Veterinary Prescription (e-prescription) system was adopted from 2019 and serves as the main AMU monitoring system for the country's authorities. This system provides data that are used by the authorities to focus official controls on high antibiotic-using farms or high prescribing veterinarians.

ClassyFarm, a voluntary risk assessment tool is also being implemented in the country with the aim of categorizing the risk of farms in the field of veterinary public health. It allows the detection, collection and processing of data relating to the following assessment areas: biosecurity; animal welfare; health and production parameters; animal feed; consumption of antimicrobial drugs and injuries found at the slaughterhouse. Some of its modules are becoming progressively mandatory for farms in specific sectors. In addition, various prudent use guidelines (including species-specific ones) have been developed nationally.

The private and public sector initiatives taken in recent years by the poultry industry and regional pilot projects involving pig farms (especially in the Emilia-Romagna region) led to considerable reductions in the use of antimicrobials. Several actions and elements can be pointed as responsible for such success: improved biosecurity, farm advisory services, focus on infection prevention and control, free diagnostic, and laboratory tests to farmers. In addition, various information measures, awareness campaigns and training activities have been undertaken, involving veterinarians, farmers, and other stakeholders. From the other side, one of the main problems still faced in the country concerns the fact that for some farmers it might still be cheaper to continue using antimicrobials rather than investing in improvements in farm infrastructure or husbandry systems.

8.2 AMU in Italian Pig production

In the Italian pig sector, the main constrain that limit the diffusion of harmonized good practices is the high fragmentation of the production system. Around the 34-40% of the production is integrated, while the remaining 60-70% is divided in mid or small farms. Since 2020 the risk assessment tool ClassyFarm is mandatory in the pig sector for all farms and the assessment is in charge to the veterinary of the farm. Moreover, periodically the Local Health Unit-LHU veterinary (public body) verifies the score by an audit.

Another action that affected the use of antibiotic in the pig sector was the limitation in the use of colistin, especially with the prohibition of its use associated with other antibiotics. This fact strongly affected the use of colistin on weaned pigs, which today is almost zero. As consequence the use of therapeutic doses of ZnO increased, replacing colistin.

In pigs, especially at weaning, the first way of administration of antibiotic is orally, while in suckling pigs, sows and fattening pigs (apart the first week post housing from site 2 to site 3), the injection is the first way of administration. Anyway, the weaning phase is the one where most of the antimicrobials are used in pig production, so specific actions on this production phase could significantly affect the AMU on the Italian pig sector.

Concerning vaccination, apart the obligatory ones, the adoption of specific vaccination plans targeted for each farm gain consensus in the last year. The Experimental Zooprophyllactic Institute (IZS), coordinates a project to produce vaccines targeted to specific pathogen strains of each farm. Moreover, for colibacillosis disease, the diffusion of oral vaccination increases the resistance of the pigs against *E. coli* F4 and F18.

Other preventive strategies based on the improvement of the external biosecurity measures has been recently adopted due to the COVID-19 outbreak as well as the risk of diffusion of African Swine Fever (ASF) that already reach some EU countries. This increased biosecurity could have a positive effect on the general health status of the farm (to be demonstrated in the next year). Together with the aforementioned strategies, the adoption of feeding strategy based on the low crude protein content and the use of feed additives like acidifiers, crystalline amino acids and probiotic, concurs in increase the natural resistance of the pigs against pathogens.

8.2.1 First pig case study, Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome (PRRS)

8.2.1.1 Background

The case study was based on data collected from farm devoted the production of the Italian heavy pig and selected diverge ted for the occurrence of the Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome (PRRS), positive or negative. The production sites considered in this case study are not certified to be free from the PRRS, and all the animals have been vaccinated. Thus we can find farms PRRS negative and positive.

There are farms considered PRRS negative (PRRS-) where the antibody detected in the blood are very low and originated from the vaccination as well as no clinical illnesses occurred in these farms since long time. From the other hand there are PRRS positive (PRRS+) farms where the disease is recurrent,

and the level of antibody in blood is quite high. This categorization can be adopted for the site 1 (gestation-farrowing unit) and site 2 (weaning unit), while in the site 3 (fattening unit), frequently the pigs become seropositive for the PRRS. The data derived from full integrated production systems.

8.2.1.2 Methods

The data collected for this case study, derived from a database that is organized to provide the yearly antibiotic consumption from each production system (PRRS+ and PRRS-) and for production site (weaning unit and fattening unit). The farms are full integrated systems and organized in a multi-site production system where the pigs of the same site 1 are reared in predetermined sites 2 and site 3 year by year, to avoid cross contamination between the production systems. This study quantifies the AB use in Italian weaning (W) and fattening (F) conventional industrial units differentiated for the serological status (seronegative (-) or seropositive (+)) against the Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome (PRRS). Collected data cover the 2017-2020 period and AB use is expressed as mg of active compounds (AC) per kg of produced body weight (BW). The ACs were categorised following the EU/EMA scale: B: Restrict; C: Caution; D: Prudence. So, for the case study pigs derived from two sites 1, it was considered one PRRS+ and one PRRS-. The number of pigs and the average BW (kg) produced per production phase are: W/PRRS-: 115.970/2,916,458; W/PRRS+: 65.331/1,593,631; F/PRRS-: 108.248/15,037,139; F/PRRS+: 54.410/7,440,633.

8.2.1.3 Results and conclusions

The use of class B was not affected by the production phase and PRRS status. Conversely, for class C the interaction was observed ($P=0.02$). W/PRRS+ and F/PRRS+ showed the higher AB use (with $P<0.0001$ and $P<0.01$, respectively). Thus, the PRRS- system resulted less treated than the PRRS+ (27 vs 95 mg/kg), which was expected. For class D the interaction tended to be significant ($P=0.06$), with PRRS- showing a lower AB use than PRRS+ (110 vs 425; $P=0.047$) and AB being more used in W than in F (466 vs 69mg/kg; $P=0.02$). The variation in the relative quantity of produced BW treated with each AB class was also analysed. At weaning, the % of BW treated with class B decreased from 9% PRRS+ and 14% PRRS- (2017) to 1% PRRS+ and 10% PRRS- (2020). Along the same period, PRRS+ increased the percentage of BW treated with class C (45% vs 56%), while PRRS- also decreased class C (42% vs 39%) but increased the BW percentage treated with class D (44% vs 51%). At fattening, the use of class B decreased from 3% PRRS+ and 7% PRRS- in 2017, to zero in 2020. In 2017 the most represented AB of the class C, expressed as relative quantities of treated weaning pig weight in the PRRS+ system were: 40% Tilmicosin, 32% Florfenicol and 18% Gentamicin while in PRRS- were: 36% Lincomycin, 21% Florfenicol and 10% Gentamicin. In 2020 for the class C, the relative quantities of treated weaning pig weight in the PRRS+ system were: 24% Lincomycin, 23% Florfenicol, 19% Tiamulin 17% Gentamicin while in PRRS- were 31% Lincomycin and 21% Clavulanic acid. For the class D both in PRRS+ and PRRS- the most used AC expressed as relative quantities of treated weaning pig weight was Amoxicillin (83% and 74%, respectively in the 2017 / 79% and 89%, respectively in the 2020). In conclusion, the PRRS directly affected the use of AB during the overall growing phase of pigs with highest impacts on the weaning phase. In the last 4 years, the total use of the class B was strongly reduced in the examined farms as well as the AC used changes from 2017 to 2020.

8.2.2 Second case study, AB-free vs conventional production systems

8.2.2.1 Background

The data for the case study were collected from full integrated production systems. The selected production sites are devoted to produce pigs slaughtered at 135kg. The production system is organized in a multi-site production system where the pigs of the site 1 are reared in predetermined site 2 and site 3 year by year, to avoid cross contamination between the production systems. In this case study it was compared pigs reared in conventional farming system (CONV) with pigs reared in an antibiotic free system (AB-free), where the AB use is forbidden during the last 4 months before slaughter. In this production system, pigs were reared in the same way in site 1 and site 2. After that, half of the pigs are reared in fattening units dedicated to the AB free production system and half pigs are reared in fattening units dedicated to the conventional production.

8.2.2.2 Methods

The data collected for this case study comes from a private company database that is organized to provide the yearly antibiotic consumption from each production system. This study quantifies the AB use in fattening units differentiated for the commercial production system AB-free versus conventional farms. Collected data cover the 2017-2019 period and AB use is expressed as mg of active compounds (AC) per kg of produced body weight (BW). The ACs were categorised following the EU/EMA scale: B: Restrict; C: Caution; D: Prudence. The number of pigs and the average BW (kg) produced per production system are: AB-free: 45.093/ 5.330.135; CONV: 106.101/ 11.612.231 respectively.

8.2.2.3 Results and conclusions

The total AB consumption was lower for the AB-free production system, than the CONV system (18.9 vs 50.7; $P < 0.05$). The use of class B, C and D was not affected by the production system when considered together. The mg of class B are much lower than the mg of class C and D (0.06, 10.49, 24.25, respectively). Considering together the class C and the class D, the production system affected the AB use ($P < 0.05$). Thus, the AB-free system resulted less treated than the CONV (18.9 vs 50.6 mg/kg). The variation in the relative quantity of produced BW treated with each AB class was also analysed.

In 2017 the most represented AB of the class C, expressed as relative quantities of treated weaning pig weight in the AB-free production system were: 73% Apramycin, 27% Lincomycin, while in CONV were: 67% Tylosin, 10% Apramycin. While, in 2019 the most represented AB of the class C, expressed as relative quantities of treated weaning pig weight in the AB-free production system were: 51% Lincomycin, 30% Florfenicol, 19% Clavulanic acid, while in CONV were: 27% Florfenicol, 27% Lincomycin and 19 Tiamulin. For the class D in the 2017, in both AB-free and CONV production systems the most used AC expressed as relative quantities of treated weaning pig weight was Doxycycline (69% and 61%, respectively). While in 2019 for the class D in AB-free system the most used AC expressed as relative quantities of treated weaning pig weight was: 97% Amoxicillin and for CONV were: 59% Amoxicillin and 41% Doxycycline. In conclusion, in the studied production systems, the class B was less used, and the antibiotic belonging to the class D was the most used in terms of mg. The AB-free production system strongly reduce the use of AB as well as the AC used.

9 Case study analysis: poultry production in Italy

9.1 Background

In 2018 the estimated Population Correction Units (PCU) for poultry in Italy corresponded to 18.7% of the 3.819 Italian PCU of all food-producing animals. At National Level, a first Plan for the responsible use of veterinary medicines and the fighting against antimicrobial resistance in poultry was adopted in 2015 for the period 2015-16, which was followed by the 2017 NAP. In the poultry sector, in Italy, thanks to the high level of integration of poultry companies, a fast decrease on the use of antimicrobials was observed with a percentage of antibiotic free production raising above the 30 % of total production. Antimicrobials are used to treat infections associated to respiratory tract, foot pad lesions and gastro-enteritis. Bacterial infections, in particular respiratory ones, are often secondary infections after a primary viral infection.

Based on this knowledge the vaccination program is one of the most preventive and effective measures in health management. In Italy, broilers are currently vaccinated for: Marek Disease, Infectious Bronchitis, Newcastle disease, Gumboro disease, infectious anemia, aviary encephalomyelitis, and viral arthritis and coccidiosis.

Along with vaccination other preventive measures are applied at different steps of production and have significantly contributed to the reduction of antimicrobial use namely: 1) improved biosecurity, 2) the use of feed additives such as probiotics, prebiotics and organic acids which stimulate the immune system reinforcing the health status of animals and preventing the emergence of bacterial diseases, 3) specific attention to quality of feed and water, as well as quality of chicks and breeders.

Despite all the measures applied, there are important constraints that prevent a further reduction on the use of antimicrobials: 1) the implementation of biosecurity is limited in old buildings in which windows are not present, essential for the welfare of animals,; 2) antimicrobial treatments are applied in feed or water (increasing potential environmental contamination) and always as metaphylactic approach. From 20k to 40k animals are stocked in the same holding: When specific symptoms are observed by farm veterinarians, the whole flock is treated. Description of case studies – Ab-free vs conventional production systems

Both conventional and antibiotic free production might produce broilers without the use of antimicrobials. In general, conventional intensive systems are related to older buildings with no windows (not adhering with recent welfare recommendations), rearing both female and males and sometimes lacking precision farming tools such as forced ventilation and automatic monitoring of CO₂. Antibiotic free productions are related to more recent or restructured buildings with very high biosecurity implementation, forced ventilation and windows. Females, with a shorter production cycle, are preferentially reared with a generally lower stocking density. In case of bacterial diseased animals, the whole flock is treated with antibiotics and the label antibiotic-free is removed from the produced meat. The frequency of antibiotic treatments is generally one over ten-fifteen or more cycles of production which means once every two or three years or more.

9.2 Methods

Based on the private database of the integrated poultry company and the interviews to farmers and veterinarians, cumulative data of the last five years on medical and production costs as well as on production performances were collected on 34 conventional and 96 antibiotic-free farms. Costs of total medical treatments, vaccines, pharmaceutical, feed additives and disinfection were collected. For production performances, the total production cost per kg of live animal (cumulative cost of chicks, feed, contract farming and medication) was available along with number of animals, feed conversion ratio as well as mortality for production performances.

9.3 Results

In Table 9-1 and

Table 9-2 the medication costs per kg of live animal are reported for conventional and AB free farms respectively. The total cost for medication was similar in conventional and AB free farms in the period 2016-2020, although in AB free farms there was a higher cost for vaccination and feed additives and a lower cost for pharmaceuticals (including antibiotics) suggesting a more intensive use of preventive measures and a lower use of pharmaceuticals in comparison to conventional farms. Looking at the trends, in both conventional and AB free farms an increase of costs/kg for vaccination and feed additives as well a decrease trend on costs of pharmaceuticals is shown. These results suggest that although a higher effort was done in AB free farms, both production systems showed an increasing use of preventive measures and a decreasing use of pharmaceuticals during the last 5 years. No data are available for the year 2016 for AB free farms because first AB free farms started their production in 2017.

Table 9-1 costs of medication per kg of live animal reared in conventional farms, 2016-2020

Year	vaccines	pharmaceuticals	feed additives	disinfectants	Total
2016	0,0065	0,0240	-	-	0,0305
2017	0,0090	0,0140	0,0027	0,0027	0,0283
2018	0,0114	0,0117	0,0031	0,0012	0,0274
2019	0,0110	0,0098	0,0034	0,0017	0,0259
2020	0,0100	0,0094	0,0032	0,0023	0,0250

Table 9-2 cost of medication per kg of live animal reared in AB free farms, 2016-2020

Year	vaccines	pharmaceuticals	feed additives	disinfectants	total
2016	-	-	-	-	-
2017	0,0102	0,0091	0,0062	0,0028	0,0283
2018	0,0124	0,0044	0,0060	0,0013	0,0240
2019	0,0131	0,0050	0,0052	0,0021	0,0254
2020	0,0129	0,0063	0,0048	0,0018	0,0259

In Table 9-3 and

Table 9-4 the production performances (number, age (days) and weight of animals (kg), feed conversion ratio, percentage of mortality in the first week of life as well as in the all production period) are shown along with production costs (total production per kg of live animal which include the costs of chicks, feed, contract farming and medication) in conventional and AB free farms. AB free production showed a slightly lower feed conversion ratio in 2017-2018, but equal in the 2019-2020 and a considerably lower percentage of mortality than conventional production. This suggests that in AB free production the health status of animals was favoured without any reduction of growth performances.

The slightly lower weight of the animals at the end of the production cycle is related to the fact that in Ab-free systems females are mostly reared for a shorter period and achieve a lower weight. Interestingly, no significant differences were observed in relation to total cost per kg comparing the two systems. Regarding the trends, the feed conversion ratio positively decreased in both systems suggesting that there was a common effort in finding optimal rearing conditions to reach the optimal parameters suggested in the reference tables of genetic breeds.

Table 9-3 production performances and total production costs of conventional farms, 2016-2020

Year	N° animals	Age (mean - days)	Weight (mean - kg)	FCR*	% Mortality 1st week	% Mortality	total cost €/kg
2016	12.608.253	45,65	2,697	1,858	1,54%	5,85%	€ 1,011
2017	12.742.752	45,63	2,704	1,811	1,60%	5,78%	€ 0,989
2018	15.034.913	46,02	2,729	1,809	1,47%	5,16%	€ 0,997
2019	15.408.102	45,84	2,857	1,757	1,41%	5,00%	€ 0,981
2020°	12.413.348	46,61	2,893	1,760	1,40%	5,34%	€ 0,971

*FCR: feed conversion ratio, ° data related to January – August 2020

Table 9-4 production performances and total production costs of AB free farms, 2016-2020

Year	N° animals	Age (mean - days)	Weight (mean - kg)	FCR*	% Mortality 1st week	% Mortality	total cost €/kg
2016	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2017	767.867	45,12	2,507	1,791	1,44%	4,90%	€ 1,016
2018	4.395.448	45,20	2,548	1,797	1,20%	4,71%	€ 1,005
2019	7.385.921	43,91	2,441	1,758	1,17%	3,76%	€ 0,994
2020°	6.661.749	45,46	2,515	1,776	1,04%	3,78%	€ 0,991

*FCR: feed conversion ratio, ° data related to January – August 2020

In conclusion, apart from a first important economic effort in restructuring and implementing forced ventilation and windows, the principle of AB free poultry systems has been shown to be sustainable from an economic, health and zootechnical point of view thus further promoting the already observed increasing trend (from 6% in 2017 to 48% in 2019) of the percentage of AB free broiler production over the total production.

10 Case study analysis: Vietnam

10.1 Poultry production in Vietnam

10.1.1 Quantification of AMU from the literature

This study did not assess the quantity of AMU on each farm nor for which disease farmers use AB or the molecule used. However, some elements can be found in the literature. It is often difficult to obtain reliable data on AMU, especially in LMICs. A report from Centre for Disease Dynamics Economics and Policy estimated that the total antimicrobial use in 2020 in animals in Vietnam was 1 016,23 tonnes and that this is expected to increase to 1 177.90 tonnes by 2030 (Sriram et al. 2021). This estimation is consistent with the steady increase of the total chicken population in Vietnam and the intensification of practices. Carrique-Mas et al. estimated the total AMs usage in poultry production in Vietnam based on data obtained from a published quantitative survey (Carrique-Mas et al. 2020). This study estimated the total AMU at 265.1 mg/kg in chicken production, meaning a total of 185.5 tonnes of total AMU annually.

Concerning active principles, Carrique-Mas et al., found that the AMs used by most farms were, in descending order: polypeptides, tetracyclines and penicillins. The most commonly used compound were penicillins, lincosamides, quinolones and sulphonamides/trimethoprim (Carrique-Mas et al. 2015). This study reported usage of highly critical antibiotics (quinolones, macrolides, polypeptides).

10.1.2 Diseases and stages in which AMs are more used

Truong et al., conducted 26 semi-structured group interviews with farmers and drug shop owners in 2017-2018. They identified three chicken diseases most prevalent in farms: Gumboro disease, mycoplasma and Newcastle disease. Bacterial diseases for which AMs are more used if the disease is present in the farm are pasteurellosis, colibacillosis and mycoplasmosis. Viral diseases include highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza, Newcastle Disease, Gumboro Disease. Other diseases include hepatitis, coccidiosis and aspergillosis (Truong et al. 2019).

ABs are more used in the early stage of the production (Truong et al. 2019) and it was reported that broilerfarms are a risk factor to higher AMU (per week/per chicken) compared to layers or dual purpose production in a study conducted with 208 households (10 – 200 chickens) and small scale farms (200 – 2000 chickens) (Carrique-Mas et al. 2015).

10.2 Case study, intensive production system

10.2.1 Background

The intensive production system represents a small number of farms in Vietnam (about 5%) but provides 26% of the total meat (Cuong et al. 2019) and is expected to increase in the coming years. Intensive production system can be divided into two groups: farmers under contract to a chicken company and independent farmers. The first one is vertically integrated, where companies provide all inputs to

farmers (chickens, feed, drugs, technical advice) and are in charge of selling the products to live market or to supermarkets, collective restaurant, fast food outlets. Chickens are usually slaughtered in their own slaughterhouse. Farmers are paid according to the number of chickens raised to the end with a fixed price (independent of market fluctuations). The chickens are not owned by farmers, but they own the buildings (except for some farms that are also owned by the company). Chickens are foreign bred and raised indoors with all the facilities including automatic feed and water distribution. Chickens are fed industrial feed formulated to suit their age. They have a protocol of biosecurity and a restricted access to the farms (only vets and staffs), a pest control program and a regular cleaning and disinfection of the buildings. Chickens are vaccinated according to the protocol of the company, but the study described below showed that they are not dewormed frequently and do not receive anticoccidial drugs. Several employees are working in these farms. This job represents their main activity, and they usually have less than 5 years of farming experience.

For independent farmers raising chickens in an industrial system, the main difference is the source of inputs and outputs. They usually buy feed and drugs directly from feed and drug companies and chickens are sold to middlemen for the wholesale markets or to slaughterhouse.

10.2.2 Methods

One hundred and eighteen farms were surveyed in two districts of Hanoi province in North Vietnam and three districts of Long An province in South Vietnam between May and June 2020 (Figure 10-1). Farms were randomly selected following a stratified sampling based on the flock size and the status (family or contracted to a chicken company) to include all production systems. The questionnaire interviews were conducted into twenty eight backyard farms (<100 chickens, family), 28 semi-intensive (100-2000 chickens, family), 37 intensive family (>2000, family) and 25 intensive contract (>2000, contract).

Figure 10-1: map of the study zone Hanoi province (Red River region) and Long An (Mekong Delta region)

Questions were addressed to farmers raising laying hens, broilers, or roosters through a close questionnaire on tablet using the software KoboToolBox. The duration of the interviews was between 45

min and 1h30. Questions focused on farming practices and included socio-demographic, economic and technical data (farm management, health management and biosecurity) and on antibiotic usage.

Farmers were divided into two subsets: farmers who don't use antibiotics (n=7) and farmers who use antibiotics (n=111). The following statistical analysis were performed only on farmers using AB. Data were analysed on R software on the package FactoMineR, FactoExtra and FactoShiny. Qualitative key variables were firstly selected and divided into two categories: AB usage and farming practices. A first multiple correspondence analysis (MCA) followed by a hierarchical clustering (HC) was performed on the 18 AB usage variables. From this result, a new variable with 3 categories called *ABU patterns* was created. A second MCA and HC were then performed on the 62 farming practices variables with *ABU patterns* and socio-demographic and economic variables introduced as supplementary.

10.2.3 Results

10.2.3.1 Clustering

The MCA on *ABU patterns* was performed in 18 key variables related to:

- knowledge: definition of antibiotic, source of training on ABU and date of the last training on ABU;
- usage: reason to use an AB (treatment, prevention, growth promotion), give feed that contain antibiotic;
- advice: first source of advice, second source of advice, how farmers receive advice;
- financial: place of purchase of antibiotics, share of all veterinary products in total expenditure, share of antibiotic in the total veterinary products expenditure;
- practice: dosage vs product instruction, duration vs. product instruction, withdrawal time vs. product instruction, usage of the leftover, record the information on the treatment

Three *ABU patterns* were identified: “**company**” (n=24), “**independent**” (n=28) and “**drugstore**” (n=59) corresponding to different AB usage. The three groups are described by the categories of variables that are statistically significant (p<0.05) to characterize each group in the Table 10-1.

Table 10-1: Description of the three group antibiotic usage pattern obtained after a MCA and HC on 18 AB usage variables

ABU patterns	Description
Company (n=24)	Farmers buy the antibiotics from the chicken company. Diagnostic and advice on AB use are given by a professional from the company directly in the farm. Farmers use ABs (dosage, duration, withdrawal time) according to the instruction of the professional or the product. Farmers received training on ABU from both public and private source and their last training was less than 6 months ago.
Independent (n=28)	Farmers buy antibiotics from retailers. No professionals are coming to the farms to perform a diagnostic and they use antibiotics following their own experience or in second choice from the advice of retailers. They give a higher dosage than the product's instruction and shorter duration. Their last training on ABU was more than 6 months ago from a public source and they don't know the definition of an antibiotic. AB are used for treatment and prevention.
Drugstore (n=59)	Farmers buy antibiotics from retailers (local veterinarian or drugstore that are small shops selling various products including antibiotics). Advice on AB use are given by the drugstore seller or local veterinarian directly in the drugstore or over the phone. They use AB (dosage and duration) according to the instruction of the professional or the product. They don't receive any training on ABU. AB are used for treatment.

A second MCA was performed on 47 active variables related to:

- farm management (15): employee, other animals, breed, flock, housing, recording of information on the management;
- inputs (8): feed, alternative medicines, DOCs or pullet;
- outputs (5): way to market the product, final consumers, manure management;
- biosecurity (10);
- health management (8).

Seventeen variables related to socio-demographic and economic data were introduced as supplementary as well as the *ABU patterns* created from the first MCA/HC.

Three groups of *farming practices*: “**contract**” (n=26), “**family commercial**” (n=74) and “**household**” (n=11) corresponding to different production systems were identified from the MCA/HC. The three groups are described with the categories of variables that characterized significantly the most the group in the Table 10-2.

Table 10-2 Description of the three group farming group obtained after a MCA and HCA and the association with ABU patterns

Farming practices	Description	ABU patterns
Contract (n=26)	Indoor, exotic breed, use complete feed, input/output from chicken company, biosecurity, vaccination (advice from company), <30 years old, main activity	Company (95%, v-test=9.03*)
Family commercial (n=74)	In and out, crossbreed, complete feed, feed agency, buy day-old-chicks from local hatchery, sell to middle-men, no biosecurity, disinfection, >15y experience, 25/50% income	Independent (93%, v-test=3.57) Drugstore (80%, v-test=3.05)
Household (n=11)	Free range, local breed, scavenging, multiple age, day-old-chicks are from their own production, consume their own products, direct selling, no vaccination, low biosecurity, chicken production is not their main activity	Drugstore (19%, v-test=3.44)

* : 95% of company farms are in the group contract

Figure 10-2 represents the result of the MCA/HCA on the farming practices variables with ABU patterns introduced as supplementary. Company ABU patterns is associated to contract farms, independent and drugstore to family commercial farms and drugstore to household (Table 10-2).

Figure 10-2: Projection of the 111 Vietnamese chicken farms that use AB on the first two dimensions within the 3 groups identified through HC realized on farming practices variables.

In black: categories of variables that most characterize the farms; in bold green: ABU patterns (supplementary variable)

10.2.3.2 Results of the “contract” farms associated with ABU patterns group

“Contract” farms correspond to intensive production systems. In this group, 92,3% of the farms had more than 2000 chickens and were under contract with a company and 7,7% had more than 2000 chickens but were not under contract. It is associated to the “company” ABU pattern (95% of the “company” farm groups are in the “contract” farming practice group) that is described in the Table 10-1. In this group the variable on the reason to use antibiotic (treatment, prevention, growth promotion) is not significant. However, on the 11 farmers that use AB in prevention, all give AB at arrival of the animals, 6 when the weather change and 2 before or after the vaccination and in total 9 farmers have a written protocol to prevent diseases. The technician or veterinarian from the company came directly to the farm, but in 21 farms the professionals are performing an autopsy, in 16 they do a clinical examination and in 6 farms they take a sample.

10.2.3.3 Results of the “family commercial” groups associated with the ABU patterns “independent” and “drugstore”

In the group “family commercial” farms, no farms were under contract to a company. 47.3% percent of the farms had more than 2000 chickens, 28% had between 100 and 2000 chickens and 14,9% had less than 100 chickens. It is associated to the ABU patterns “independent” (93% of the “independent” farm groups are in the farming practice’s group “family commercial”) and “drugstore” (80% of the “drugstore” farm groups are in the “family commercial” farming practice group).

10.2.3.4 Results of the “household” farms associated with ABU pattern group “drugstore”

In the group “household”, all the farms had less than 100 chickens. It is associated to the ABU patterns “drugstore” (19% of the “drugstore” farm group are in the “household” farming practice group).

10.3 Case study, organic production system

10.3.1 Background

Organic production was already present in Vietnam in the early 90s, but referred more to a traditional way of producing food. It started to be industrialized in 2004 with the creation of a network under the project “Developing a Framework for Production and Marketing of Organic Agriculture in Vietnam” (www.adda.dk), which was a cooperation between the NGO Agricultural Development Denmark-Asia (ADDA) and the Vietnamese National Farmers Union (VNFU), this project ended in 2012. Specifications were developed by the NGO IFOAM (International Federation of Agriculture Movements) and these standards were recognized by the MARD (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development) under the regulation 10-TCN602-2006 (Whitney et al., 2014b). However, no regulation circular was issued following this decree.

Participatory Guarantee System (PGS) is an organic certificate developed by IFOAM based on the active participation of stakeholders. In Vietnam, PGS was developed under the ADDA-VNFU project and recognized by the stakeholders in 2008. However, in 2007 PGS in Vietnam was still considered as an ongoing process (Pham & Marie-Vivien, 2017). Based on the IFOAM standards and the regulation issued by the MARD in 2006, the PGS Organic Standards were developed between 2011 and 2013 (Whitney et al., 2014a). Two documents are available: PGS standards for Producers and Retailers. Two years later the PGS in Vietnam was recognized by the IFOAM.

The Vietnamese Organic Agriculture Organization (VAOO) was established in 2011 and recognized by the Ministry of Home Affairs. Through Workshop they initiate with the government of the MARD and MoST (Ministry of Sciences and Technology) to develop a decree (2018) and then a circular (2019) for organic standard. Later, in 2020, the Organic Agricultural Project 2020 – 2030 was signed by the Prime Minister.

Foreign organic production standards also exist in Vietnam (USDA organic standard, EU organic).

10.3.2 Methods

A literature review on organic production and quality labels was conducted in 2020 and will be continued in July 2021. Data were collected from scientific papers as well as from grey literature (reports, website, videos and newspapers). Between November 2019 and April 2020, 34 interviews were conducted on poultry production with key experts in the animal sector in Vietnam. Eighteen respondents were from public sector, including researchers from national research institution (6), national university (4), foreign research institution (3), international organization (2), government (2) and French embassy (1). Sixteen respondents worked in the private sector for feed company (4), pharmaceutical company (3), alternative products company (4) and for the food chain (5) including two participants in the production sector and three in the distribution. The semi-structured guide was developed around five main topics including existing typology of poultry farming systems, their general technical characteristics, the health management, regulation and control, strategies to reduce AMU and alternative production system. On this last topic, questions were asked about alternative medicines and organic production. Interviews were conducted by two researchers from CIRAD and one master student. The interviews lasted between 45min and 1h.

10.3.3 Results

Results of the interviews and literature indicate that no poultry farms are certified by the national organic standard. One farm had the PGS standard but stopped two years ago. However, poultry farms with an organic foreign standard (USDA, UE) exist. Organic production is currently a private initiative without any label mainly because organic food production is not yet developed in Vietnam. Farmers should produce their own organic feed. Indeed, according to the survey described in 9.1.1.1, 7 farmers didn't use antibiotics. On the 7 farms, 6 were backyard farms, raising less than 100 chickens for their own consumption. The other farm was an intensive farm under contract to a chicken company. But, none of these farms were selling their products with an organic or AB free label. More research needs to be done on these farms.

Chicken brands can also add on their products with statement such as “no use of prohibited substances”, “no antibiotic residues”. These products are sold in supermarkets or in specialized shops. The legislative framework surrounding these initiatives also needs to be studied.

Finally, some poultry farms have the national quality standard VietGAHP (Vietnamese Good Animal Husbandry Practices). This standard refers to a quality standard that guarantees products without AB residues. During the interviews, it was reported that consumers don't trust this label because of a lack of control.

To conclude, more research needs to be done in this production system and will be carried out in the future.

10.3.4 Comparison of poultry production systems in Vietnam

From the data collected at farm level, a comparison between production system and ABU patterns can be done. As a reminder, this study identified three ABU patterns each one associated to farming practices (i.e. production system). “Company” ABU patterns is associated to “contract” farms, “independent” and “drugstore” to family commercial farms and “drugstore” to household. Farms in contract are using antibiotics only according to the advice of a veterinarian or a technician working for the chicken company. In this case farmers have a low decision power and the level of AMU depends on the willingness of the chicken company (some companies are already promoting a prudent AMU to fight against AMR). Family commercial farms that are raising chickens in lower intensive system for commercial purpose have heterogeneous ABU patterns. On one side, there are farmers that seem to misuse antibiotics, which are used for prevention without any professional advice and with an improper dosage, according to their own experience. On the other side, there are farmers that use antibiotics according to the drugstore advice without any clinical examination in most of the times and only for treatment, both metaphylactic and curative. Finally, household farms that raise chickens for their own consumption also ask advice to the drugstore. To assess the level of AMU for this group it would be needed to explore ABU patterns among retailers (local vet, drugstore). In the literature it has been reported higher quantities of AMs in household farms (between 10 and 200 chickens) than on small to medium farms (200 – 2000 chickens) (Carrique-Mas et al. 2015).

From the semi-structured interviews, experts always point family commercial farms as having the most AB misuse (no respect of dosage or withdrawal time), intensive farms use systematically antibiotics whereas backyard farms use only antibiotic for treatment. About farmers that raise chickens under the labels “no use of prohibited substance” or “no antibiotic residues”, this mean that that farmers comply

with the withdrawal time and that antibiotics prohibited by law are not used but, antibiotics can still be used for treatment and prevention. About organic production, according to the National Organic Standard, antibiotics should not be used. And, in the PGS Organic Standards, antibiotic can be used only if animals are sick and if preventive and alternative practices are not effective.

11 Conclusions

Difficulties in access reliable and good quality data on antimicrobial use and resistance, stratified by production systems, species, farms and veterinarians is one of the main problems that the fight against antimicrobial resistance faces today. Without such information it becomes extremely hard to evaluate and find the sources of the problem and the feebleness of the systems. Thus targeted actions and policies that would be much more efficient in terms of resource use for combating the problem, became also impracticable or exceptionally expensive. Initiatives to collect and report AMU data combining several countries, such as that of OIE and ESVAC are essential for creating a database, to standardize the methods and to create a benchmarking system. In possession of this information, international institutions and national governments will be able to have a better overview of the problem, compare the results and implement joint or individual actions for reducing AMU.

The first efforts from all countries might be attributing increased responsibility to the stakeholders involved in AMU: pharma industry, integrating processing companies (feed companies), veterinarians and farmers. Then implement “compulsory” data reporting/collection systems, which can be enabled by the use of digital tools, when possible. This will provide real-time AMU data and benchmarking. Stakeholders advocating for violation of data privacy are against such system. They must be remembered that AMR is a public health problem, which can be largely attributed to AMU in the livestock production, therefore it must be treated and fought as public. Imprudent practices must be identified and corrected, so the entire society don’t suffer the consequences of few negligent.

In this regard, data collection and quality information is just one of the first battles that needs to be won. The cases and data presented in this report evidence that some production systems and practices, especially those related to animal welfare and health could be favoured for achieving a prudent use of antimicrobials, a real decrease in their consumption and consequently an eventual decrease in antimicrobial resistance, where a direct relation between AMU and AMR is assumed. Further animal health and welfare regulations should be implemented. Furthermore, it could be useful to put the focus on preventive health work and optimal environments rather than on simply lowering of antibiotic use. With intersectional, collaborative work towards optimizing environments and prevent diseases, lower AMU should come as a secondary effect.

Nonetheless it becomes paramount to produce high quality information with data that is ‘accurate’, ‘complete’, ‘consistent’, ‘unique’ and ‘readily available’, so the information is useful and reliable. We can further extend these characteristics and include ‘standardized’, so comparability among regions, countries, sectors, farms, veterinarians, etc. is facilitated. This is especially important when the problem at stake is the same for everybody.

12 References

- . 2021. “OIE Annual Reports on the Use of Antimicrobial Agents in Animals. Better Understanding of the Global Situation.” Fourth Report. Paris: World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE).
- Anses, 2018, Suivi des ventes de médicaments vétérinaires contenant des antibiotiques en France en 2017, Rapport annuel, Edition scientifique, Novembre 2018, 100 p.
- Brewer, M. S., and M. Rojas. 2008. “Consumer Attitudes Toward Issues in Food Safety.” *Journal of Food Safety* 28 (1): 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-4565.2007.00091.x>.
- Carrique-Mas, Juan J, Nguyen V. Trung, Ngo T. Hoa, Ho Huynh Mai, Tuyen H. Thanh, James I. Campbell, Jaap A. Wagenaar, Anita Hardon, Thai Quoc Hieu, and Constance Schultsz. 2015. “Antimicrobial Usage in Chicken Production in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam.” *Zoonoses and Public Health* 62 (April): 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.1111/zph.12165>.
- Carrique-Mas, Juan J., Marc Choisy, Nguyen Van Cuong, Guy Thwaites, and Stephen Baker. 2020. “An Estimation of Total Antimicrobial Usage in Humans and Animals in Vietnam.” *Antimicrobial Resistance & Infection Control* 9 (1): 16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13756-019-0671-7>.
- Chauvin C. Bouvarel I., Beloeil P.A., Orand J.P., Guillemot D., Sanders P., 2005. *Vet. Res.*, 36: 13-25; Chauvin C. Querrec M., Perrot A., Guillemot D., Sanders P., 2008. *J. Vet. Pharm. and Ther*, 31(4): 301-311. ; Chauvin C., 2009. *J. Vet. Pharm. and Ther*, 32(suppl.1): 111-112.
- Chauvin, 2012, Rapport d’études sur l’utilisation des antibiotiques en 2012 (not published)
- Chevalier D, Nicolas C, Amand G., 2015. Le bâtiment d’élevage, un outil stratégique pour la filière avicole. <https://www.itavi.asso.fr/content/le-batiment-delevage-un-outil-strategique-pour-la-filiere-avicole>
- Chevance Anne, Delphine Urban, Gérard Moulin, 2019. Cessions d’aliments médicamenteux contenant des antibiotiques en France Analyse des résultats des deux premiers trimestres de l’année 2018.
- Cuong, Nguyen Van, Doan Hoang Phu, Nguyen Thi Bich Van, Bao Dinh Truong, Bach Tuan Kiet, Bo Ve Hien, Ho Thi Viet Thu, et al. 2019. “High-Resolution Monitoring of Antimicrobial Consumption in Vietnamese Small-Scale Chicken Farms Highlights Discrepancies Between Study Metrics.” *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 6 (June): 174. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00174>.
- Dezat E, Dennery G., Rousset N., 2013. Intérêts et mise en œuvre du bétonnage des sols en volailles de chair. <https://www.itavi.asso.fr/content/interets-et-mise-en-oeuvre-du-betonnage-des-sols-en-volailles-de-chair>
- Dezat E., Gauhier-Austerlitz D., 2020, Gestion des litières et du fumier chez les aviculteurs bretons <http://www.bretagne.synagri.com/synagri/gestion-des-litieres-en-aviculture>
- Dezat E., Nicolas C., Pattier S., 2015, Impact de l’utilisation d’échangeurs de chaleur sur les performances technico-économiques des volailles de chair. <https://www.itavi.asso.fr/content/impact-de-lutilisation-dechangeurs-de-chaleur-sur-les-performances-technico-economiques-des>
- ECDC/EFSA/EMA. 2017. “ECDC/EFSA/EMA Second Joint Report on the Integrated Analysis of the Consumption of Antimicrobial Agents and Occurrence of Antimicrobial Resistance in Bacteria from Humans and Food-Producing Animals.” *EFSA Journal* 15 (7): e04872. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4872>.
- ESVAC. 2020. “Sales of Veterinary Antimicrobial Agents in 31 European Countries in 2018,” 109.
- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, European Food Safety Authority, and European Medicines Agency. 2015. “ECDC/EFSA/EMA First Joint Report on the Integrated Analysis of the Consumption of Antimicrobial Agents and Occurrence of Antimicrobial Resistance in Bacteria from Humans and Food-Producing Animals: Joint Interagency Antimicrobial Consumption and Resistance Analysis (JIACRA) Report.” *EFSA Journal* 13 (1): 4006. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2015.4006>.

- Gery-Choquet A., Rousset N, Leblanc-Maridor M., Bonnet-Beaugrand F., 2019, Freins et motivations des éleveurs de poulets à mettre en place des mesures préventives contre la colibacillose aviaire et typologie des éleveurs en vue d’apporter un conseil adapté, <https://www.itavi.asso.fr/content/freins-et-motivations-des-eleveurs-de-poulets-mettre-en-place-des-mesures-preventives-contre>
- Hercule J., 2020, Évolutions du parc de bâtiments de production de volailles de chair. <https://www.itavi.asso.fr/content/evolutions-du-parc-de-batiments-de-production-de-volailles-de-chair-3>
- ITAVI, 2019, Performances techniques et coûts de production en volaille de chair – résultats 2018. <https://www.itavi.asso.fr/content/performances-techniques-et-couts-de-production-en-volailles-de-chair-resultats-2019>
- Klein, Eili Y, Maja Milkowska-Shibata, Katie K Tseng, Mike Sharland, Sumanth Gandra, Céline Pulcini, and Ramanan Laxminarayan. 2020. “Assessment of WHO Antibiotic Consumption and Access Targets in 76 Countries, 2000–15: An Analysis of Pharmaceutical Sales Data.” *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, July. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(20\)30332-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30332-7).
- Klein, Eili Y., Thomas P. Van Boeckel, Elena M. Martinez, Suraj Pant, Sumanth Gandra, Simon A. Levin, Herman Goossens, and Ramanan Laxminarayan. 2018. “Global Increase and Geographic Convergence in Antibiotic Consumption between 2000 and 2015.” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 115 (15): E3463–70. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1717295115>.
- Leroy, L, Hercule, J, 2020, « Panorama des filières avicoles biologiques en Europe », *TeMA n°52, Technique et Marchés Avicoles*, ITAVI - <https://www.itavi.asso.fr/content/panorama-des-filieres-avicoles-biologiques-en-europe>
- Lusk, Jayson L., F. Bailey Norwood, and J. Ross Pruitt. 2006. “Consumer Demand for a Ban on Antibiotic Drug Use in Pork Production.” *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 88 (4): 1015–33. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8276.2006.00913.x>.
- Nicolas C, 2019, Enquête sols béton en volailles de chair. https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwj0s_3CxuTuAhXHBGMBHQJCBqEQFjAMegQI-AxAC&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.chambres-agriculture-bretagne.fr%2Fsynagri%2Fact-batiment-volaille-enquete-sur-les-sols-beton&usg=AOvVaw2sFQEytFq6yLB_2tPKRxDD
- Nicolas C., 2011, la statique à lanterneau cède du terrain. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwjzrP7Rr-TuAhWLx4UKHcybCDoQFjACegQIARAC&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.chambres-agriculture-bretagne.fr%2Fca1%2FPJ.nsf%2FTECHPJPARCLEF%2F16555%3FOpenDocument&usg=AOvVaw3IO1bfXdFxxkudtISnJ-qJb>
- Nielsen, Cecilie Liv, Hanne Kongsted, Jan Tind Sørensen, and Mogens Agerbo Krogh. 2021. “Antibiotic and Medical Zinc Oxide Usage in Danish Conventional and Welfare-Label Pig Herds in 2016–2018.” *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 189 (April): 105283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2021.105283>.
- OIE. 2020. “OIE Annual Reports on the Use of Antimicrobial Agents in Animals. Better Understanding of the Global Situation.” Fourth Report. Paris: World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE).
- Poizat, A., F. Bonnet-Beaugrand, A. Rault, C. Fourichon, and N. Bareille. 2017. “Antibiotic Use by Farmers to Control Mastitis as Influenced by Health Advice and Dairy Farming Systems.” *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 146 (October): 61–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2017.07.016>.
- Puterflam J., Kempf I., Delannoy S., Yousfi L., Le bouquin S., Galliot P., Balaine L., Souillard S., 2019. La colibacillose en élevage de poulet s de chair. Une description dans 80 élevages du Grand-

- Ouest. TeMa, Octobre – Novembre - Décembre 2019 – n°52 : 19-23
<https://www.itavi.asso.fr/content/la-colibacillose-en-poulet-de-chair>
- Rousset N., Carré Y., Richard A., Brice Y. et Chauvin C., 2019. RefA²vi : vers la formalisation d'un réseau de références professionnelles français sur l'utilisation des antibiotiques en exploitation avicoles. Treizièmes Journées de la Recherche Avicole et Palmipèdes à Foie Gras, Tours, 20 et 21 mars 2019
- Smith-Spangler, Crystal, Margaret L. Brandeau, Grace E. Hunter, J. Clay Bavinger, Maren Pearson, Paul J. Eschbach, Vandana Sundaram, et al. 2012. "Are Organic Foods Safer or Healthier Than Conventional Alternatives?: A Systematic Review." *Annals of Internal Medicine* 157 (5): 348. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-157-5-201209040-00007>.
- Smith, David L., Jonathan Dushoff, and J. Glenn Morris Jr. 2005. "Agricultural Antibiotics and Human Health." *PLOS Medicine* 2 (8): e232. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.0020232>.
- Sneeringer, Stacy, James M. Mac Donald, Nigel Key, William D. Mc Bride, and Kenneth Mathews. 2015. "Economics of Antibiotic Use in U.S. Livestock Production." USDA, Economic Research Report Number 200.
- Sriram, Aditi, Erta Kalanxhi, Geetanjali Kapoor, Jessica Craig, Ruchita Balasubramanian, Sehr Brar, Nicola Criscuolo, et al. 2021. "The State of the World's Antibiotics 2021 : A Global Analysis of Antimicrobial Resistance and Its Drivers." Washington DC: Center for Disease Dynamics Economics and Policy. <https://cddep.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/The-State-of-the-Worlds-Antibiotics-in-2021.pdf>.
- Tang, Karen L, Niamh P Caffrey, Diego B Nóbrega, Susan C Cork, Paul E Ronksley, Herman W Barkema, Alicia J Polachek, et al. 2017. "Restricting the Use of Antibiotics in Food-Producing Animals and Its Associations with Antibiotic Resistance in Food-Producing Animals and Human Beings: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis." *The Lancet Planetary Health* 1 (8): e316–27. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(17\)30141-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(17)30141-9).
- Taylor, Louise H., Sophia M. Latham, and Mark E.J. Woolhouse. 2001. "Risk Factors for Human Disease Emergence." Edited by M. E. J. Woolhouse and C. Dye. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences* 356 (1411): 983–89. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2001.0888>.
- Truong, Dinh Bao, Hoang Phu Doan, Vinh Khanh Doan Tran, Van Cuong Nguyen, Tuan Kiet Bach, Chalalai Rueanghiran, Aurélie Binot, et al. 2019. "Assessment of Drivers of Antimicrobial Usage in Poultry Farms in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam: A Combined Participatory Epidemiology and Q-Sorting Approach." *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 6 (March): 84. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00084>.
- Van Boeckel, Thomas P, Sumanth Gandra, Ashvin Ashok, Quentin Caudron, Bryan T Grenfell, Simon A Levin, and Ramanan Laxminarayan. 2014. "Global Antibiotic Consumption 2000 to 2010: An Analysis of National Pharmaceutical Sales Data." *The Lancet Infectious Diseases* 14 (8): 742–50. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(14\)70780-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(14)70780-7).
- Van Boeckel, Thomas P., Charles Brower, Marius Gilbert, Bryan T. Grenfell, Simon A. Levin, Timothy P. Robinson, Aude Teillant, and Ramanan Laxminarayan. 2015. "Global Trends in Antimicrobial Use in Food Animals." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 112 (18): 5649–54. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1503141112>.
- Van Horne, P.L.M, 2018, Competitiveness of the EU poultry meat sector, base year 2017, international comparison of production costs
- Willis, Laurie Denyer, and Clare Chandler. 2019. "Quick Fix for Care, Productivity, Hygiene and Inequality: Reframing the Entrenched Problem of Antibiotic Overuse." *BMJ Global Health* 4 (4): e001590. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2019-001590>.

